

Puerto Rico Department of Education (English): Science - Grade K, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, A1, A2, B1, B2, C1

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.K.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		Interdependent relationships in ecosystems: animals, plants and their environment
EXPECTATION	K.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Matter organization and energy flow in organisms.
INDICATOR	K.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and level organization of matter.
	K.B.CB1.EM.1.	Distinguishes between living things and non-living objects and establishes that living things are different and have distinctive parts when identifying them (legs, head, wings) that give them a shape. Ex: body parts of humans, chickens, butterflies, and others.
	K.B.CB1.EM.2.	Describes and classifies animals and their offspring. Ex: mare- foal, hen- chick, cow- calf, humans- children.
	K.B.CB1.EM.3.	Describes the importance of healthy eating to keep the body systems healthy.
INDICATOR	K.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	K.B.CB1.IE.1.	Distinguishes between what is food and what is not. Recognizes that food is the primary source of energy for organisms. Identifies the principal parts of a plant. Makes observations about the relationships between plants, animals and humans. Ex: the study of food-chains.
	K.B.CB1.IE.2.	Describes patterns on what living things need to survive when making observations about the differences between plants, animals and humans. Ex: includes different types of food; the animal's need of water and space; plant's need of light; land and water.
	K.B.CB1.IE.3.	Distinguishes and describes different types of habitats in which living beings live and adapt.
	K.B.CB1.IE.4.	Evaluates different models regarding the adequate habits to promote health and growth. Can be done through drawings or theatrical representations. Ex: to keep a healthy body: eat well, rest, exercise, good hygiene habits.
INDICATOR	K.B.CB1.CC.	Conservation and change
	K.B.CB1.CC.1.	Identifies change patterns in the life-cycle of living beings (growth, length, weight, height) and recognizes reproduction as a form of living being's conservation.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.K.F.CF.	Physical Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure and function of matter
EXPECTATION	K.F.CF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties
INDICATOR	K.F.CF1.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	K.F.CF1.EM.1.	Recognizes different types of matter according to their physical properties and groups them according to one or

		more of their properties. Ex: physical properties can include texture, shape, color and size.
INDICATOR	K.F.CF1.IE. K.F.CF1.IE.1.	Interactions and energy Predicts and corroborates how matter will react to hot and cold stimuli (heating and cooling).
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions: pull and push
EXPECTATION	K.F.CF2.	Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - force and movement; types of interactions; stability and instability in physical systems.
INDICATOR	K.F.CF2.IE. K.F.CF2.IE.1. K.F.CF2.IE.2.	Interactions and energy Performs research to compare the effects of different forces or directions on the movement of an object when pushing or pulling. Analyzes data to determine how a change of force affects speed or direction of an object and provides evidence on the effect.
DOMAIN		Sound, light and heat
EXPECTATION	K.F.CF4.	Waves and their applications to information transference technologies - properties of waves; electromagnetic radiation; information and instrumentation technologies.
INDICATOR	K.F.CF4.IE. K.F.CF4.IE.1.	Interactions and energy Develops arguments based on evidence of the importance and use of light, sound and heat in everyday student activities.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.K.T.CT.	Earth and Space Sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems: cycles and patterns
EXPECTATION	K.T.CT1.	The place of Earth in the Universe - the universe and the stars; Earth and the solar system.
INDICATOR	K.T.CT1.IE. K.T.CT1.IE.1. K.T.CT1.IE.2. K.T.CT1.IE.3. K.T.CT1.IE.4.	Interactions and energy Makes observations to determine the effect of sunlight on Earth's surface. Examples of Earth's surface can be sand, rocks, water, as well as temperature and the effects on objects, plants and human beings to create shadows. Uses tools and materials to design and create a structure that serves to reduce the Sun's effect on temperature of an area. Uses observations to predict patterns on Earth caused by different systems of this planet; this includes climate patterns, day and night, seasons and lunar phases. Recognizes and identifies the position of planets in our solar system.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	K.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - materials and systems of Earth; water function in the processes of Earth's surface; meteorology and atmospheric conditions.
INDICATOR	K.T.CT2.EM.	Structures and organization levels of matter

	K.T.CT2.EM.1.	Recognizes and describes the different materials that compose Earth's systems. Examples of these materials include soil, rocks, water and atmosphere; these influence climatic events.
INDICATOR	K.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	K.T.CT2.IE.1.	Makes observations about the local weather conditions to describe climate patterns.
	K.T.CT2.IE.2.	Describes different climatic events to make predictions of weather conditions and be prepared to react and respond to these events.
DOMAIN		Human impact
EXPECTATION	K.T.CT3.	Earth and human activity - Dangers of nature; human impact on Earth's systems.
INDICATOR	K.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	K.T.CT3.CC.1.	Analyzes the ways in which humans can reduce waste and pollution of their environment.
	K.T.CT3.CC.2.	Recognizes climate characteristics of Puerto Rico. Differentiates different weather states (ex: more than a week, makes observations of weather conditions for a while).
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.1.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		From molecules to organisms: structures and processes
EXPECTATION	1.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Structure and function; growth and development of organisms; information process
INDICATOR	1.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	1.B.CB1.EM.1.	Creates models on structural similarities and differences between humans, plants and animals (can use drawings, sculptures, or theatrical representations). Uses patterns in the basic structures and recognizes diversity.
	1.B.CB1.EM.2.	Makes observations in order to describe the structures that plants and animals need to survive and grow. Examples include parts of animals: beaks, wings, legs, fins; parts of plants: stems, leaves, roots, bark; parts of flowers. Constructs models with the purpose of studying the connection between the different structures and the function of these. Examples of models include drawings, models, dioramas, simple sentences. Examples of connections include movement and parts of plants and organisms, among others.
	1.B.CB1.EM.3.	Differentiates between sensorial structures of different animals and associates the body parts with sensorial information (humans and animals). Recognizes that there are specialized doctors to treat and cure different senses of the body.
	1.B.CB1.EM.4.	Constructs models to show that the human body is a system of parts that interact at different levels (skeletal, respiratory and digestive, etc; and the organs that

		compose them).
INDICATOR	1.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	1.B.CB1.IE.1.	Use materials to design a solution to a human problem by mimicking how plants and/or animals use their external parts to help them survive, grow, and meet their needs. (biomimicry) Examples of human problems that can be resolved observing nature can include: designing camouflage clothing or equipment to protect cyclists that mimics the shell of a turtle, nutshells, or animal scales (skin); stabilizing structures such as animals' tails or plants' roots'; scaring off intruders by having thorns on stems and feathers on animals.
	1.B.CB1.IE.2.	Expresses the benefits to the human body when having good hygiene, healthy eating, and exercise habits. Examples include brushing teeth, washing hair, cleaning the house, selecting healthy food alternatives, playing outdoors.
	1.B.CB1.IE.3.	Under supervision, reads texts and uses media to identify behavior patterns between parents and offspring, that help them survive. Some examples of conduct patterns may include the signals that offspring make (crying, tweeting, and other vocalizations) and the parents responses (how to feed, comfort and protect offspring).
DOMAIN		Heredity and variations in the characteristics
EXPECTATION	1.B.CB3.	Heredity and variations in characteristics - heredity of characteristics; variations in characteristics.
INDICATOR	1.B.CB3.EM.	Structures and organization levels of matter
	1.B.CB3.EM.1.	Makes observations, describes and groups plants, animals and human beings according to characteristics that make them similar or different (ex: difference between animals and plants; between animals and humans; between plants and humans).
	1.B.CB3.EM.2.	Develops logical arguments about the fact that plants and offspring resemble their parents, but are not exactly the same. Examples of patterns can include the characteristics that some plants and animals share. . Examples of observations can include leaves, flowers, roots of a same plant, that are similar in shape but different in size, thickness, color and appearance; a particular litter of dogs, cats or other animals that look like their parents but are not exactly the same.
INDICATOR	1.B.CB3.CC.	Conservation and change
	1.B.CB3.CC.1.	Reviews information to understand life-cycles. Recognizes that reproduction is a conservation form among living things. Examples include research of plant, insect and fish life-cycles.
	1.B.CB3.CC.2.	Interprets related information with the biodiversity concept making emphasis on the appreciation of nature and life diversity. Researches on flora, native fauna and endangered species. Emphasis will be studying outdoors, outside the classroom.

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.1.FCF.	Physical Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure and properties of matter
EXPECTATION	1.F.CF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; chemical reactions
INDICATOR	1.F.CF1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	1.F.CF1.EM.1.	Recognizes the states of matter and identifies its characteristics. Ex: study the characteristics of sand, clay, gravel, leaves, flowers, a pencil, paper or ice, butter, alcohol, water or oil, honey and air, among others.
	1.F.CF1.EM.2.	Compares and contrasts and groups matter according to its physical properties. For example, the physical properties of matter can include size, color, malleability, porosity, shape, texture, hardness and flexibility.
	1.F.CF1.EM.3.	Identifies patterns on how matter reacts to cold and heat.
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions: pull and push
EXPECTATION	1.F.CF2.	Movement and stability: forces and interactions - Force and movement: types of interactions; stability and instability in physical systems
INDICATOR	1.F.CF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	1.F.CF2.IE.1.	Makes observations to explain how forces are manifested when using magnets when pulling or pushing an object.
INDICATOR	1.F.CF2.CC.	Conservation and change
	1.F.CF2.CC.1.	Makes research to determine how different forces can generate a relative change in the position or movement of an object.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	1.F.CF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; conservation and transference of energy; energy in chemical processes and everyday life.
INDICATOR	1.F.CF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	1.F.CF3.IE.1.	Recognizes that energy is important and is present in light, sound and heat. An example is the importance of the Sun to living things. Sun is necessary for the life of plants. A plant will die with the lack of sunlight or another source of energy.
DOMAIN		Waves: Light and sound
EXPECTATION	1.F.CF4.	Waves and their applications in technology to transfer information - Properties of waves; electromagnetic radiation; information and instrumentation technologies.
INDICATOR	1.F.CF4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	1.F.CF4.IE.1.	Performs research to show that the materials that vibrate can produce sound and that sound produces vibrations in certain materials.
	1.F.CF4.IE.2.	Performs observations to elaborate an oral and written argument based on evidence about the fact that objects

		are only visible when illuminated.
	1.F.CF4.IE.3.	Performs experiments to determine the effect of a ray of light through objects made of different materials.
	1.F.CF4.IE.4.	Builds a model that uses light or sound to resolve a situation of distance communication.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.1.T.CT.	Earth and Space Sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems: cycles and patterns
EXPECTATION	1.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - The universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	1.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	1.T.CT1.IE.1.	Makes observations about the Sun, the Moon and stars to describe patterns that can be predicted. Examples can include the relationship of the Sun with the year's seasons and the difference between day and night.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	1.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth's materials and systems; The function of water in the processes of Earth's surface; meteorology and atmospheric conditions
INDICATOR	1.T.CT2.EM.	Structure and level organization of matter.
	1.T.CT2.EM.1.	Compares the physical properties of Earth's materials to identify different possible uses of these materials in everyday life. Examples of Earth's materials can include sediments, rocks and water.
INDICATOR	1.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	1.T.CT2.IE.1.	Reviews information to establish the relationship between sunrise and sunset, cardinal points and the seasons (ex: the Sun rises in the East and sets in the West).
INDICATOR	1.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	1.T.CT2.CC.1.	Makes observations about patterns to predict the changes that occur in nature.
	1.T.CT2.CC.2.	Recognizes daily weather patterns and symbols using maps and weather forecasts
	1.T.CT2.CC.3.	Searches for information about the different instruments used to measure and predict the changes in time (weather). Ex: rain gauge (measures the quantity of rainfall), barometer (measures atmospheric pressure), anemometer (measures wind speed and direction), clock (indicates the hour) and thermometer (indicates temperature), among others.
	1.T.CT2.CC.4.	Analyzes information to argue about the effect of climate changes on living things.
DOMAIN		Human impact
EXPECTATION	1.T.CT3.	Earth and human activities - Human impact on Earth's systems
INDICATOR	1.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	1.T.CT3.CC.1.	Identifies and explains the practices of environmental

conservation (reduce, reuse and recycle) and the effects of pollution in the diverse natural resources (water, soil and air). (Reducing is the most important because it has the most direct and broad effect in the reduction of environmental damage. Reducing implies using less resources. Reusing means extending the life span of each product, when repairing or using an object for another purpose rather than the original. Recycling means using the matter of an object and transforming it into a new product. Ex: a carton box can be shredded and through an industrial process, turned into paper).

1.T.CT3.CC.2. Evaluates how human activities have increased environmental pollution and develops an action plan in his community.

CONTENT STANDARD

PR.2.B.CB.

Biological Sciences

DOMAIN

Interdependent relationships in ecosystems

EXPECTATION 2.B.CB2.

Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics - Interdependent relationships in ecosystems

INDICATOR 2.B.CB2.EM.

Structure and level organization of matter

2.B.CB2.EM.1.

Recognizes the importance of a flower in pollination as an important process in plant reproduction.

2.B.CB2.EM.2.

Makes direct observations of the parts of a plant (roots, stems, leaves, flower) to identify their basic functions. Gathers information to present models on how plant structures interact with pollination.

INDICATOR

2.B.CB2.IE.

Interactions and energy

2.B.CB2.IE.1.

Investigates the basic needs of plants: light, air and water. For example: plant several seeds in similar containers to observe the growth, controlling variables (darkness, light presence, types of soil, absence or presence of water); develop similar plants (species, size and leaf amount; planted in the same type of container and same amount of land); makes observations controlling variables (darkness, light presence, absence and presence of water)

2.B.CB2.IE.2.

Develops a simple model that shows the function that animals have when scattering seeds or pollinating plants.

2.B.CB2.IE.3.

Recognizes food-chains and describes the function of plants in them (food-chains). Plants are producers because they produce their own food - a type of sugar (glucose) - through the process of photosynthesis.

2.B.CB2.IE.4.

Classifies animals according to their feeding: herbivores eat plants; among these the fruitarians eat fruit and folivores especially eat leaves; carnivores eat other animal's flesh; omnivores are organisms that eat all kinds of food. There are other types of organisms (bacteria and fungi) that are decomposers in the food-chain. The decomposers are organisms that feed on the dead tissue or cells called detritus; these accomplish an important function in the ecosystem.

EXPECTATION	2.B.CB4.	Biological evolution: unity and diversity - Humans and biodiversity
INDICATOR	2.B.CB4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	2.B.CB4.IE.1.	Recognizes ecosystems as places where the living and non-living interact. Identifies different aquatic ecosystems (fresh water, such as rivers, streams) and land (forests, deserts).
	2.B.CB4.IE.2.	Compares data of different areas and establishes connections between biodiversity and environmental conditions. The emphasis is on the conservation of natural resources.
	2.B.CB4.IE.3.	Makes direct observations on the biodiversity of terrestrial and aquatic systems, with emphasis in comparing the diversity of the ecosystems. Examples include fresh water (rivers, streams), salt water (oceans), terrestrial ecosystems (rain forest, dry forest, desert).
	2.B.CB4.IE.4.	Makes observations of plants and animals to compare life's diversity in a variety of habitats.
	2.B.CB4.IE.5.	Builds models to represent community interactions: urban or rural, mountain and coastal areas. Includes human and plant interactions.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.2.FCF.	Physical Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure and properties of matter
EXPECTATION	2.FCF1.	Matter and its interactions - structure and properties; chemical reactions
INDICATOR	2.FCF1.EM.	Structure and level organization of matter
	2.FCF1.EM.1.	Describes characteristics of matter's states: solid, liquid and gas; and classifies objects according to their state.
	2.FCF1.EM.2.	Plans and realizes research to describe and classify different types of materials according to their observable physical properties. Examples of the properties can include color, texture, hardness, flexibility and absorbency.
	2.FCF1.EM.3.	Analyzes obtained data tests to different materials to predict which ones have the most adequate physical properties (Ex: different materials that float). Proves the predictions through research. Examples of physical properties can include flexibility, hardness, texture and absorbency.
	2.FCF1.EM.4.	Makes observations to explain in a written form, how an object built from a reduced quantity of pieces can be disassembled to make a different object. Applies concepts in the design of a new object. The emphasis is on the Law of Conservation of Mass or Matter.
INDICATOR	2.FCF1.CC.	Conservation and change
	2.FCF1.CC.1.	Describes how changes in temperature can produce changes in the characteristics and properties of materials (color, shape, size).

2.F.CF1.CC.2. Investigates on the reversible and non-reversible changes that arise from heating or cooling a material. Explains the observed in the investigation. For example, melting a piece of ice or burning paper.

DOMAIN

Forces and interactions

EXPECTATION 2.F.CF2.

Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions; Stability and instability of physical systems

INDICATOR 2.F.CF2.IE.

Interactions and energy

2.F.CF2.IE.1.

Makes observations on the different magnetic forces of magnets. Uses the observations to explain and create uses and applications of magnets in the real world.

2.F.CF2.IE.2.

Explains the relationship between force and movement in matter and describes the magnetic interactions of magnets, metals and compasses.

2.F.CF2.IE.3.

Compares and contrasts the effect of the magnitude of various forces on the changes of object's movement and position, which serve these forces. Examples of forces can include pulling, pushing and magnetism (gravity force is not discussed in terms of force at this level).

DOMAIN

Energy

EXPECTATION 2.F.CF3.

Energy - Conservation and transference of energy

INDICATOR 2.F.CF3.IE.

Interactions and energy

2.F.CF3.IE.1.

Recognizes diverse sources of energy like the Sun, food, batteries, air, water, among others. Identifies the Sun as a source of heat and light for planet Earth,

2.F.CF3.IE.2.

Builds a model of Earth where the Sun is identified as a source of light and heat for the planet.

2.F.CF3.IE.3.

Makes observations about different energy sources and compares the observed amounts of energy produced through different sources. Examples of energy sources that are taught in second grade are limited to Sun energy, light, sound and heat.

2.F.CF3.IE.4.

Explains that food is a primary source of energy to living organisms and classifies the different food according to their origin (animal or vegetable).

DOMAIN

Waves

EXPECTATION 2.F.CF4.

Waves and their application in information transference technologies - Wave properties

INDICATOR 2.F.CF4.IE.

Interactions and energy

2.F.CF4.IE.1.

Recognizes and describes wave observations (Ex: an ocean wave is a wave, sound waves).

2.F.CF4.IE.2.

Explains the relationship between the behavior of waves and energy that is expressed in regular movement patterns.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.2.T.CT.

Earth and Space Sciences

DOMAIN

Earth systems: The stars and solar system

EXPECTATION	2.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	2.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	2.T.CT1.IE.1.	Recognizes that energy is necessary for certain events and processes. For example, Sun is recognized as a source of heat and light for planet Earth.
	2.T.CT1.IE.2.	Performs research to provide evidence on how the Sun is a primary source of light and heat for Earth.
	2.T.CT1.IE.3.	Makes a model to show how the inclination and axis position of the Earth affect the way that sunlight reaches Earth.
INDICATOR	2.T.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	2.T.CT1.CC.1.	Predicts observations from the ground for a determined period of time, using sky elements, as the Sun, Moon and stars.
	2.T.CT1.CC.2.	Makes observations of the sky to describe lunar phases and construct models that describe these phases. (Phases: New moon is when you can't see it because the Moon is aligned between Earth and the Sun. First quarter moon is when you can see a larger amount of moon increasing because the Earth forms a 90° angle between the Moon and the Sun. Full moon is when Earth is aligned between the Moon and the Sun and you can see the largest portion of the Moon. Third quarter moon is when you can see a smaller amount of moon decreasing because Earth forms a 90° angle between the Moon and the Sun).
DOMAIN		Earth's systems: processes that shape Earth
EXPECTATION	2.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth's materials and systems; tectonic plates and interactions between systems at grand- scale; water's function in Earth's surface processes; meteorology and atmospheric conditions; Earth's history
INDICATOR	2.T.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	2.T.CT2.EM.1.	Describes, compares and groups materials on Earth according to their physical properties (natural materials and man-made).
	2.T.CT2.EM.2.	Develops a model to represent land formations (mountains, plains, wooded hills) and water bodies (rivers, lakes, etc) in an area of Puerto Rico. The emphasis is on land formations in different areas of Puerto Rico.
	2.T.CT2.EM.3.	Recognizes that natural phenomena produces changes on Earth's surface (rain, wind, snow, tsunamis, earthquakes, hurricanes, etc).
	2.T.CT2.EM.4.	Gets information to identify where water is on our planet, in solid or liquid form.
INDICATOR	2.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	2.T.CT2.CC.1.	Uses diverse source information to identify different terrestrial events that occur on our planet.
	2.T.CT2.CC.2.	Compares solutions to reduce or prevent water and wind effects on Earth's surface. The emphasis is on the use of

various information sources.

2.T.CT2.CC.3. Recognizes climate models and predicts how these influence changes of the planet. Uses weather information offered by newspaper, television or internet as an information source.

DOMAIN

Human impact

EXPECTATION 2.T.CT3. Earth and human activities - natural resources; human impact on Earth's systems

INDICATOR 2.T.CT3.CC. Conservation and change

2.T.CT3.CC.1. Recognizes the ways that humans pollute their community. Examples : throwing garbage into bodies of water, deforestation, throwing used oil on land.

2.T.CT3.CC.2. Designs plans to contribute to the conservation of a local community, with a focus on alternative methods to use natural resources.

CONTENT STANDARD

PR.3.B.CB. Biological Sciences

DOMAIN

Structures of living beings

EXPECTATION 3.B.CB1. From molecules to organisms: processes and structures - Structure and function; Growth and development of organisms

INDICATOR 3.B.CB1.EM. Structure and organization level of matter

3.B.CB1.EM.1. Observes and describes patterns in the characteristics of plant structure to determine how to classify them. Deduces that plants (herbs, shrubs and trees) have a series of structures that facilitate their classification.

3.B.CB1.EM.2. Identifies plants according to their structures and diverse types of stems: herbaceous have not developed hardened woody structures, besides being soft (herbs); woody have developed hardened structures (wood); roots (fibrous, branched or primary); leaves (simple or compound according to their ribbing: parallel-veined, penninervis or palminervis; according to their edge: whole, wavy, dented, serrated, or lobed; according to their stem: alternate, opposite or basal). There are other types of stems, such as tuberculous (part of a subterraneous stem of plant axis), the voluble (that curls around a support and goes around the stem), the bulbous (plant organ that permits the growth of a plant each year), the rhizome (stem from which adventitious roots grow each year), and the air-runner (aerial and crawling stems), among others. There are various types of roots: taproot formed by a thicker main root and thinner ones that come out of the main one; fibrous roots have no main root; nodulated roots have a very thick main root that reserves substances; tubercular roots have thick fasciculated structures; branched roots seem like branches of a tree and don't have a main root; aquatic roots float within the water not attached to anything; sucking roots are known as parasitic because they introduce their roots into other plants or vegetables and

		suck-in their sap.
	3.B.CB1.EM.3.	Looks for evidence to distinguish between terrestrial, aquatic or aerial plants and builds models to represent the differences.
INDICATOR	3.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	3.B.CB1.IE.1.	Develops models with the purpose of describing that each organism has its own life-cycle, but that all go through the following elements: birth, growth, reproduction and death. Includes models of sexual and asexual reproduction. Builds models of plant flowering related to the life-cycle of plants.
DOMAIN		Interdependent relationships in ecosystems
EXPECTATION	3.B.CB2.	Ecosystems: interactions, energy and dynamics - Social interactions and group behavior
INDICATOR	3.B.CB2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	3.B.CB2.IE.1.	Recognizes that living beings need other living beings and their environment to survive.
	3.B.CB2.IE.2.	Explains that some animals form groups to help their members to survive.
DOMAIN		Heredity and variations in characteristics: vital cycles and characteristics
EXPECTATION	3.B.CB3.	Genetic heredity: Heredity and variations in characteristics - Characteristics heredity; variations in characteristics
INDICATOR	3.B.CB3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	3.B.CB3.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data to provide evidence that plants and animals have inherited characteristics from their parents, which vary within the organisms that belong to a same group. The patterns represent similarities and differences of characteristics between parents and their offspring, and between siblings.
	3.B.CB3.IE.2.	Explains how the environment influences the characteristics of organisms. Similarities and differences also occur in plants where the environment affects the characteristics. Examples include plants that don't grow as they should because of lack of water; or an overweight dog because of excess food and lack of exercise.
INDICATOR	3.B.CB1.CC.	Conservation and change
	3.B.CB1.CC.1.	Identifies the characteristics that are transmitted and kept from generation to generation within a species or group of species. Organisms reproduce in similar organisms of themselves.
DOMAIN		Heredity and characteristic variations : vital cycles and characteristics
EXPECTATION	3.B.CB4.	Biological evolution: unity and diversity - evidence of diversity and common ancestors; natural selection; adaptation; humans and biodiversity
INDICATOR	3.B.CB4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	3.B.CB4.IE.1.	Explains how characteristic variations between individuals of the same species offers advantages to

survive, find a mate and reproduce. Examples of cause and effect relationships may include plants that have thorns and because of this, are less prone to predator attacks; animals that mimic or use camouflage are more adapted to survive and therefore are more prone to reproduce.

3.B.CB4.IE.2. Constructs an argument from evidence to explain in a certain environment, some types of organisms survive better than others, and some don't survive at all. Examples of evidence can include the needs and characteristics of the organisms and implicated habitats. The organisms and their habitat form a system in which all parts depend one on another.

INDICATOR 3.B.CB4.CC. Conservation and change

3.B.CB4.CC.1. Analyzes and interprets data from fossils to offer evidence of organisms and the environment in which they lived in the past. Examples of data can include the type, size and distribution of fossil organisms. The types of environment can include: marine fossils found in the Arctic and fossils of extinct organisms.

3.B.CB4.CC.2. Establishes an exposition to solve a problem caused by environmental changes that impact plants and animals that live there. Examples of environmental changes can include changes in Earth's characteristics, water distribution, food and presence of other organisms.

CONTENT STANDARD PR.3.FCF. Physical Sciences

DOMAIN Structure and function of matter

EXPECTATION 3.F.CF1. Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; chemical reactions

INDICATOR 3.F.CF1.EM. Structure and organization level of matter

3.F.CF1.EM.1. Uses qualitative and quantitative descriptions to measure and prove the physical properties of matter. Examples of properties: temperature, mass, magnetism and buoyancy.

3.F.CF1.EM.2. Recognizes and identifies the three states of matter and classifies them according to the state it is in. For example, recognizes that fluids flow and can be colorless.

INDICATOR 3.F.CF1.IE. Interactions and energy

3.F.CF1.IE.1. Describes the basic concepts of mixtures. Ex: identifies the difference between homogeneous and heterogeneous mixtures.

INDICATOR 3.F.CF1.CC. Conservation and Change

3.F.CF1.CC.1. Predicts physical changes in matter thanks to the heating and cooling processes.

DOMAIN Forces and interactions

EXPECTATION 3.F.CF2. Movement and stability: forces and interactions - Force and movement; types of interactions

INDICATOR 3.F.CF2.IE. Interactions and energy

- 3.F.CF2.IE.1. Performs research to evince the effects of balanced and unbalanced forces in the movement of an object.
- 3.F.CF2.IE.2. Makes observations on the movement of an object to provide evidence about the fact that patterns can be used to predict movement in the future.
- 3.F.CF2.IE.3. Recognizes the cause and effect relationships of electric and magnetic interactions between two objects that are not in contact.
- 3.F.CF2.IE.4. Explains how the basic forces of magnetism and gravity are present in natural phenomena.
- 3.F.CF2.IE.5. Identifies a problem that can be solved applying scientific ideas on magnets or gravity. The emphasis is on the scientific method to make simple investigations.
- 3.F.CF2.IE.6. Explains the effects of friction and gravity on objects.

DOMAIN

EXPECTATION 3.F.CF3.

Energy

Energy - definitions of energy; conservation and transference of energy; energy in chemical processes and daily life

INDICATOR

- 3.F.CF3.IE. Interactions and energy
- 3.F.CF3.IE.1. Infers that objects produce sound, emit light and absorb or release heat.
- 3.F.CF3.IE.2. Explains how objects absorb or release heat and recognizes that heat can transform matter.
- 3.F.CF3.IE.3. Identifies the properties and characteristics of sound and explains the way they are spread: height (characteristic: frequency of the wave, that it can be acute, medium or low); length (characteristic: vibration length, that can be long or short); intensity (characteristic: wave amplitude, that can be strong, weak or mild) ; tone (characteristic: waveform, that can be metallic, harsh).
- 3.F.CF3.IE.4. Describes the use of different forms of energy in nature and everyday phenomena. Examples of energy include mechanical, luminous, sonic, thermal, hydraulic and wind energy.
- 3.F.CF3.IE.5. Uses knowledge about the different types of energy to create a device (model) that demonstrates energy use to solve a problem. Examples of energy include mechanical, luminous, sonic, thermal, hydraulic and wind.

DOMAIN

EXPECTATION 3.F.CF4.

Waves

Waves and their applications for information transference technologies - properties of waves; information and instrumentation technologies

INDICATOR

- 3.F.CF4.IE. Interactions and energy
- 3.F.CF4.IE.1. Identifies, describes and relates wave properties (amplitude, wave length, frequency and speed). Emphasis is on recognition that waves transfer energy, have properties that can be described and interact in a predictable manner. An example is an echo: vibration that produces sound.
- 3.F.CF4.IE.2. Establishes the relationship between the properties and

wave behavior and energy.

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.3.T.CT.	Earth and Space Sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems: The stars and solar system
EXPECTATION	3.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - The universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	3.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	3.T.CT1.IE.1.	Explains how the Sun provides energy for Earth's processes. An example could be to recognize solar energy as a form of light and heat, and how this influences on the growth of plants or water cycle on Earth, etc.
	3.T.CT1.IE.2.	Identifies the relative position of bodies in the solar system.
	3.T.CT1.IE.3.	Shows the orbital relationships between the Sun, Moon and Earth and explains how these generate patterns that can be observed. Examples of patterns can include the observable changes in a night sky, through-out the day and night, the seasons and eclipses.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems: Processes that shape Earth
EXPECTATION	3.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth's materials and systems; Tectonic plates and system interaction on a large scale; water's role in the processes of Earth's surface; meteorology and atmospheric conditions; natural hazards.
INDICATOR	3.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	3.T.CT2.IE.1.	Distinguishes between the concepts of time and climate. Obtains and uses information to describe the climate in different regions around the world.
	3.T.CT2.IE.2.	Obtains information about different terrestrial regions on Earth to draw conclusions about the relationship between terrestrial formations and climatic zones. Examples can include the ideas that mountainous zones have lower temperatures or that desert areas have less precipitation, etc.
INDICATOR	3.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	3.T.CT2.CC.1.	Examines the gradual and sudden changes on Earth's surface to explain how changes create new terrestrial formations. Examples of gradual changes may include weathering and erosion. Examples of sudden changes may include the impact of volcanoes, earthquakes and tsunamis.
	3.T.CT2.CC.2.	Represents data through the use of tables and other types of graphs to describe climate patterns and predict the effect of weather conditions during a particular season in a determined zone (use of newspapers or daily information on climate, among others).
	3.T.CT2.CC.3.	Investigates on how to prepare to reduce the impact of a natural phenomena related to climate and weather.

DOMAIN		Human impact
EXPECTATION	3.T.CT3.	Earth and human activities - natural resources; natural hazards; human impact on Earth's systems.
INDICATOR	3.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	3.T.CT3.CC.1.	Recognizes the consequences of damage caused by humans to other living beings and the environment.
	3.T.CT3.CC.2.	Compares and contrasts the changes or damage caused to the planet by natural phenomena and by human activities.
	3.T.CT3.CC.3.	Develops a plan to reduce the effects and damage caused by humans to Earth's systems. Some examples of damage caused by humans include pollution, overload of natural resources, mis-use of land, irrational city spread-out, excessive hunt of organisms and technological pollution (mobile phones, GPS, computers, recorders, ipods, among other articles; these have made our functions easier, but once we stop using them, they turn into technological pollution).
	3.T.CT3.CC.4.	Develops a logical argument related to the use and conservation of natural resources.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.4.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure, function and information processing
EXPECTATION	4.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: Processes and structures - Structure and function; Information processing; The cell; Adaptations
INDICATOR	4.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	4.B.CB1.EM.1.	Arguments on the fact that both plants and animals have internal and external structures that have functions on growth, development, survival, conduct and reproduction.
	4.B.CB1.EM.2.	Mentions and debates the functional advantages of structural adaptations. Examples of structures may include leaves, stems, roots, heart, stomach, lungs and brain, among others.
	4.B.CB1.EM.3.	Creates structure and function models of the biological systems. Examples: cell model (prokaryotic, eukaryotic, animal and plant); human body systems (emphasis on digestive, reproductive, circulatory, musculoskeletal, and respiratory systems. Making emphasis on recognizing the parts and an introduction to the function of each one as part of a system; also makes emphasis on the importance of protecting, respecting and keeping healthy each system); and ecosystem models (making emphasis on the relationships between components and their function in ecosystems).
	4.B.CB1.EM.4.	Uses analogies to compare and contrast the cellular structures and their functions. Differentiates between animal and plant cell.
	4.B.CB1.EM.5.	Uses a model to describe that animals receive

information through their senses, process information in their brains and respond in different ways. The emphasis is in information transference systems.

INDICATOR	4.B.CB1.CC.	Conservation and change
	4.B.CB1.CC.1.	Defines, identifies and uses evidence to elaborate arguments about adaptive mechanisms in plants and animals that permit it survive and react to environmental changes.
	4.B.CB1.CC.2.	Recognizes that the shape, structure and vital functions of organisms may change throughout its development stages. The emphasis is on development and growth of adolescence.
	4.B.CB1.CC.3.	Identifies and accepts the changes suffered during adolescence.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.4.FCF.	Physical science
DOMAIN		Matter structure and classification; Properties and changes in matter
EXPECTATION	4.FCF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Chemical reactions
INDICATOR	4.FCF1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	4.FCF1.EM.1.	Compares, contrasts and measures the physical properties of matter.
	4.FCF1.EM.2.	Describes the physical and chemical properties of matter in qualitative and quantitative terms. Examples of these properties can include size, mass, volume, temperature, magnetism and buoyancy, flammability (characteristic that materials have when burnt or lighted when exposed to fire), combustion, corrosion, reactivity. Includes the importance of matter conservation in change processes.
	4.FCF1.EM.3.	Recognizes that different types of temperature scales exist: Centigrade ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), Fahrenheit ($^{\circ}\text{F}$) y Kelvin (K).
INDICATOR	4.FCF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	4.FCF1.IE.1.	Recognizes that energy is necessary to produce changes in matter's properties.
INDICATOR	4.FCF1.CC.	Conservation and change
	4.FCF1.CC.1.	Predicts changes in the states of matter from the increase or decrease of the heat that is applied.
	4.FCF1.CC.2.	Describes the processes that conserve and change matter's properties. Emphasis is on the operational definition of concepts: fusion, solidification, evaporation, condensation, combustion and reactivity.
	4.FCF1.CC.3.	Identifies the application and importance of the processes of fusion, solidification, evaporation, and condensation in industry, organisms and everyday life of human beings.
	4.FCF1.CC.4.	Compares and contrasts between the characteristics that describe mixtures and solutions (emphasis on the identification of homogeneous and heterogeneous

		mixtures).
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions
EXPECTATION	4.FCF2.	Movement and stability: forces and interactions - force and movement; Types of interactions; The relationship between force and energy; Stability and instability in physical systems
INDICATOR	4.FCF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	4.FCF2.IE.1.	Defines and identifies types of forces and how these are related with energy. The emphasis is on electrical and magnetic forces, friction and gravity.
	4.FCF2.IE.2.	Explains and proposes examples on how energy that is present in a force, affects the movement of an object. Examples of force may include pushing or pulling, gravity, friction and magnetism.
INDICATOR	4.FCF2.CC.	Conservation and change
	4.FCF2.CC.1.	Establishes a relationship between the velocity of an object and its energy.
	4.FCF2.CC.2.	Formulates questions and predicts results about energy changes that occur when objects collide. Emphasis must be that the change of energy is a product of the interaction that results from the change in velocity, not of the forces.
DOMAIN		Energy transference and conservation
EXPECTATION	4.FCF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; Conservation and transference of energy; Energy in chemical processes and everyday life
INDICATOR	4.FCF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	4.FCF3.IE.1.	Defines and provides examples of different types of energy (potential, kinetic, electric, magnetic, of light and heat) and how it can transfer from one place to another through sound, light, heat and electrical currents.
	4.FCF3.IE.2.	Compares and describes the processes and results of transference and conservation of energy.
	4.FCF3.IE.3.	Constructs an apparatus that converts one form of energy into another. Examples may include any design that converts light, sound, heat or mechanical or electrical energy, such as a solar heater that converts light into heat.
	4.FCF3.IE.4.	Distinguishes between conductors and insulators; its use in energy transference.
	4.FCF3.IE.5.	Experiments with the design of an apparatus that uses different energy paths. Examples of energy paths may include circuits and electromagnetic fields. Different batteries may be used with the purpose of lighting one or several small bulbs.
DOMAIN		Wave properties and behavior
EXPECTATION	4.FCF4.	Waves and their applications in information transference technologies - Wave properties; Information and instrumentation technologies
INDICATOR	4.FCF4.IE.	Interactions and energy

	4.F.CF4.IE.1.	Conceptually defines the different types of waves (mechanic and electromagnetic) and describes wave's characteristics and general properties.
	4.F.CF4.IE.2.	Builds models to demonstrate the relationship that exists between wave characteristics and properties (such as amplitude and magnitude with the effect produced on movement, force and energy of objects).
	4.F.CF4.IE.3.	Identifies a problem and designs a solution for the interference of wave properties.
	4.F.CF4.IE.4.	Creates and compares patterns to identify and group data and transfer information. Examples may include binary codes as: male= 1, female= 2, data to represent whites and blacks on an image, use of Morse-code to send information, and others.
INDICATOR	4.F.CF4.CC.	Conservation and change
	4.F.CF4.CC.1.	Explains how changes in longitude, amplitude and frequency in waves provoke alterations in the components of a system. Identifies simple reflection and refraction examples of waves.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.4.T.CT.	Earth and Space Sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems
EXPECTATION	4.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	4.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	4.T.CT1.IE.1.	Defines, describes and represents the rotation and revolution movements of the Earth in relation to the Sun, and how these are related with changes on Earth.
	4.T.CT1.IE.2.	Explains how the Sun is the primary energy source on Earth and provokes many other changes of Earth's surface. Examples may include seasons, lunar phases, tides and eclipse formation.
	4.T.CT1.IE.3.	Examines patterns in the lunar and solar phases to explain how these produce different effects on Earth. Examples of effects can include tides, seasons, shadows and eclipses.
DOMAIN		Processes that shape Earth
EXPECTATION	4.T.CT2.	Earth' systems - Earth's materials and systems; Tectonic plates and system interactions on a large scale; History of planet Earth; Landforms in Puerto Rico
INDICATOR	4.T.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	4.T.CT2.EM.1.	Describes the types of geologic features found in Puerto Rico: mountains, wooded hills, plains, hills, valleys, canyons, gorges, basins, and mountain ranges.
	4.T.CT2.EM.2.	Recognizes, describes and explains the relationship between different types of terrain in Puerto Rico and their ecosystems.
	4.T.CT2.EM.3.	Groups rocks into igneous, metamorphic, and sedimentary. Explains the process of rock formation.

	4.T.CT2.EM.4.	Interprets and analyzes map data to describe patterns in Earth's characteristics.
INDICATOR	4.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	4.T.CT2.CC.1.	Identifies evidence from patterns in rock formation and fossils in rock layers to support an explanation of the changes in landscape over time.
	4.T.CT2.CC.2.	Examines patterns in Earth's characteristics to offer evidence that describes Earth's history and the movement of the continents over time.
	4.T.CT2.CC.3.	Makes observations and measurements to collect evidence on the effects of weathering and erosion by water, ice, wind or vegetation of the characteristics of Earth's surface.
DOMAIN		Human impact
EXPECTATION	4.T.CT3.	Earth and human activity - Natural resources; Nature's dangers; Human impact on Earth's systems
INDICATOR	4.T.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	4.T.CT3.IE.1.	Identifies how severe natural phenomena (earthquakes, hurricanes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions) can modify the environment and how they recover their balance.
	4.T.CT3.IE.2.	Describes that the energy and the fuel human beings use are from natural resources and that their use affects the environment and society. Examples of renewable energy of natural resources can include hydroelectric, solar, and wind energies; examples of non-renewable energy include fossil-fuels and radioactive materials.
	4.T.CT3.IE.3.	Distinguishes and groups natural renewable and non-renewable resources; distinguishes between the risks and benefits of each source of energy.
	4.T.CT3.IE.4.	Describes and identifies environmental problems caused by human interaction on water bodies, soil and landscape (plains, mountains, wooded hills, hills, valleys, canyons, gorges, basins and mountain ranges).
INDICATOR	4.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	4.T.CT3.CC.1.	Generates and compares multiple solutions to reduce the impact of Earth's processes and phenomena on human beings.
	4.T.CT3.CC.2.	Designs alternative solutions for the impact of human actions to the environment, focusing on ecosystems and environments of Puerto Rico. The emphasis is on water, air, and soil pollution, conservation of natural resources and the appropriate and responsible handling of wastes.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.5.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		Matter and energy in organisms and ecosystems
EXPECTATION	5.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: processes and structures - Flow organization or matter and energy in organisms
INDICATOR	5.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	5.B.CB1.EM.1.	Identifies and groups plants with and without seeds.

		Creates models to represent the difference between vascular and non-vascular plants with or without seeds.
INDICATOR	5.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.B.CB1.IE.1.	Recognizes some factors that affect the growth of plants, such as the presence or lack of Sun or a source of light, space, presence or lack of water, minerals, land or types of soil.
	5.B.CB1.IE.2.	Explains the role that plants play in evolution.
	5.B.CB1.IE.3.	Supports the argument that plants acquire the material they need to grow, as air and water. The emphasis is on the idea that the materials plants live on come mainly from air and water, not from soil. A plant can grow without the presence of soil. Minerals can be obtained from water. Hydroponic agriculture is a method to cultivate plants.
	5.B.CB1.IE.4.	Uses models to describe that energy in animal's food'(used for their recovery, growth and movement, and to keep body heat) was originally solar energy. Examples of models can include diagrams and charts.
EXPECTATION	5.B.CB2.	Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics - Interdependent relationships in ecosystems; Transference cycles of matter and energy in ecosystems
INDICATOR	5.B.CB2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	5.B.CB2.EM.1.	Numbers and explains some uses that humans give to fungi and the function of these in ecosystems.
	5.B.CB2.EM.2.	Uses observations and evidence to classify organisms in the six kingdoms. Emphasis is on recognizing the existence of different levels of organization of the kingdoms when interacting in ecosystems.
	5.B.CB2.EM.3.	Develops a model to describe matter movement between producers, consumers (plants, animals), decomposers and the environment; establishes the difference between these. Emphasis on their function within the food-chain or web. Emphasis is on the idea that matter that is not food (air, water, decomposed materials in soil) become food material once again in plants.
	5.B.CB2.EM.4.	Models the role of vertebrates and invertebrates in ecosystems, when distinguishing between both groups and making emphasis in the classification of each sub-group.
INDICATOR	5.B.CB2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.B.CB2.IE.1.	Builds a model to represent the commercial and ecological value of plants in ecosystems.
INDICATOR	5.B.CB2.CC.	Conservation and change
	5.B.CB2.CC.1.	Identifies ways to conserve organism survival in their environment.
	5.B.CB2.CC.2.	Designs solutions so humans can help manage and protect the biotic and abiotic factors in ecosystems.

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.5.FCF.	Physical Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure and properties in matter
EXPECTATION	5.FCF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; chemical reactions
INDICATOR	5.FCF1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	5.FCF1.EM.1.	Develops a model to describe that matter is composed of such tiny particles that they can't be seen with a naked eye (atoms and sub-particles) and includes the presentation of models that show matter at a microscopic scale.
	5.FCF1.EM.2.	Makes observations and measurements to identify materials according to the physical and chemical properties of matter. Examples of materials to identify can include powders, metals, minerals and liquids. Examples of properties may include color, hardness, reflectivity (transparent, opaque, translucent), conductivity (electrical or thermal), magnetism, solubility; among others.
	5.FCF1.EM.3.	Distinguishes between the chemical and physical properties of matter. Chemical properties are manifested in chemical reactions: corrosiveness of acids (ammonia, for example); corrosive substances are very dangerous and can injure skin, eyes and lungs if their fumes are inhaled; decomposition (ex: water can decompose in hydrogen and oxygen through an electric current), reactivity (iron rusts at room temperature, gold doesn't rust; alcohol is flammable, water isn't). Examples of physical properties: color, odor, flavor, boiling temperature, fusion point, solubility, hardness, electric conductivity, thermal conductivity.
	5.FCF1.EM.4.	Investigates to determine if the combination of two or more substances results in new substances.
	5.FCF1.EM.5.	Distinguishes between the mixture separation methods: filtration, evaporation, distillation, precipitation, sedimentation.
INDICATOR	5.FCF1.CC.	Conservation and change
	5.FCF1.CC.1.	Experiments with the mixture separation methods and explains their importance in everyday life and environmental conservation.
	5.FCF1.CC.2.	Measures and prepares graphs where the quantities related with the combination of two or more substances that are mixed, are expressed, in order to show that the total weight of mass is conserved even when you heat it or cool it.
	5.FCF1.CC.3.	Conceptually defines the terms of mass and weight and establishes the existing relationship between both of them. Differentiates between mass and weight.
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions
EXPECTATION	5.FCF2.	Movement and stability: forces and interactions - Types of interactions; stability and instability in physical systems

INDICATOR	5.F.CF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.F.CF2.IE.1.	Groups, compares and contrasts examples of simple and compound machines, and explains their use.
	5.F.CF2.IE.2.	Designs a test to show the interactions between work, force and energy.
	5.F.CF2.IE.3.	Experiments to provide evidence about the effect simple or compound machines have on the force needed to move an object.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	5.F.CF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between force and energy
INDICATOR	5.F.CF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.F.CF3.IE.1.	Explains how kinetic and potential energies are related in closed systems.
	5.F.CF3.IE.2.	Applies scientific principles to design, build and try and apparatus that minimizes or maximizes the transference of thermal energy.
INDICATOR	5.F.CF3.CC.	Conservation and change
	5.F.CF3.CC.1.	Explains how the Law the Conservation of Matter is related to the equilibrium of energies in matter.
	5.F.CF3.CC.2.	Presents examples that support the idea that when the kinetic energy of an object changes, energy is transferred from or to this same object.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.5.T.CT.	Earth and space sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems: stars and the solar system
EXPECTATION	5.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - The universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	5.T.CT1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	5.T.CT1.EM.1.	Elaborates an argument to explain that the difference in the Sun's light intensity compared to that of other stars, is due to the relative distance of these and Earth.
INDICATOR	5.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.T.CT1.IE.1.	Elaborates an argument to explain that objects are pulled downwards because of the gravitational attraction between them and the Earth.
	5.T.CT1.IE.2.	Uses scientific evidence through the use of various information sources to explain the function of the Sun and oceans in water's cycle.
INDICATOR	5.T.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	5.T.CT1.CC.1.	Shows and compares Earth's rotation and revolution movements to describe its effects on daily life.
	5.T.CT1.CC.2.	Represents data through graphs to reveal patterns in everyday changes of shadows length and direction, day and night, effects on the seasons and the appearance of stars in the sky according to the seasons.
DOMAIN		Earth systems

EXPECTATION	5.T.CT2.	Earth systems - Earth's materials and systems; Water function in the processes of the surface of Earth; Meteorology and atmospheric conditions
INDICATOR	5.T.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	5.T.CT2.EM.1.	Explains the importance of the cycle of water for the planet's life (river formation, industry, needs and uses at home, agriculture, fun, source of food and habitat). Recognizes the need of water in ecosystems.
	5.T.CT2.EM.2.	Operationally defines the concept of safe water and describes the steps in the process of water purification.
	5.T.CT2.EM.3.	Describes and builds graphs to represent the quantities and percentages of water (salty and fresh) in various water bodies to give evidence about water distribution on Earth. Water bodies are referred to the natural aquatic formations, like oceans, lakes, rivers, glaciers, subterranean aquatic formations and aquifers and polar ice caps.
INDICATOR	5.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.T.CT2.IE.1.	Defines, differentiates and identifies the different climate zones on the planet.
	5.T.CT2.IE.2.	Develops a model from an example to describe the interaction of Earth's different spheres. Examples of spheres include geosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere.
INDICATOR	5.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	5.T.CT2.CC.1.	Develops a model of water's cycle and rock formation's cycle.
	5.T.CT2.CC.2.	Distinguishes how different geological processes provide evidence that supports the formation of solids on Earth throughout its geological history. Examples of geological processes can be the formation of sedimentary rocks, formation of fossil-fuels, formation of fossils and slow changes on Earth's surface, as weathering and erosion of canyons.
DOMAIN		Human impact
EXPECTATION	5.T.CT3.	Earth and human activity - Natural resources; Human impact on Earth's systems; Global climate change
INDICATOR	5.T.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	5.T.CT3.IE.1.	Recognizes the causes of global climate changes in Earth's biomes (tundra, taiga, temperate forest, tropical rain forest, jungle, savannah, desert).
	5.T.CT3.IE.2.	Identifies the effects of global climate changes on Earth's biomes and biosphere, with a particular focus on Puerto Rico's ecosystems.
INDICATOR	5.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	5.T.CT3.CC.1.	Obtains and analyzes information on how communities and individuals use scientific ideas to protect the environment and natural resources.
	5.T.CT3.CC.2.	Develops commentary projects to protect the local environment or the community's natural resources.

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.6.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		Matter and energy in organisms and ecosystems
EXPECTATION	6.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: Processes and structures - Flow organization of matter and energy in organisms.
INDICATOR	6.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	6.B.CB1.IE.1.	Explains the role of photosynthesis in the cycle of matter and flow of energy into and out of organisms. The emphasis is on registering matter's movement and energy's flow.
	6.B.CB1.IE.2.	Describes how food is decomposed (into the elements that form it) and regroups to form new molecules that support growth or liberation of energy through chemical reactions according to how matter moves within the organism. Emphasis is on describing that molecules break-up and regroup and during this process energy is liberated.
	6.B.CB1.IE.3.	Explains how the flow of matter and energy is important to keep a healthy life. Emphasis is on a balanced feeding, exercise, rest, etc.
INDICATOR	6.B.CB1.CC.	Conservation and change
	6.B.CB1.CC.1.	Submits evidence on how photosynthesis contributes to the reduction of atmospheric pollution to conserve the environment.
DOMAIN		Structure and changes in matter
EXPECTATION	6.F.CF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; chemical reactions
INDICATOR	6.F.CF1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	6.F.CF1.EM.1.	Groups and classifies matter by its physical and chemical properties
	6.F.CF1.EM.2.	Applies the utility concept of the physical and chemical properties in daily life.
	6.F.CF1.EM.3.	Explains that each element is formed by only one type of atoms and that elements are organized on a periodic table according to their properties.
	6.F.CF1.EM.4.	Identifies and explains the basic format of the periodic table (groups or families, number of protons, number of electrons, number of neutrons, number of mass (addition of protons and neutrons in the nucleus of an atom), atomic number (quantity of protons that an atom has), period, metals, non-metals, metalloids, synthetic elements, state of matter of the elements).
	6.F.CF1.EM.5.	Groups and classifies elements into metals, non-metals, and metalloids using the periodic table.
INDICATOR	6.F.CF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	6.F.CF1.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data about the properties of substances before and after substances interact, to determine if a chemical reaction has occurred. Emphasis is on physical and chemical change, endothermic and

		exothermic reactions.
INDICATOR	6.F.CF1.CC.	Conservation and change
	6.F.CF1.CC.1.	Predicts and describes the physical and chemical changes in matter produced by the increasing or decreasing effects of heat (includes change of states: solid, liquid, gas).
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.6.F.CF.	Physical Sciences
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions
EXPECTATION	6.F.CF2.	Movement and stability: forces and interactions - force and movement; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems
INDICATOR	6.F.CF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	6.F.CF2.IE.1.	Describes basic concepts of Newton's Laws of Movement (speed, rapidness, acceleration, deceleration) and relates them to everyday life movements (rectilinear and circular movements).
	6.F.CF2.IE.2.	Applies Newton's 3rd Law to provide a solution to a problem that involves the movement of two objects that collide.
	6.F.CF2.IE.3.	Explains the fact that an object's change in movement depends on the sum of forces on the object and the object's mass. Emphasis is on the balance and unbalance of forces within a system, the qualitative comparison of forces, mass, and changes in movement, the reference mark, and the identification of measuring units.
	6.F.CF2.IE.4.	Formulates questions about the evidence needed to determine the present factors in electromagnetic and gravitational forces.
DOMAIN		Waves and their applications
EXPECTATION	6.F.CF4.	Waves and their applications in information transference technologies - Electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies
INDICATOR	6.F.CF4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	6.F.CF4.IE.1.	Develops a model to describe how waves are reflected, absorbed or transmitted thru various materials.
	6.F.CF4.IE.2.	Uses mathematical representations to describe a simple model that represents how amplitude and magnitude of a wave are related with the present energy in the wave.
DOMAIN		Space systems
EXPECTATION	6.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - The universe and stars; Earth and the solar system.
INDICATOR	6.T.CT1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	6.T.CT1.EM.1.	Develops models that describe the physical properties, position and movement of components of the solar system.
INDICATOR	6.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy

	6.T.CT1.IE.1.	Elaborates an argument based on evidence to justify the need of space exploration and the cost-efficient role of the mission.
	6.T.CT1.IE.2.	Establishes the relationship between gravity force and the Sun's energy in everyday life on planet Earth. Examples of gravity should include manners in which movements within galaxies and the solar system are important to Earth.
	6.T.CT1.IE.3.	Develops and uses a model of Earth-Sun-Moon system to describe the cyclical patterns of lunar phases, solar and lunar eclipse, and the seasons.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	6.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth's materials and systems; Tectonic plates and grand-scale system interactions; The role of water in processes of the Earth's surface; Meteorology and atmospheric conditions
INDICATOR	6.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	6.T.CT2.IE.1.	Explains the relationship that exists between global warming and meteorological phenomena from scientific evidence.
INDICATOR	6.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	6.T.CT2.CC.1.	Identifies and classifies the change processes that Earth suffers. Examples include layers of earth, rocks and rock cycles, main tectonic plates, types of rock in Puerto Rico and tectonic plates in our region.
	6.T.CT2.CC.2.	Shows knowledge on tectonic plates to explain the phenomena that occurs in small or grand-scale on Earth.
	6.T.CT2.CC.3.	Explains the effect of water on Earth's surface for long periods of time. Emphasis is on erosion and precipitation.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.6.T.CT.	Earth and Space Sciences
DOMAIN		Human impact on Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	6.T.CT3.	Earth and human activity - Natural resources; Nature's dangers: From natural processes varied risks are derived; Human impact on Earth's systems; Global climate change
INDICATOR	6.T.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	6.T.CT3.IE.1.	Uses evidence to evaluate the impact of human activity on the biosphere, geosphere and atmosphere, on planet earth, making emphasis on Puerto Rico.
	6.T.CT3.IE.2.	Develops a logical argument to support and describe alternative energy sources.
INDICATOR	6.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	6.T.CT3.CC.1.	Designs a conservation plan for the biosphere, geosphere and atmosphere, specifically on Puerto Rico.
	6.T.CT3.CC.2.	Uses knowledge about Earth's systems to predict and plan what to do with the effects of natural phenomena.

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.EI.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure, function and information processing
EXPECTATION	EI.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: Structures and processes - Structure and function; Organism growth and development
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	EI.B.CB1.EM.1.	Recognizes that living beings are composed of cells; either one cell or many different cells in variable quantities. Emphasis is on developing evidence that a cell is the basic functional structure in living organisms and understanding that living beings can be composed of one or many cells.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.2.	Uses technology to develop and use a model that describes the total function of a cell and the ways its parts contribute to its functions. Emphasis is on the functioning of the cell as a total system and the main role of the cell's parts, specifically the nucleus, chloroplasts, mitochondria, cell membrane and cell wall.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.3.	Compares and contrasts the processes of cellular reproduction. Emphasis is on cellular cycle, mitosis and meiosis.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.4.	Demonstrates that the body is a system formed by sub-systems formed by groups of cells that interact between themselves. Emphasis is on the conceptual comprehension that cells form tissues and tissues form specialized organs to realize specific corporal functions. Examples may include: the interaction of subsystems within a system and the normal function of those systems. Evaluation is limited to circulatory, excretory, digestive, respiratory, muscular and nervous systems.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.5.	Collects and summarizes information on sensorial receptors that respond to stimuli sending messages to the brain for immediate conduct or memory storage.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.6.	Builds a model of mammal reproduction, internal or external fertilization; and the stages of human development.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.7.	Defines the differences of masculine and feminine reproductive systems in humans, and the structure and function changes during adolescence, puberty, fertilization and pregnancy.
	EI.B.CB1.EM.8.	Compares the differences in structure and function between plant angiosperms and gymnosperms.
DOMAIN		Growth, development and reproduction of organisms.
EXPECTATION	EI.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: Structures and processes - Growth and development of organisms
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.B.CB1.IE.1.	Explains how specialized structures of plants and animal behavior have evolved to contribute to the reproduction and preservation of species. Examples of plant structures can include bright flowers that attract

pollinators. Examples of conducts that affect the animal reproductive probability may include, building nests to protect offspring from cold, herd organization to protect themselves from predators, and vocalization and bright feathering to attract mates.

EI.B.CB1.IE.2. Evaluates how environmental and genetic factors influence the growth of organisms. Understands how scientists use genetic knowledge to predict offspring. Examples of local environmental conditions may include food, light, space, and water availability. Examples of genetic factors may include breeding large sized cattle and the types of problems that affect organism growth. Examples of evidence may include drought that affects the growth of plants, the use of fertilizers that increase growth in plants, different variety of seeds growing at a different speed under different conditions, an fish that grow larger in larger tanks contrary to fish in reduced spaces.

EI.B.CB1.IE.3. Defines the role of adolescents in society through information collection about adolescent periods and the difference between sex, gender, and sexuality. Recognizes that fertilization and birth are essential processes for life.

DOMAIN

Organism classification

EXPECTATION EI.B.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Interactions between kingdoms and group behavior

INDICATOR EI.B.CB1.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

EI.B.CB1.EM.9.

Identifies the characteristics that are used to group organisms by a classification system.

EI.B.CB1.EM.10.

Identifies the organization levels of organisms in a kingdom. Example: scientific name = gender - species; taxonomy = kingdom- phylum- class- order- family- gender- species.

DOMAIN

Growth, development and reproduction of organisms

EXPECTATION EI.B.CB3.

Heredity and characteristic variations - Characteristic heredity; Variations in characteristics.

INDICATOR EI.B.CB3.CC.

Conservation and change

EI.B.CB3.CC.1.

Explains why the structural changes in genes (mutations) found in chromosomes may affect proteins and cause beneficial, harmful or neutral changes in the structure and function of an organism. Emphasis is on the conceptual comprehension that changes in genetic material may result in the production of different protein.

EI.B.CB3.CC.2.

Builds a model to explain why asexual reproduction results in identical genetic information offspring and why sexual reproduction results in variable genetic information. Emphasis is on the use of models as Punnett squares, diagrams and simulations to describe the relationships cause-effect in the transmission of parent's genes to offspring, that result in genetic variations.

EI.B.CB3.CC.3.

Distinguishes between internal and external

		reproduction.
	EI.B.CB3.CC.4.	Collects and communicates information on mammal reproduction and the stages of human development.
	EI.B.CB3.CC.5.	Describes the DNA structure and explains the importance of this in living beings.
DOMAIN		Natural selection and adaptations
EXPECTATION	EI.B.CB4.	Biological evolution: unity and diversity - Evidence of common ancestors and diversity; Natural and artificial selection; Adaptation
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.B.CB4.IE.1.	Devises arguments on the impact of genetic engineering and biotechnology in agriculture, food production and medical applications, among others.
	EI.B.CB4.IE.2.	Collects and summarizes information about the technologies that have changed the way humans control characteristic heredity wished in organisms. Emphasis is on the synthesis of information from reliable sources about the influence of humans in the genetic results in artificial selection (such as genetic modification).
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB4.CC.	Conservation and change
	EI.B.CB4.CC.1.	Interprets data about patterns in fossil records that document the existence, diversity, extinction and change in life forms thru the history of life on Earth, under the assumption that natural laws operate in the present that same as in the past. Emphasis is on finding patterns in the complexity level of anatomic structures of organisms and the chronological order of fossil appearance in rock layers.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.2.	Compares the anatomical similarities and differences between present organisms and fossil organisms to infer evolutionary relationships. Emphasis is on explanations about evolutionary relationships between organisms, in terms of similarities or differences in the general appearances of anatomical structures.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.3.	Compares similarity patterns in the embryological development between multiple species and identifies non-evident relationships in the already complete formed anatomy. Emphasis is on inferring general patterns of relationships between different organisms' embryos comparing the macroscopic appearance in diagrams and images. The comparison evaluation is limited to the general appearance of anatomical structures in the embryological development.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.4.	Explains how genetic variations in the characteristics of a population increase the probability of survival and reproduction of some individuals in a specific environment. Emphasis is on using simple assumptions about probability and proportional reasoning to build explanations.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.5.	Uses mathematical representations to support the explanations on how natural selection can lead to increases or decreases of specific characteristics in

certain populations throughout time. Emphasis is on the use of mathematical models, probability assumptions and proportional reasoning to support the explanations on change tendencies in populations over time. The evaluations do not include Hardy Weinberg calculations.

DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	EI.B.IT.1.	Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimize the design solution
INDICATOR	EI.B.IT.1.IT.	Design for engineering
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.1.	Defines specifications and limitations of a design problem with sufficient precision to assure a successful solution, taking into consideration the relevant scientific principles and potential impacts on people and the environment, that could limit the possible solutions.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.2.	Develops a model to generate data when realizing interactive tests and modifications to an object, tool or process, in order to document and obtain the optimal design.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.3.	Analyzes data from the tests to determine similarities and differences between several design solutions, and identifies the best characteristics of each one, and combines them into a new solution, that better attends the criteria for the their success.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.4.	Evaluates competitive design solutions using a systematic process to determine how properly the specifications and problem limitations are taken care of. Emphasis is on realizing projects where various disciplines, like robotics, are integrated.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.5.	Knows the inherent fundamental concepts for the creation of a research proposal. Emphasis is on knowing the scientific method and bases for the development of a research proposal. Research problem identification, variable identification, hypothesis writing, measurement, and means to collect and interpret data must be emphasized, also ethical and security aspects.

CONTENT STANDARD PR.EI.F.CF. Physical Sciences

DOMAIN		Structure and properties of matter
EXPECTATION	EI.F.CF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Chemical reactions; Definitions of energy
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF1.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	EI.F.CF1.EM.1.	Collects information from reliable sources to explain the use of knowledge on atomic models and the atomic theory.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.2.	Uses knowledge about atomic structures to classify the families of chemical elements and predict their location on the periodic table.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.3.	Describes the processes in which substances are combined to form compounds. Emphasis is on simple

		ionic and covalent bonds, Lewis structures and valence electrons.
	EI.FCF1.EM.4.	Develops models to describe the atomic composition of simple molecules and extended structures. Examples of simple molecules may include water and carbon dioxide. Examples of extended structures may include sodium chloride or a diamond. Examples of models at a molecular level may include drawings, 3D models, or computer representations.
	EI.FCF1.EM.5.	Collects and understands information to describe that synthetic materials are produced from natural resources and have an impact on society. Emphasis is on natural resources that go thru a chemical process to form synthetic material. Examples may include: new medicines, food and alternative fuels.
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.FCF1.IE.1.	Develops a model that proves changes in the movement of particles, temperature and state of a substance when thermal energy is added or removed. Emphasis is on qualitative models of a molecular level of solids, liquids and gases to prove that by adding or removing thermal energy, kinetic particle energy increases or decreases until a change in state occurs. Examples of particles may include molecules or atoms. Examples of substances may include water, carbon dioxide and helium.
DOMAIN		Chemical reactions
EXPECTATION	EI.FCF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Chemical reactions; nuclear fusion
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.FCF1.IE.2.	Plans and conducts research to provide data on how the chemical and physical properties of substances interact to determine if a reaction has occurred. Examples of reactions may include burning sugar or steel wool and the reaction of acetic acid with sodium bicarbonate.
	EI.FCF1.IE.3.	Realizes a project to build, demonstrate and modify an apparatus that liberates or absorbs thermal energy thru chemical processes. Emphasis is on the design, controlling the energy transference to the environment, and on the modification of an apparatus using factor such as the type and concentration of a substance. Examples of designs may involve chemical reactions such as dissolving sodium bicarbonate and acetic acid (vinegar). Endothermic (absorbs energy) and exothermic (liberates energy) chemical reaction concepts are integrated.
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.CC.	Conservation and change
	EI.FCF1.CC.1.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the total number of atoms doesn't change in a chemical reaction, and therefore mass is conserved. Emphasis is on applying the Matter Conservation Law in the balanced chemical equations represented by physical models or drawings, including digital media to represent atoms.

INDICATOR	EI.F.CF1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	EI.F.CF1.EM.6.	Designs and realizes an experiment to demonstrate the difference between a compound and a mixture based on the methods (chemical or physical) that are used to separate them (mixtures) or decompose them (compounds). Emphasis is on that mixtures are separated by physical methods (filtration, chromatography, decantation, crystallization, distillation, among others), while a compound is decomposed by chemical methods (heating, electrolysis, photolysis).
	EI.F.CF1.EM.7.	Collects evidence to establish a contrast between a diluted, saturated and over-saturated solution, explains their properties, and provides examples and uses of each of these types of solutions in everyday life.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.8.	Analyzes the general properties of acids and bases (alkaline substances) and applies them in the qualitative determination of pH of different materials (mixtures and substances) as a way to classify them as acids or alkaline, as well as provide examples of their uses and applications in science and everyday life. Examples may be the use of antacids to control the pH of gastric juices, pH in swimming pools, acid rain, hygiene and cleaning products.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.9.	Collects evidence from different sources to build an explanation about the risks and dangers of chemical substances in everyday life. Examples of risks may include flammable corrosive, and radioactive.
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions
EXPECTATION	EI.F.CF2.	Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions: Energy in chemical processes in daily life.
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.F.CF2.IE.1.	Compares Newton's movement laws (first, second and third) and applies them to design a research that proves each one of them. Emphasis is on the differences between mass and weight concepts.
	EI.F.CF2.IE.2.	Plans a research to give proof on the sum of forces in a collision, considering the forces that act on an object and its mass. Evidence can be provided thru quantitative and qualitative comparisons.
	EI.F.CF2.IE.3.	Builds and presents arguments using reliable evidence to support the premise that gravitational interactions are by attraction and depend on interacting objects mass.
	EI.F.CF2.IE.4.	Explains, thru evidence, the nature of electric and magnetic forces present in matter, and uses knowledge for the design of simple electrical circuits, in series and in parallel.
	EI.F.CF2.IE.5.	Realizes research and evaluates the experimental design to give evidence that force fields between objects exist, even when the objects are not in contact. Emphasis is on gravitational fields, electric fields and magnetic fields.

EI.F.CF2.IE.6. Collects evidence to support and explanation and provide examples that correlate the importance of work, force and energy concepts in everyday life.

EI.F.CF2.IE.7. Creates a problem solution using a simple machine or a compound machine.

DOMAIN

Energy

EXPECTATION EI.F.CF3.

Energy - Definitions of energy; conservation and transference of energy; relationship between forces and energy.

INDICATOR EI.F.CF3.IE.

Interactions and energy

EI.F.CF3.IE.1.

Builds and interprets graphic information from data to describe the relationships between kinetic energy, mass and speed of an object.

EI.F.CF3.IE.2.

Develops a model to explain that when changing the layout of objects that interact at a distance, different quantities of potential energy are stored.

EI.F.CF3.IE.3.

Applies scientific principles to design, build and try an apparatus that minimizes or maximizes thermal energy transference.

EI.F.CF3.IE.4.

Plans research about thermal energy transference that determines the relationships between the transferred energy, type of material, mass and change in the average kinetic energy particles from the sample's temperature measurements.

EI.F.CF3.IE.5.

Builds, uses and presents arguments to support the premise that when kinetic energy of an object changes, energy is transferred from or to the object. Emphasis is on the Conservation of Energy Law.

DOMAIN

Waves and electromagnetic radiation

EXPECTATION EI.F.CF4.

Waves and their applications in information technology transference - Wave's properties; electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies

INDICATOR EI.F.CF4.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

EI.F.CF4.EM.1.

Plans research to collect evidence that describes sound and light wave properties. Emphasis is on the electromagnetic spectrum model and the difference between mechanic and electromagnetic waves.

EI.F.CF4.EM.2.

Integrates qualitative scientific information and technical information to support the premise that digital signals are the most trustworthy way to encrypt and transmit information rather than analogue signals. Emphasis is on the basic comprehension that waves can be used for communication purposes. Examples may include: use of optic fiber to transmit light pulses, radio pulse waves in wi-fi apparatus, and the conversion of binary patterns kept to generate a text or sound on a computer screen.

INDICATOR EI.F.CF4.IE.

Interactions and energy

EI.F.CF4.IE.1.

Gets and communicates information to correlate the range and energy of waves. Emphasis is on the Sun as energy source and radiant energy forms. (Electromagnetic spectrum)

INDICATOR	EI.F.CF4.CC. EI.F.CF4.CC.1.	Conservation and change Creates models to represent the different wave behaviors according to their movement thru different environments. Emphasis is on wave interactions such as reflection, refraction, dispersion and interference.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	EI.F.IT 1.	Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimizes the design solution
INDICATOR	EI.F.IT 1.IT. EI.F.IT 1.IT.1.	Design for engineering Defines the specifications and limitations of a design problem with enough precision to assure a successful solution, taking into consideration the relevant scientific principles and potential impacts on people and the environment that could limit the possible solutions.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.2.	Develops a model to generate data when making interactive tests and changes to an object, tool or process, to document and obtain the optimal design.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.3.	Analyzes test's data to determine the similarities and differences between various design solutions, and identifies the best characteristics of each one, and combines them into a new solution, that better serves the criteria for the success of these.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.4.	Evaluates solutions for competitive design using a systematic process to determine how well the specifications and problem limitations are served. Emphasis is on realizing projects where various disciplines, like robotics, are integrated.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.5.	Composes a research proposal. Emphasis is on the composition of a research proposal that integrates acquired knowledge on problem identification in research, the revising of scientific literature, the identification and control of variables, the composition of hypothesis, measuring, experimental design, ways to collect and interpret data and ethical and security aspects.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.E.IT.CT.	Earth and space sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems
EXPECTATION	EI.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - The universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	EI.T.CT1.EM. EI.T.CT1.EM.1.	Structure and organization level of matter Investigates on the origin and evolution of the universe. Emphasis is on the Big Bang Theory.
	EI.T.CT1.EM.2.	Gets information from various sources to describe life cycles of stars and correlates its life cycles with their apparent and absolute magnitudes.
INDICATOR	EI.T.CT1.IE. EI.T.CT1.IE.1.	Interactions and energy Develops and uses a model to describe gravity's role in the movement of galaxies and the solar system.

		Emphasis is on the gravitational model as the force that keeps the solar system and Milky Way united and that controls orbit movements within these. Model examples may be physical, conceptual or digital.
	E.I.T.CT1.IE.2.	Creates an explanation of the various roles of the Sun and its importance in everyday life. Emphasis must include the Sun as a source of energy for life, solar cycles, magnetic storms, and nuclear fusion and fission.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	E.I.T.CT1.CC.1.	Develops and uses an Earth-Moon-Sun model to describe cyclical lunar phases, Sun and Moon eclipses, and the seasons. Develops an explanation on how these patterns have positive and negative impacts on everyday life.
	E.I.T.CT1.CC.2.	Obtains and evaluates information to present an argument related to the importance space exploration has had in the history of human beings and the impact it could have in the future.
DOMAIN		Earth's geological history
EXPECTATION	E.I.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Earth's geological eras; Earth's materials and systems; Tectonic plates and system interaction at large scale; Water's role in the formation of Earth's surface; Bio-geology
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	E.I.T.CT1.EM.3.	Builds a scientific explanation based on evidence from rock layers to understand how the geological time scale is used to organize the 4.6 billion years of Earth's geological history. Emphasis is on how the analysis of rock and fossil formation is used to establish the relative age of important events in the geological history of Earth. Examples of the important events on Earth may vary from the most recent (the last glacial era) to the most antique (Earth formation or evidence of the oldest existence of life).
	E.I.T.CT1.EM.4.	Analyzes geological events that gave origin to geographic formation and structure of Puerto Rico. Emphasis is on rock formations, karst zone and cave formation, among others.
	E.I.T.CT1.EM.5.	Describes the important characteristics of Earth's surface. Emphasis is on identifying Earth's layers according to their chemical composition and physical properties, and analyzes the fundamentals of continental drift and its impact on the planet.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	E.I.T.CT1.IE.3.	Builds an explanation based on evidence from various sources about the origin of Earth.
	E.I.T.CT1.IE.4.	Describes the causes and actions of earthquakes and volcanos on Earth's crust. Emphasis is on the relationship of tectonic plates and the results from the Puerto Rico Seismic Network.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change

EI.T.CT1.CC.3. Builds an explanation based on evidence about how geoscience's processes have changed the earth's surface at different moments and spatial scales, and describes the difference between changes at small and large scale. Emphasis is on the processes that change the Earth's surface at spatial and time scales may be large or small, and that in geoscience processes they tend to behave gradually, but they are defined by catastrophic events.

EI.T.CT1.CC.4. Analyzes and interprets data on rock and fossil distribution, continental shapes and ocean floor structures to offer evidence on the plate tectonic theory. Uses this data to predict future evidence for this theory. Emphasis must include evidence found in Puerto Rico.

DOMAIN

Geological processes of Earth

EXPECTATION EI.T.CT2.

Earth's systems - Earth's materials and systems; Water's role in processes of Earth's surface

INDICATOR EI.T.CT2.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

EI.T.CT2.EM.1.

Explains how erosive agents contribute to the formation of coastal structures. Emphasis is on comparing Puerto Rico's beaches.

EI.T.CT2.EM.2.

Uses different types of cartographic projections to describe earth's surface. Emphasis is on using geographic coordinates, level curves, scales, global positioning system, etc.

INDICATOR EI.T.CT2.IE.

Interactions and energy

EI.T.CT2.IE.1.

Develops a model to describe Earth's cycling of matter and the energy flow that is the basis of these processes. Emphasis is on melting, crystalizing, weathering, deformation and sedimentation processes, that act together to form rocks and minerals thru the circulation of Earth's materials.

EI.T.CT2.IE.2.

Develops a model to describe the circulation of water thru Earth's systems, driven by Sun's energy and gravity force. Emphasis is on the way in which water changes its state as it moves thru the multiple paths of the hydrologic cycle.

EI.T.CT2.IE.3.

Identifies the components and describes the process in which carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus biogeochemical cycles happen, among others.

INDICATOR EI.T.CT2.CC.

Conservation and change

EI.T.CT2.CC.1.

Presents a scientific explanation based on evidence about how uneven distribution of minerals, energy and subterraneous water resources are results of past and future processes of geoscience. Emphasis is on how these resources are limited and typically non-renewable, and how their distribution is significantly changing due to the extraction of these by humans. Examples of uneven distribution of resources as result of past processes include but are not limited to oil, metals, minerals and soil.

DOMAIN

Terrestrial atmosphere

EXPECTATION EI.T.CT2.

Earth's systems - Water's role on the processes of

		Earth's surface; Meteorology and atmospheric conditions; Global climate change
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	E.I.T.CT2.IE.4.	Collects data to offer evidence on how movement and complex interactions between air masses result in changes of weather conditions. Emphasis is on how masses of air flow from high pressure regions to low pressure regions, altering climate conditions (temperature, pressure, humidity, precipitation, and wind) in fixed locations over time, and how when different masses of air collide, sudden changes may arise in the climate. Emphasis is on how climate can be predicted using probability.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	E.I.T.CT2.CC.2.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the rotation of Earth and uneven heat cause atmospheric and oceanic circulation patterns that determine regional climates. Emphasis is on how the patterns vary according to the latitude, altitude and geographic distribution of Earth. Emphasis will also be on atmospheric circulation in latitudinal bands determined by solar light, Coriolis effect, and resulting winds. Oceanic circulation must be focused on the heat transference of the global oceanic convection cycle, limited by the Coriolis effect and the continental edges. Special emphasis is on Puerto Rico's climate.
	E.I.T.CT2.CC.3.	Formulates questions that sustain evidence on the factors that have provoked the increase in global temperature during the 20th century and early 21st century.
DOMAIN		Human impact on natural resources
EXPECTATION	E.I.T.CT3.	Earth and human activity - Natural resources; Natural dangers; Human impact on Earth's systems; Global climate change
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	E.I.T.CT3.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data about natural dangers to predict catastrophic events and makes an oral and written report on the development of technologies to mitigate its effects.
	E.I.T.CT3.IE.2.	Builds an argument supported by evidence on how the increase of human population and natural resources consumption per capita impacts Earth's systems. Examples of evidence include databases on human population and consumption rates of food and natural resources. Examples of impacts may include changes in appearance, composition and structures in Earth's systems, and also the speed in which these changes occur.
	E.I.T.CT3.IE.3.	Builds an argument supported by evidence to describe the main and alternative sources of energy and explains the advantages and disadvantages of the use of each of these sources.

INDICATOR	EI.T.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	EI.T.CT3.CC.1.	Applies scientific principles to design a monitoring method to minimize human impact on the environment. Examples of design processes may include to examine human impact on the environment, evaluate possible solutions and design and evaluate solutions that can help reduce impact.
	EI.T.CT3.CC.2.	Builds an explanation on the main causes of global climate changes in Puerto Rico, and designs a plan to reverse these changes in the local community, focusing on the benefits and problems of the design.
	EI.T.CT3.CC.3.	Formulates questions to determine how the different interactions in environmental systems affect the health of the system in the long term, and describes solutions that return the systems equilibrium.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	EI.T.IT1.	Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Optimizes the design's solution
INDICATOR	EI.T.IT1.IT.	Design for engineering
	EI.T.IT1.IT.1.	Defines the specifications and limitations of a design problem with enough precision to assure a successful solution, taking into consideration the relevant scientific principles and potential impact on people and environment that could limit possible solutions.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.2.	Develops a model to generate data when realizing interactive tests and modifications to an object, tool or process, in order to document and obtain the optimum design.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.3.	Analyzes data from tests to determine similarities and differences between different design solutions, and identify the best characteristics of each, and combine them into a new solution, that better serves the criteria for their success.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.4.	Evaluates competitive design solutions using a systematic process to determine how well the specifications and problem limitations are attended. Emphasis is on realizing projects where various disciplines are integrated, for example, robotics.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.5.	Realizes research in all its parts. Emphasis is on realizing the experimental phase of the research proposal, collecting, analyzing and interpreting data, compose the research's report and communicate the results.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.EI.B.CB.	Biological Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure, function and information processing
EXPECTATION	EI.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: Structures and processes - Structure and function; Organism growth and development
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter

- EI.B.CB1.EM.1. Recognizes that living beings are composed of cells; either one cell or many different cells in variable quantities. Emphasis is on developing evidence that a cell is the basic functional structure in living organisms and understanding that living beings can be composed of one or many cells.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.2. Uses technology to develop and use a model that describes the total function of a cell and the ways its parts contribute to its functions. Emphasis is on the functioning of the cell as a total system and the main role of the cell's parts, specifically the nucleus, chloroplasts, mitochondria, cell membrane and cell wall.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.3. Compares and contrasts the processes of cellular reproduction. Emphasis is on cellular cycle, mitosis and meiosis.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.4. Demonstrates that the body is a system formed by sub-systems formed by groups of cells that interact between themselves. Emphasis is on the conceptual comprehension that cells form tissues and tissues form specialized organs to realize specific corporal functions. Examples may include: the interaction of subsystems within a system and the normal function of those systems. Evaluation is limited to circulatory, excretory, digestive, respiratory, muscular and nervous systems.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.5. Collects and summarizes information on sensorial receptors that respond to stimuli sending messages to the brain for immediate conduct or memory storage.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.6. Builds a model of mammal reproduction, internal or external fertilization; and the stages of human development.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.7. Defines the differences of masculine and feminine reproductive systems in humans, and the structure and function changes during adolescence, puberty, fertilization and pregnancy.
- EI.B.CB1.EM.8. Compares the differences in structure and function between plant angiosperms and gymnosperms.

DOMAIN

Growth, development and reproduction of organisms.

EXPECTATION EI.B.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: Structures and processes - Growth and development of organisms

INDICATOR EI.B.CB1.IE.

Interactions and energy

EI.B.CB1.IE.1.

Explains how specialized structures of plants and animal behavior have evolved to contribute to the reproduction and preservation of species. Examples of plant structures can include bright flowers that attract pollinators. Examples of conducts that affect the animal reproductive probability may include, building nests to protect offspring from cold, herd organization to protect themselves from predators, and vocalization and bright feathering to attract mates.

EI.B.CB1.IE.2.

Evaluates how environmental and genetic factors influence the growth of organisms. Understands how scientists use genetic knowledge to predict offspring.

Examples of local environmental conditions may include food, light, space, and water availability. Examples of genetic factors may include breeding large sized cattle and the types of problems that affect organism growth. Examples of evidence may include drought that affects the growth of plants, the use of fertilizers that increase growth in plants, different variety of seeds growing at a different speed under different conditions, an fish that grow larger in larger tanks contrary to fish in reduced spaces.

EI.B.CB1.IE.3. Defines the role of adolescents in society through information collection about adolescent periods and the difference between sex, gender, and sexuality. Recognizes that fertilization and birth are essential processes for life.

DOMAIN

Organism classification

EXPECTATION EI.B.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Interactions between kingdoms and group behavior

INDICATOR EI.B.CB1.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

EI.B.CB1.EM.9.

Identifies the characteristics that are used to group organisms by a classification system.

EI.B.CB1.EM.10.

Identifies the organization levels of organisms in a kingdom. Example: scientific name = gender - species; taxonomy = kingdom- phylum- class- order- family- gender- species.

DOMAIN

Growth, development and reproduction of organisms

EXPECTATION EI.B.CB3.

Heredity and characteristic variations - Characteristic heredity; Variations in characteristics.

INDICATOR EI.B.CB3.CC.

Conservation and change

EI.B.CB3.CC.1.

Explains why the structural changes in genes (mutations) found in chromosomes may affect proteins and cause beneficial, harmful or neutral changes in the structure and function of an organism. Emphasis is on the conceptual comprehension that changes in genetic material may result in the production of different protein.

EI.B.CB3.CC.2.

Builds a model to explain why asexual reproduction results in identical genetic information offspring and why sexual reproduction results in variable genetic information. Emphasis is on the use of models as Punnett squares, diagrams and simulations to describe the relationships cause-effect in the transmission of parent's genes to offspring, that result in genetic variations.

EI.B.CB3.CC.3.

Distinguishes between internal and external reproduction.

EI.B.CB3.CC.4.

Collects and communicates information on mammal reproduction and the stages of human development.

EI.B.CB3.CC.5.

Describes the DNA structure and explains the importance of this in living beings.

DOMAIN

Natural selection and adaptations

EXPECTATION EI.B.CB4.

Biological evolution: unity and diversity - Evidence of

		common ancestors and diversity; Natural and artificial selection; Adaptation
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.B.CB4.IE.1.	Devises arguments on the impact of genetic engineering and biotechnology in agriculture, food production and medical applications, among others.
	EI.B.CB4.IE.2.	Collects and summarizes information about the technologies that have changed the way humans control characteristic heredity wished in organisms. Emphasis is on the synthesis of information from reliable sources about the influence of humans in the genetic results in artificial selection (such as genetic modification).
INDICATOR	EI.B.CB4.CC.	Conservation and change
	EI.B.CB4.CC.1.	Interprets data about patterns in fossil records that document the existence, diversity, extinction and change in life forms thru the history of life on Earth, under the assumption that natural laws operate in the present that same as in the past. Emphasis is on finding patterns in the complexity level of anatomic structures of organisms and the chronological order of fossil appearance in rock layers.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.2.	Compares the anatomical similarities and differences between present organisms and fossil organisms to infer evolutionary relationships. Emphasis is on explanations about evolutionary relationships between organisms, in terms of similarities or differences in the general appearances of anatomical structures.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.3.	Compares similarity patterns in the embryological development between multiple species and identifies non-evident relationships in the already complete formed anatomy. Emphasis is on inferring general patterns of relationships between different organisms' embryos comparing the macroscopic appearance in diagrams and images. The comparison evaluation is limited to the general appearance of anatomical structures in the embryological development.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.4.	Explains how genetic variations in the characteristics of a population increase the probability of survival and reproduction of some individuals in a specific environment. Emphasis is on using simple assumptions about probability and proportional reasoning to build explanations.
	EI.B.CB4.CC.5.	Uses mathematical representations to support the explanations on how natural selection can lead to increases or decreases of specific characteristics in certain populations throughout time. Emphasis is on the use of mathematical models, probability assumptions and proportional reasoning to support the explanations on change tendencies in populations over time. The evaluations do not include Hardy Weinberg calculations.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	EI.B.IT 1.	Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimize the

		design solution
INDICATOR	EI.B.IT.1.IT.	Design for engineering
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.1.	Defines specifications and limitations of a design problem with sufficient precision to assure a successful solution, taking into consideration the relevant scientific principles and potential impacts on people and the environment, that could limit the possible solutions.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.2.	Develops a model to generate data when realizing interactive tests and modifications to an object, tool or process, in order to document and obtain the optimal design.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.3.	Analyzes data from the tests to determine similarities and differences between several design solutions, and identifies the best characteristics of each one, and combines them into a new solution, that better attends the criteria for the their success.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.4.	Evaluates competitive design solutions using a systematic process to determine how properly the specifications and problem limitations are taken care of. Emphasis is on realizing projects where various disciplines, like robotics, are integrated.
	EI.B.IT.1.IT.5.	Knows the inherent fundamental concepts for the creation of a research proposal. Emphasis is on knowing the scientific method and bases for the development of a research proposal. Research problem identification, variable identification, hypothesis writing, measurement, and means to collect and interpret data must be emphasized, also ethical and security aspects.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.EI.F.CF.	Physical Sciences
DOMAIN		Structure and properties of matter
EXPECTATION	EI.F.CF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Chemical reactions; Definitions of energy
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF1.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	EI.F.CF1.EM.1.	Collects information from reliable sources to explain the use of knowledge on atomic models and the atomic theory.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.2.	Uses knowledge about atomic structures to classify the families of chemical elements and predict their location on the periodic table.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.3.	Describes the processes in which substances are combined to form compounds. Emphasis is on simple ionic and covalent bonds, Lewis structures and valence electrons.
	EI.F.CF1.EM.4.	Develops models to describe the atomic composition of simple molecules and extended structures. Examples of simple molecules may include water and carbon dioxide. Examples of extended structures may include sodium chloride or a diamond. Examples of models at a molecular level may include drawings, 3D models, or computer

		representations.
	EI.FCF1.EM.5.	Collects and understands information to describe that synthetic materials are produced from natural resources and have an impact on society. Emphasis is on natural resources that go thru a chemical process to form synthetic material. Examples may include: new medicines, food and alternative fuels.
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.FCF1.IE.1.	Develops a model that proves changes in the movement of particles, temperature and state of a substance when thermal energy is added or removed. Emphasis is on qualitative models of a molecular level of solids, liquids and gases to prove that by adding or removing thermal energy, kinetic particle energy increases or decreases until a change in state occurs. Examples of particles may include molecules or atoms. Examples of substances may include water, carbon dioxide and helium.
DOMAIN		Chemical reactions
EXPECTATION	EI.FCF1.	Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Chemical reactions; nuclear fusion
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.FCF1.IE.2.	Plans and conducts research to provide data on how the chemical and physical properties of substances interact to determine if a reaction has occurred. Examples of reactions may include burning sugar or steel wool and the reaction of acetic acid with sodium bicarbonate.
	EI.FCF1.IE.3.	Realizes a project to build, demonstrate and modify an apparatus that liberates or absorbs thermal energy thru chemical processes. Emphasis is on the design, controlling the energy transference to the environment, and on the modification of an apparatus using factor such as the type and concentration of a substance. Examples of designs may involve chemical reactions such as dissolving sodium bicarbonate and acetic acid (vinegar). Endothermic (absorbs energy) and exothermic (liberates energy) chemical reaction concepts are integrated.
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.CC.	Conservation and change
	EI.FCF1.CC.1.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the total number of atoms doesn't change in a chemical reaction, and therefore mass is conserved. Emphasis is on applying the Matter Conservation Law in the balanced chemical equations represented by physical models or drawings, including digital media to represent atoms.
INDICATOR	EI.FCF1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	EI.FCF1.EM.6.	Designs and realizes an experiment to demonstrate the difference between a compound and a mixture based on the methods (chemical or physical) that are used to separate them (mixtures) or decompose them (compounds). Emphasis is on that mixtures are separated by physical methods (filtration, chromatography, decantation, crystallization, distillation,

		among others), while a compound is decomposed by chemical methods (heating, electrolysis, photolysis).
	EI.FCF1.EM.7.	Collects evidence to establish a contrast between a diluted, saturated and over-saturated solution, explains their properties, and provides examples and uses of each of these types of solutions in everyday life.
	EI.FCF1.EM.8.	Analyzes the general properties of acids and bases (alkaline substances) and applies them in the qualitative determination of pH of different materials (mixtures and substances) as a way to classify them as acids or alkaline, as well as provide examples of their uses and applications in science and everyday life. Examples may be the use of antacids to control the pH of gastric juices, pH in swimming pools, acid rain, hygiene and cleaning products.
	EI.FCF1.EM.9.	Collects evidence from different sources to build an explanation about the risks and dangers of chemical substances in everyday life. Examples of risks may include flammable corrosive, and radioactive.
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions
EXPECTATION	EI.FCF2.	Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions: Energy in chemical processes in daily life.
INDICATOR	EI.FCF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.FCF2.IE.1.	Compares Newton's movement laws (first, second and third) and applies them to design a research that proves each one of them. Emphasis is on the differences between mass and weight concepts.
	EI.FCF2.IE.2.	Plans a research to give proof on the sum of forces in a collision, considering the forces that act on an object and its mass. Evidence can be provided thru quantitative and qualitative comparisons.
	EI.FCF2.IE.3.	Builds and presents arguments using reliable evidence to support the premise that gravitational interactions are by attraction and depend on interacting objects mass.
	EI.FCF2.IE.4.	Explains, thru evidence, the nature of electric and magnetic forces present in matter, and uses knowledge for the design of simple electrical circuits, in series and in parallel.
	EI.FCF2.IE.5.	Realizes research and evaluates the experimental design to give evidence that force fields between objects exist, even when the objects are not in contact. Emphasis is on gravitational fields, electric fields and magnetic fields.
	EI.FCF2.IE.6.	Collects evidence to support and explanation and provide examples that correlate the importance of work, force and energy concepts in everyday life.
	EI.FCF2.IE.7.	Creates a problem solution using a simple machine or a compound machine.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	EI.FCF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; conservation and

		transference of energy; relationship between forces and energy.
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.F.CF3.IE.1.	Builds and interprets graphic information from data to describe the relationships between kinetic energy, mass and speed of an object.
	EI.F.CF3.IE.2.	Develops a model to explain that when changing the layout of objects that interact at a distance, different quantities of potential energy are stored.
	EI.F.CF3.IE.3.	Applies scientific principles to design, build and try an apparatus that minimizes or maximizes thermal energy transference.
	EI.F.CF3.IE.4.	Plans research about thermal energy transference that determines the relationships between the transferred energy, type of material, mass and change in the average kinetic energy particles from the sample's temperature measurements.
	EI.F.CF3.IE.5.	Builds, uses and presents arguments to support the premise that when kinetic energy of an object changes, energy is transferred from or to the object. Emphasis is on the Conservation of Energy Law.
DOMAIN		Waves and electromagnetic radiation
EXPECTATION	EI.F.CF4.	Waves and their applications in information technology transference - Wave's properties; electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF4.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	EI.F.CF4.EM.1.	Plans research to collect evidence that describes sound and light wave properties. Emphasis is on the electromagnetic spectrum model and the difference between mechanic and electromagnetic waves.
	EI.F.CF4.EM.2.	Integrates qualitative scientific information and technical information to support the premise that digital signals are the most trustworthy way to encrypt and transmit information rather than analogue signals. Emphasis is on the basic comprehension that waves can be used for communication purposes. Examples may include: use of optic fiber to transmit light pulses, radio pulse waves in wi-fi apparatus, and the conversion of binary patterns kept to generate a text or sound on a computer screen.
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF4.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.F.CF4.IE.1.	Gets and communicates information to correlate the range and energy of waves. Emphasis is on the Sun as energy source and radiant energy forms. (Electromagnetic spectrum)
INDICATOR	EI.F.CF4.CC.	Conservation and change
	EI.F.CF4.CC.1.	Creates models to represent the different wave behaviors according to their movement thru different environments. Emphasis is on wave interactions such as reflection, refraction, dispersion and interference.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	EI.F.IT1.	Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering

		problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimizes the design solution
INDICATOR	EI.F.IT 1.IT.	Design for engineering
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.1.	Defines the specifications and limitations of a design problem with enough precision to assure a successful solution, taking into consideration the relevant scientific principles and potential impacts on people and the environment that could limit the possible solutions.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.2.	Develops a model to generate data when making interactive tests and changes to an object, tool or process, to document and obtain the optimal design.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.3.	Analyzes test's data to determine the similarities and differences between various design solutions, and identifies the best characteristics of each one, and combines them into a new solution, that better serves the criteria for the success of these.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.4.	Evaluates solutions for competitive design using a systematic process to determine how well the specifications and problem limitations are served. Emphasis is on realizing projects where various disciplines, like robotics, are integrated.
	EI.F.IT 1.IT.5.	Composes a research proposal. Emphasis is on the composition of a research proposal that integrates acquired knowledge on problem identification in research, the revising of scientific literature, the identification and control of variables, the composition of hypothesis, measuring, experimental design, ways to collect and interpret data and ethical and security aspects.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.EI.T.CT.	Earth and space sciences
DOMAIN		Space systems
EXPECTATION	EI.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - The universe and stars; Earth and the solar system
INDICATOR	EI.T.CT1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	EI.T.CT1.EM.1.	Investigates on the origin and evolution of the universe. Emphasis is on the Big Bang Theory.
	EI.T.CT1.EM.2.	Gets information from various sources to describe life cycles of stars and correlates its life cycles with their apparent and absolute magnitudes.
INDICATOR	EI.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	EI.T.CT1.IE.1.	Develops and uses a model to describe gravity's role in the movement of galaxies and the solar system. Emphasis is on the gravitational model as the force that keeps the solar system and Milky Way united and that controls orbit movements within these. Model examples may be physical, conceptual or digital.
	EI.T.CT1.IE.2.	Creates an explanation of the various roles of the Sun and its importance in everyday life. Emphasis must include the Sun as a source of energy for life, solar cycles, magnetic storms, and nuclear fusion and fission.

INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	E.I.T.CT1.CC.1.	Develops and uses an Earth-Moon-Sun model to describe cyclical lunar phases, Sun and Moon eclipses, and the seasons. Develops an explanation on how these patterns have positive and negative impacts on everyday life.
	E.I.T.CT1.CC.2.	Obtains and evaluates information to present an argument related to the importance space exploration has had in the history of human beings and the impact it could have in the future.
DOMAIN		Earth's geological history
EXPECTATION	E.I.T.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Earth's geological eras; Earth's materials and systems; Tectonic plates and system interaction at large scale; Water's role in the formation of Earth's surface; Bio-geology
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	E.I.T.CT1.EM.3.	Builds a scientific explanation based on evidence from rock layers to understand how the geological time scale is used to organize the 4.6 billion years of Earth's geological history. Emphasis is on how the analysis of rock and fossil formation is used to establish the relative age of important events in the geological history of Earth. Examples of the important events on Earth may vary from the most recent (the last glacial era) to the most antique (Earth formation or evidence of the oldest existence of life).
	E.I.T.CT1.EM.4.	Analyzes geological events that gave origin to geographic formation and structure of Puerto Rico. Emphasis is on rock formations, karst zone and cave formation, among others.
	E.I.T.CT1.EM.5.	Describes the important characteristics of Earth's surface. Emphasis is on identifying Earth's layers according to their chemical composition and physical properties, and analyzes the fundamentals of continental drift and its impact on the planet.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	E.I.T.CT1.IE.3.	Builds an explanation based on evidence from various sources about the origin of Earth.
	E.I.T.CT1.IE.4.	Describes the causes and actions of earthquakes and volcanos on Earth's crust. Emphasis is on the relationship of tectonic plates and the results from the Puerto Rico Seismic Network.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	E.I.T.CT1.CC.3.	Builds an explanation based on evidence about how geoscience's processes have changed the earth's surface at different moments and spatial scales, and describes the difference between changes at small and large scale. Emphasis is on the processes that change the Earth's surface at spatial and time scales may be large or small, and that in geoscience processes they tend to behave gradually, but they are defined by catastrophic events.

	E.I.T.CT1.CC.4.	Analyzes and interprets data on rock and fossil distribution, continental shapes and ocean floor structures to offer evidence on the plate tectonic theory. Uses this data to predict future evidence for this theory. Emphasis must include evidence found in Puerto Rico.
DOMAIN		Geological processes of Earth
EXPECTATION	E.I.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth's materials and systems; Water's role in processes of Earth's surface
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	E.I.T.CT2.EM.1.	Explains how erosive agents contribute to the formation of coastal structures. Emphasis is on comparing Puerto Rico's beaches.
	E.I.T.CT2.EM.2.	Uses different types of cartographic projections to describe earth's surface. Emphasis is on using geographic coordinates, level curves, scales, global positioning system, etc.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	E.I.T.CT2.IE.1.	Develops a model to describe Earth's cycling of matter and the energy flow that is the basis of these processes. Emphasis is on melting, crystalizing, weathering, deformation and sedimentation processes, that act together to form rocks and minerals thru the circulation of Earth's materials.
	E.I.T.CT2.IE.2.	Develops a model to describe the circulation of water thru Earth's systems, driven by Sun's energy and gravity force. Emphasis is on the way in which water changes its state as it moves thru the multiple paths of the hydrologic cycle.
	E.I.T.CT2.IE.3.	Identifies the components and describes the process in which carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus biogeochemical cycles happen, among others.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.CC.	Conservation and change
	E.I.T.CT2.CC.1.	Presents a scientific explanation based on evidence about how uneven distribution of minerals, energy and subterranean water resources are results of past and future processes of geoscience. Emphasis is on how these resources are limited and typically non-renewable, and how their distribution is significantly changing due to the extraction of these by humans. Examples of uneven distribution of resources as result of past processes include but are not limited to oil, metals, minerals and soil.
DOMAIN		Terrestrial atmosphere
EXPECTATION	E.I.T.CT2.	Earth's systems - Water's role on the processes of Earth's surface; Meteorology and atmospheric conditions; Global climate change
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	E.I.T.CT2.IE.4.	Collects data to offer evidence on how movement and complex interactions between air masses result in changes of weather conditions. Emphasis is on how masses of air flow from high pressure regions to low pressure regions, altering climate conditions

(temperature, pressure, humidity, precipitation, and wind) in fixed locations over time, and how when different masses of air collide, sudden changes may arise in the climate. Emphasis is on how climate can be predicted using probability.

INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT2.CC. E.I.T.CT2.CC.2.	Conservation and change Develops and uses a model to describe how the rotation of Earth and uneven heat cause atmospheric and oceanic circulation patterns that determine regional climates. Emphasis is on how the patterns vary according to the latitude, altitude and geographic distribution of Earth. Emphasis will also be on atmospheric circulation in latitudinal bands determined by solar light, Coriolis effect, and resulting winds. Oceanic circulation must be focused on the heat transference of the global oceanic convection cycle, limited by the Coriolis effect and the continental edges. Special emphasis is on Puerto Rico's climate.
	E.I.T.CT2.CC.3.	Formulates questions that sustain evidence on the factors that have provoked the increase in global temperature during the 20th century and early 21st century.
DOMAIN		Human impact on natural resources
EXPECTATION	E.I.T.CT3.	Earth and human activity - Natural resources; Natural dangers; Human impact on Earth's systems; Global climate change
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT3.IE. E.I.T.CT3.IE.1.	Interactions and energy Analyzes and interprets data about natural dangers to predict catastrophic events and makes an oral and written report on the development of technologies to mitigate its effects.
	E.I.T.CT3.IE.2.	Builds an argument supported by evidence on how the increase of human population and natural resources consumption per capita impacts Earth's systems. Examples of evidence include databases on human population and consumption rates of food and natural resources. Examples of impacts may include changes in appearance, composition and structures in Earth's systems, and also the speed in which these changes occur.
	E.I.T.CT3.IE.3.	Builds an argument supported by evidence to describe the main and alternative sources of energy and explains the advantages and disadvantages of the use of each of these sources.
INDICATOR	E.I.T.CT3.CC. E.I.T.CT3.CC.1.	Conservation and change Applies scientific principles to design a monitoring method to minimize human impact on the environment. Examples of design processes may include to examine human impact on the environment, evaluate possible solutions and design and evaluate solutions that can help reduce impact.
	E.I.T.CT3.CC.2.	Builds an explanation on the main causes of global

		climate changes in Puerto Rico, and designs a plan to reverse these changes in the local community, focusing on the benefits and problems of the design.
	EI.T.CT3.CC.3.	Formulates questions to determine how the different interactions in environmental systems affect the health of the system in the long term, and describes solutions that return the systems equilibrium.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	EI.T.IT1.	Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Optimizes the design's solution
INDICATOR	EI.T.IT1.IT.	Design for engineering
	EI.T.IT1.IT.1.	Defines the specifications and limitations of a design problem with enough precision to assure a successful solution, taking into consideration the relevant scientific principles and potential impact on people and environment that could limit possible solutions.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.2.	Develops a model to generate data when realizing interactive tests and modifications to an object, tool or process, in order to document and obtain the optimum design.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.3.	Analyzes data from tests to determine similarities and differences between different design solutions, and identify the best characteristics of each, and combine them into a new solution, that better serves the criteria for their success.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.4.	Evaluates competitive design solutions using a systematic process to determine how well the specifications and problem limitations are attended. Emphasis is on realizing projects where various disciplines are integrated, for example, robotics.
	EI.T.IT1.IT.5.	Realizes research in all its parts. Emphasis is on realizing the experimental phase of the research proposal, collecting, analyzing and interpreting data, compose the research's report and communicate the results.
CONTENT STANDARD	PR.ES.B.	Biology
DOMAIN		From molecules to organisms: structures and processes
EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB1.	From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Structure and function; flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycles and energy transference in ecosystems; Organism's development and growth
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB1.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ES.B.CB1.EM.1.	Uses models of cell types to establish differences between the organelles and their functions, including the nucleus, that contains the genetic material that determines heredity.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.2.	Analyzes the structure of DNA and RNA molecules and their replication by means of tridimensional models.

	ES.B.CB1.EM.3.	Explains, using scientific evidence, how DNA's structure determines the structure of proteins that perform the essential functions of life thru specialized cell systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.4.	Uses a model to illustrate the rank organization and interaction of systems that realize specific functions within multicellular organisms. Includes the human body systems such as: digestive, circulatory and immunological, skeletal, muscular, nervous, excretory, reproductive, integumentary and endocrinological systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.5.	Plans and realizes a research to provide evidence that the reaction mechanisms keep homeostasis. Examples of research may include the average of heartbeats in reaction to exercise, the reaction of stomas to humidity and temperature, a root's development in reaction to water levels.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.6.	Represents with concept maps or graph organizers, the relationship between the processes that occur in the mitochondria of cells during cellular respiration.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.7.	Builds diagrams and models to represent the changes that occur during the cellular division phases and cellular differentiation, when producing and keeping complex organisms.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB1.IE.1.	Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on making models of biogeochemical cycles that include carbon cycles in the oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) providing the base for living organisms.
	ES B.CB1.IE.2.	Builds and revises an explanation based on evidence on how carbon, hydrogen and oxygen of sugar molecules can combine with other elements to form amino-acids and other carbon molecules. Emphasis is on the use of models and simulations that support this explanation.
	ES B.CB1.IE.3.	Develops a model that illustrates that cellular respiration is a chemical process by which food molecule links and oxygen molecules break-up and form new links, resulting in a net energy transference. Emphasis is on conceptual understanding of entry and exit processes during cellular respiration.
	ES B.CB1.IE.4.	Uses models to illustrate how photosynthesis and respiration transform light energy into stored chemical energy. Emphasis is on the illustration of entry and exit of matter and the transference and transformation of energy in photosynthesis by plants and other photosynthetic organisms. Examples of models can include diagrams, chemical equations and conceptual models.
	ES B.CB1.IE.5.	Collects information about macromolecules (proteins, lipids, carbon hydrates, nucleic acids) that compose a cell and uses it to explain that spatial atom distribution in these determine some of their functions in living

		organisms.
	ES B.CB1.IE.6.	Explains thru models, the function and structure of cellular membrane in relation to particle movement in biotic and abiotic systems such as: diffusion and osmosis.
	ES B.CB1.IE.7.	Collects evidence to explain that the protein synthesis process is essential in the enzyme production that regulates all the processes that the cell realizes.
DOMAIN		Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics
EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB2.	Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics - Interdependent relationships in ecosystems; Dynamics, functioning and resistance of ecosystems; Cyclical movement of matter and energy transference in ecosystems; Social interactions and group behavior; Human beings and biodiversity; Development of a possible solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB2.EM.1.	Uses mathematical or technological representations to support explanations about the factors that affect the carrying capacity of ecosystems at different scales. Emphasis is on the quantitative analysis and relationship comparison between interdependent factors including limits, resources, climate and competition. Examples of mathematical comparisons may include graphs, tables, histograms, and population changes collected from simulations and historical data.
	ES.B.CB2.EM.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support and revise the explanations based on evidence about the factors that affect biodiversity and populations in ecosystems ant different scales. Examples of mathematical representations include finding an average, determine trends or patterns, and use comparative graphs of a variety of data.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB2.IE.1.	Builds and revises an explanation, based on evidence, about the cycles of matter and energy flow in aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of aerobic and anaerobic respiration in different environments.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support statements on matter's cycles and energy flow between organisms of an ecosystem. Emphasis is on the use of mathematical models of energy storage in biomass, to describe the flow transference of energy thru ecosystems. Emphasis is on atoms and molecules (such as carbon, oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) that are kept as they pass thru an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.3.	Develops models to illustrate the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples of models could include simulations and mathematical models. The evaluation does not include the specific chemical steps of photosynthesis and respiration.

ES.B.CB2.IE.4. Evaluates statements, evidence and reasoning that complex interactions of ecosystems keep the number and type of organisms in a relatively consistent way in stable conditions. But changes in the conditions may result in a new ecosystem. Examples of changes in the conditions of an ecosystem may include small changes, either physical or biological such as temporary hunting or flooding; or extreme changes as volcanic eruptions and increase in sea levels.

INDICATOR ES.B.CB2.CC. Conservation and change

ES.B.CB2.CC.1. Identifies environmental factors to discuss the negative and positive effects of population growth.

ES.B.CB2.CC.2. Builds a model that represents and explains the step sequence of ecological succession states in an ecosystem.

ES.B.CB2.CC.3. Explains the relationship between populations, communities and ecosystems of the biosphere.

ES.B.CB2.CC.4. Designs, evaluates and refines a solution to reduce the impact of human activities in the environment and biodiversity. Examples of the activities may include urbanization, dam construction, dissemination of invading species.

ES.B.CB2.CC.5. Evaluates scientific evidence of group behavior of individuals and the opportunity they have to survive and reproduce. Emphasis is on : (1) distinguishing between group and individual behavior, (2) identifying evidence that supports the results of group behavior and (3) developing logical and reasonable arguments based on evidence. Examples of group behavior may include flocks, herds and cooperative behaviors such as hunting, migrations and swarms.

DOMAIN Heredity and characteristic variations

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB3. Heredity and characteristic variations - Structure and function; Characteristic heredity; Characteristic variations

INDICATOR ES.B.CB3.EM. Structure and organization level of matter

ES.B.CB3.EM.1. Poses questions to clarify the relationship of DNA's role and chromosomes in the instruction codes for the characteristic variations that pass from one generation to another.

INDICATOR ES.B.CB3.CC. Conservation and change

ES.B.CB3.CC.1. Poses and defends a statement based on evidence about the genetic and hereditary variations that can result from: (1) new genetic combination thru the meiosis process, (2) viable errors that may occur during DNA replication and/or (3) mutations caused by environmental factors. Emphasis is on the use of data to support arguments on the different forms in which mutations can occur.

ES.B.CB3.CC.2. Applies statistical and probability concepts to explain the variation and distribution of visible characteristics in a population. Emphasis is on the use of mathematics to describe the probability and characteristic presence that

are related to genetics and environmental factors., as well as representing phenotypic and genotypic proportions in different genetic crossings.

ES.B.CB3.CC.3. Recognizes and explains that multicellular organisms are developed from a simple zygote and that the resulting phenotype will depend on the genotype that was established at the moment of fertilization.

ES.B.CB3.CC.4. Explains the importance of life's continuity thru the action of genes, hereditary patterns, organism reproduction and cell reproduction.

DOMAIN

Natural selection and evolution

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB4.

Biological evolution: Unity and diversity - Evidence of common ancestors and diversity; Adaptation; Natural selection; Biodiversity and human beings; Development of a possible solution

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

ES.B.CB4.EM.1.

Communicates scientific information that biological evolution and common ancestors are supported by multiple lines of empiric evidence. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of each evidence line has and biological in relation to the common ancestor evidence and biological evolution. Examples of evidence may include similarities in the DNA sequences, anatomic structures and development appearance order of embryological structures.

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.B.CB4.IE.1.

Builds an explanation based on evidence that the evolution process mainly results from four factors: (1) a species potential to increase in quantity, (2) the genetic variation of individuals in a species by mutation or sexual reproduction, (3) the competition for limited resources that each individual needs to survive and reproduce in the environment, and (4) ensure the proliferation of those organisms that are more able to survive and reproduce in the environment. Emphasis is on the use of evidence to explain the influence that the four factors have on the number of organisms, behaviors, morphology, or physiology, in terms of the ability to compete for limited resources and subsequently, in the individual survival and adaptation of species. Examples of evidence may include mathematical models as a simple distribution graph and proportional reasoning.

ES.B.CB4.IE.2.

Determines the effects of the different types of natural selection in the gene set (gene pool) of an organism.

ES.B.CB4.IE.3.

Applies statistical and probability concepts to support explanations about organisms with advantageous hereditary characteristics that tend to increase in proportion comparing to those that don't have the same characteristics. Emphasis is on the change analysis in the numerical distribution of the characteristics and on using these changes as evidence to support explanation on how natural selection determines the survival capacity for groups of organisms.

	ES.B.CB4.IE.4.	Builds an explanation based on evidence on how natural selection leads to the adaptation of populations. Emphasis is on using data to provide evidence on how biotic and abiotic differences in ecosystems (seasonal temperature changes, long period climate changes, light, acidity, geographic barriers, or evolution of other organisms) contribute to gene changes throughout time, leading to adaptation of the population. Hardy Weinberg's principle is integrated to quantify the process of natural selection in a population.
	ES.B.CB4.IE.5.	Evaluates the role of natural selection in the development of the Theory of Evolution.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB4.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB4.CC.1.	Evaluates the evidence that supports the statements that changes in the environmental conditions may result in: (1) increase in the number of individuals of a species, (2) emergence of new species, (3) extinction of other species. Emphasis is on determining the cause-effect relationships on how environmental changes, such as deforestation, fishing, use of fertilizers, drought, flooding and rate of environmental changes, affect the distribution or disappearance of species' characteristics.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.2.	Reviews and evaluates a simulation to test a solution that decreases the adverse impacts of human activities in biodiversity. Emphasis is on the design of solutions for a proposed problem that is related to a threatened species or in danger of extinction; or with genetic variation of multiple species organisms.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.3.	Analyzes how human beings have the responsibility to keep the environment in good condition for the survival of species.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	ES.B.IT 1.	Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Optimizes the design solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.IT 1.IT.	Design for Engineering
	ES.B.IT 1.IT.1.	Analyzes a major global challenge to specify the limitations and quantitative criteria of solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.
	ES.B.IT 1.IT.2.	Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be resolved using engineering knowledge.
	ES.B.IT 1.IT.3.	Evaluates a real and complex problem solution based on criteria as costs, benefits, security, trustworthiness, and aesthetics considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.
	ES.B.IT 1.IT.4.	Uses a computer simulation to model the impact of proposed solutions to solve a real and complex problem with multiple criteria and limitations within and between the relevant systems to the problem.

CONTENT STANDARD	PR.ES.F.	Physics
DOMAIN		Forces and interactions
EXPECTATION	ES.FCF2.	Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems
INDICATOR	ES.FCF2.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ES.FCF2.EM.1.	Explains what fluids are and describes how these create pressure on a surface. (surface tension)
	ES.FCF2.EM.2.	Explains and describes how the surface tension principles and types of fluids affect mechanization. Emphasis is on applying the kinetic-molecular theory.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.FCF2.IE.1.	Designs a model to explain the movement of a dimension through verbal, graphic and mathematic descriptions. Emphasis is on the movement's description through the concepts of: distance, displacement, speed, velocity and acceleration. The use of the units from the International Measurement System must be integrated, and also their conversions, significant digits, scientific notation and mathematical equations.
	ES.FCF2.IE.2.	Identifies and describes the four fundamental forces in everyday life: strong nuclear interaction, weak nuclear interaction, gravity and electromagnetism.
	ES.FCF2.IE.3.	Uses knowledge on the different movement laws to apply them in problem solutions of everyday life. Emphasis is on the Newton, Coulomb and Kepler laws.
	ES.FCF2.IE.4.	Uses Newton's second law of motion when describing the mathematical relationship between net force on a macroscopic object, its mass and acceleration. Data examples may include tables or position or velocity graphs as time function for objects subject to a non-balanced net force, such as an object in free-fall, and object rolling on a ramp or an object in movement pulled by a constant force.
	ES.FCF2.IE.5.	Uses mathematical representations of Newton's gravitational law and Coulomb's law, to describe and predict gravitational and electrostatic forces between objects.
	ES.FCF2.IE.6.	Explains the functioning of machines, using force and movement concepts that are useful or resolve an everyday-life problem.
	ES.FCF2.IE.7.	Uses mathematical representations to describe movement in two dimensions and the force equilibrium with vectors. Represents and calculates the magnitude and direction of vector quantities by graph and mathematical methods applying the basic trigonometrical functions. Projectile motion and inclined plane are included.
	ES.FCF2.IE.8.	Designs an experiment to explain the principles and applications of uniform circular movement and simple harmonic movement.

	ES.FCF2.IE.9.	Applies scientific and engineering ideas to design and evaluate an apparatus that minimizes the force on a macroscopic object during collision. The examples may include a helmet or parachute.
	ES.FCF2.IE.10.	Explains the concepts of electrical charge, electric current, electric potential, electric field, and magnetic field, and establishes the difference between contact forces and long-range forces. Explains the properties of conductive materials and designs electrical circuits in series and in parallel.
	ES.FCF2.IE.11.	Offers experimental evidence that an electric current may produce a magnetic field and a magnetic field may produce an electric current.
	ES.FCF2.IE.12.	Describes apparatus that resolve everyday-life problems and those which result from the application of physics. Examples of force may be: electrical, magnetic, gravitational and nuclear forces. Examples of apparatus may include those that use conductors, circuits and fields.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.FCF2.CC.1.	Uses mathematical representations to support the premise that the total momentum of a system of objects is preserved when the net force on the system is zero.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	ES.FCF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Energy in chemical processes in everyday-life.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ES.FCF3.EM.1.	Explains energy in terms of scale, from atomic scale to macroscopic scale.
	ES.FCF3.EM.2.	Classifies energy as kinetic or potential and contrasts the different types: thermal, chemical, nuclear, electromagnetic and mechanical. Calculates the kinetic and potential energy changes in a system.
	ES.FCF3.EM.3.	Classifies and explains the origin of different sources of energy: fossil-fuels, solar, geothermal, wind, hydraulic, biomass, among others.
	ES.FCF3.EM.4.	Explains the relationship between energy, work, and power.
	ES.FCF3.EM.5.	Explains the work-energy theorem.
	ES.FCF3.EM.6.	Identifies the electrical phenomena as a manifestation of the charges of subatomic particles (electrons).
	ES.FCF3.EM.7.	Compares electric and magnetic forces regarding the field and its relationship with charges in movement.
	ES.FCF3.EM.8.	Explains the relationships between electrostatic charges using Coulomb's laws.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.FCF3.IE.1.	Calculates the energy change between the components of a system when the energy of one of them is known and the energy flow into or out-of the systems.

- ES.FCF3.IE.2. Designs a model that illustrates that energy at a macroscopic scale may be understood as a combination of energy associated to particle movements (objects) and energy associated to the relative position of particles (objects). Examples of macroscopic scale phenomena may include the conversion of kinetic energy to thermal energy, stored energy in an object positioned over Earth, and stored energy between two electrically charged plates.
- ES.FCF3.IE.3. Designs and refines an apparatus that works within controlled limitations to convert energy from one form into another. Examples of apparatus may include Rube Goldberg, wind turbines, solar cells, solar ovens and generators. Examples of limitations may include the use of renewable energy forms and efficiency.
- ES.FCF3.IE.4. Explains that when two components are combined at different temperatures in an enclosed system, the total transference of thermal energy results in a more uniform energy distribution between the system's components (thermodynamics' second law). Examples of research may include mixing liquids with different initial temperatures or adding different temperature objects to water.
- ES.FCF3.IE.5. Explains the interactions through electrical or magnetic fields to illustrate the forces between objects and energy changes of objects from interaction.
- ES.FCF3.IE.6. Plans and realizes research to propose the use of different energy sources in Puerto Rico, taking into consideration the cost-benefit and cost-effective proportion.

DOMAIN

Waves and their applications

EXPECTATION ES.FCF4.

Waves and their applications to technological development - Wave's properties; Electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.FCF4.EM.1. Explains, through models, the effect of wave's properties in the behavior of matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.2. Distinguishes between the types of mechanical waves: transverse and longitudinal.
- ES.FCF4.EM.3. Explains the idea that electromagnetic radiation can be described with a wave model or particle model, and that in some cases, one of the models is more useful than the other. Examples include how wave and particle models explain the properties of visible light.
- ES.FCF4.EM.4. Explains reflection, refraction, diffraction, polarization, transformation and absorption as manifestations of the interactions between waves and matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.5. Proposes the development of technology that demonstrates the application of light properties in the design of useful prototypes or to resolve a daily-life problem.
- ES.FCF4.EM.6. Explains and describes how wave principles are used to

create useful technologies for humans.

- ES.FCF4.EM.7. Communicates technical information on how some technological apparatus use behavioral principles and interactions of waves with matter to transmit and capture information and energy. Examples may include solar cells that capture light and convert it into electricity, medical imaging, and communication technologies.
- ES.FCF4.EM.8. Evaluates questions about the advantages and disadvantages of the transmission and digital storage of information. Examples of advantages may include that digital information is stable because it can be stored, transferred and copied in a reliable, easy and rapid way in a computer. The disadvantages could be problems related to the deletion, security and theft of information.
- ES.FCF4.EM.9. Evaluates and supports or refutes the validity and reliability of the premises in publications about the effects of distant electromagnetic radiation frequencies when absorbed by matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.10. Analyzes mirror's and lenses' properties to design beam diagrams that will allow to calculate the location and size of images.
- ES.FCF4.EM.11. Searches for reliable sources of information on the scientific or everyday applications of mirrors and lenses, to make an oral presentation.

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCF4.IE.1. Analyzes wave behavior as a transference phenomenon of energy.
- ES.FCF4.IE.2. Describes energy transference in mechanic waves, such as sound waves.
- ES.FCF4.IE.3. Describes a model to represent the relationships between wave properties in different environments. Examples must include a model that represents interference and the principle of superposition.
- ES.FCF4.IE.4. Uses mathematical representations to support a premise regarding the relationship between frequencies, length of wave, speed of waves traveling through different environments. Examples of data may include electromagnetic radiation traveling through voids and glass, or seismic waves through Earth.
- ES.FCF4.IE.5. Identifies practical uses of waves, such as seismic data, acoustic effects and Doppler effect.
- ES.FCF4.IE.6. Plans research to demonstrate how waves produce fields that use or generate particles.

DOMAIN

Space systems

EXPECTATION ES.FCT1.

Earth's place in the universe - Planet Earth and the solar system; Universe and the stars; Energy in chemical processes and in everyday life; Electromagnetic radiation

INDICATOR

- ES.FCT1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCT1.IE.1. Uses mathematical or computational representations to predict the movement of orbital objects in the solar system. Emphasis is on Newton's universal gravitational

law that describes orbital movements, and that are applied to artificial satellites, as well as planets and moons.

- ES.FCT 1.IE.2. Describes and predicts natural phenomena as the movement of celestial bodies, relative movements and others, based on the laws that describe planetary and satellite movements.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.3. Describes the role of nuclear fusion in the Sun's nucleus that releases energy and that at the same time arrives to Earth in the form of radiation. Predicts the Sun's time period using other stars as information base. Emphasis is on energy transference mechanisms that allows nuclear fusion energy from the Sun's center to reach Earth. Examples of evidence for the description may include mass observation and life-span of other stars, as well as solar radiation changes due to sudden Sun flares (spatial climate), 11 yr. Sunspot cycle and the non-cyclical variations through-out the centuries.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.4. Explains the Big Bang theory based on astronomic evidence of light specters, movement in distant galaxies, and the mass composition of the universe. Evidence is on the astronomic evidence from redshift galaxies as indicator that the universe is actually expanding, background radiation microwaves are residues from the Big Bang's radiation, and the study of ordinary mass composition of the universe that is mainly found in stars and interstellar gases (from electromagnetic radiation star specter) that coincides with the predicted Big Bang theory (3/4 hydrogen and 1/4 helium).
- ES.FCT 1.IE.5. Communicates scientific ideas on the types of stars, their life-cycles, and the elements they produce. Emphasis is on nucleosynthesis and the different that create it, as well as the variations as mass function of the star and its life-span.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.6. Describes the condition under which the total mass and energy of the universe are conserved.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.FIT 1.

Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimize the design solution

INDICATOR

ES.FIT 1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.FIT 1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution to a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.FIT 1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution to a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability, and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.FIT 1.IT.3.

Uses available technological means to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life situations and optimize pre-existing models.

- ES.F.IT.1.IT.4. Explains the functioning and utility of designed models to solve everyday problems.
- ES.F.IT.1.IT.5. Identifies the limitations of developed designs for solutions that consider society's wishes and needs.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ES.Q. Chemistry

DOMAIN

Chemical reactions

EXPECTATION

ES.Q.CF1. Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties of matter; Chemical reactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Development of possible solutions to a scientific problem; Improve the design

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization level of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.1. Describes and explains the different atomic models that have been postulated and the different experiments that led to the discovery of subatomic particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.2. Uses models to explain the atom's structure and its relationship with matter's properties.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.3. Explains the meaning of isotope concept, applies knowledge to determine the average atomic mass of an element and argues on its applications, benefits and risks in different aspects of the real world.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.4. Develops models to represent the changes in the atom's nucleus composition and the energy released during fusion, fission, and radioactive disintegration processes. Examples of models must include mathematical representations.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.5. Reviews the fundamentals of the atom's mechanical-quantum model to write electronic configurations and electronic structure of symbols (Lewis Diagram).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.6. Discusses contributions realized by different scientists in the development of the Periodic Table as a method to order and classify elements based on their properties. Contributions from Dobereiner, John Newlands, Dimitri Mendeleev, Henry Mosely, among others, will be considered.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.7. Uses the periodic table as a model to determine the electronic configuration of elements and explains why elements of a same group have similar properties (periodic properties).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.8. Compares and contrasts the properties of metals, non-metals, metalloids and inert gases, and explains their uses and technological applications, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.9. Identifies and explains the properties that determine the location of an element in a period and a family on the Periodic Table, and uses them to predict the relative properties of other elements. Examples of these can be valence electrons and atomic number.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.10. Uses tendencies or patterns of the represented properties on the Periodic Table (atomic number, atomic mass, electronegativity, oxidation state and others) to

predict the elements' behavior and types of links that they form.

ES.Q.CF1.EM.11. Describes the processes by which substances are combined to form different chemical compositions and applies the naming convention of names and formulas of ionic and covalent compounds. The naming convention of positive and negative monoatomic and polyatomic ions are integrated based on their number of oxidation.

INDICATOR	ES.Q.CF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data on the properties of substances before and after interacting, to determine if a chemical reaction has happened. Examples of reactions may include burning sugar, wool-steel, and combining zinc or iron with hydrochloric acid.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.2.	Classifies chemical reactions and identifies the characteristics that distinguish them. (Combustion reactions, synthesis, etc).
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.3.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the total number of atoms does not change in a chemical reaction, and therefore mass is conserved. Emphasis is on Matter's Conservation Law and physical models and diagrams, including digital forms that represent atoms.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.4.	Designs a project to prove and modify a mechanism that releases or absorbs thermal energy in a chemical process. Emphasis is on the design, controlling the energy transference toward and from the environment, and the mechanism's modification using variables such as the type and concentration of a substance.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.5.	Creates a model that illustrates the absorption or release of energy in a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the idea that a chemical reaction is a system that produces changes of energy. Examples of models could include diagrams of reactions at a molecular level.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.6.	Applies principles and scientific evidence to provide an explanation about the effects of temperature changes or of particle concentration involved in the speed of a reaction. Emphasis is on the student's reasoning to focus on the number of particles and the energy of collision between molecules.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.7.	Evaluates the design of a chemical system specifying what change in the condition would produce an increase in the quantity of the product in equilibrium. Emphasis is on applying the Le Chatelier principle and on refining designs of chemical reaction systems, including descriptions of the connections between changes made at a macroscopic level, and what happens at a molecular level. Examples of design may include different ways of increasing the formation of a product when including the addition or extraction of reactives or products.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.8.	Uses mathematical representations to determine the stoichiometry of reactions and support the statement that atoms, and therefore, mass, are conserved during a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the use of

mathematical ideas to communicate the proportional relationships between atom's mass in reactives and products. Emphasis is also on the student's evaluation on the use of mathematical thinking and not on memorizing or memorized technique application to solve problems.

- ES.Q.CF1.IE.9. Analyzes the form in which energy is manifested and transformed from one form to another, for example, from chemical to thermal energy and from light to electric.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.10. Describes the temperature and heat flow in terms of random movement and atom and molecule vibrations.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.11. Explains how the transformation of energy is produced and vice versa during a nuclear reaction when applying the equation $\Delta E = \Delta mc^2$.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.12. Evaluates the process that occurs during a chemical reaction in terms of chemical energy transformation. Examples include necessary activation energy, absorption, and energy release during the reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.13. Explains that absorbed or released heat in a chemical reaction comes from the total energy involved in the process of forming and breaking links.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.14. Calculates the quantity of absorbed or released heat by a substance or by a chemical reaction when temperature changes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.15. Explains the difference between the concepts of enthalpy, entropy, and free energy, and how these determine the spontaneity of chemical reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.16. Uses Hess's law to determine the change in enthalpy of a chemical reaction.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.17. Explains the acid-base reactions and their application in chemical or biological processes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.18. Explains the relationship between the structure of molecules, chemical links and chemical energy.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.19. Evaluates new energetic options such as hydrogen, ethanol, carbon, waste incineration and others, with their economic and environmental implications.

DOMAIN

Structure and properties of matter

EXPECTATION ES.Q.CF1.

Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Nuclear processes; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Definitions of energy

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.12. Discriminates between extensive and intensive physical properties of matter and analyzes varied examples of situations where the material's property is fundamental for diverse uses. Examples include density, ductility, conductivity, etc.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.13. Communicates scientific and technical information on why the structure at a molecular level is important for the functioning of the design of materials. Examples may

include why materials that conduct electricity are usually made of metal, that long-lasting flexible materials are made of linked molecules, and that pharmaceutical products are designed to interact with specific receptors.

- ES.Q.CF1.EM.14. Analyzes the kinetic-molecular theory to describe and explain the physical properties of matter's states through a model.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.15. Relates the thermal energy content of a material with the movement of particles that compose it according to the kinetic-molecular theory.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.16. Explains the temperature concepts in terms of average kinetic energy content of particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.17. Describes and compares the crystalline structure and properties of different types of solids.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.18. Relates the properties of liquids (viscosity, superficial tension, capillary action and others) with intermolecular forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.19. Develops a model to predict and describe the changes in particle movement, temperature and state of a substance when there is energy change (addition or subtraction). Emphasis is on molecular quantitative models of solids, liquids and gases to demonstrate that changes in thermal energy affect the particles' kinetic energy until a change of state occurs. Example of a model is phase diagram of water and CO₂.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.20. Collects information on the attraction forces between molecules to compare the structure of different substances and infer on the intensity of forces between particles. Examples of forces are dispersion and dipole forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.21. Describes matter's classification system based on its characteristic properties (homogeneous and heterogeneous materials, substances, mixtures, solutions, etc) and applies them to explain its behavior.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.22. Designs and practices a procedure that applies adequate methods to separate mixtures and identifies substances present within, considering their properties. Offers examples of utility and application of these processes in the real world (filtration, chromatography, etc).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.23. Analyzes the properties of solutions based on the properties of their components. Examples include solute and dissolvent, types of solutions (liquid-solid, liquid-gas, etc), solution concentration (diluted, saturated, oversaturated), factors that affect solubility, solubility curves, colligative properties, solvation (dissolution) process and forces between solute and dissolvent.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.24. Analyzes the oxidation and reduction reactions to explain how they manifest in natural processes and identifies their applications in industry.

INDICATOR

ES.Q.CF1.CC. Conservation and change

ES.Q.CF1.CC.1. Analyzes the process by which chemical reactions reach

an equilibrium.

- ES.Q.CF1.CC.2. Analyzes and interprets data that shows that total mass and energy in the universe are always conserved.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.3. Evaluates Matter's Conservation Law to describe the changes that exist in a chemical reaction and establishes that in a chemical reaction the type and quantity of atoms are conserved even-though their combination form is changed. Emphasis is on the writing of chemical equations and the balance of these.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.4. Analyzes and interprets data to apply the mole concept in the calculation of empiric and molecular formulas, stoichiometric relationships and to express the concentration of a solution (molarity).
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.5. Identifies stoichiometric relationships in a chemical reaction and calculates the theoretical yield and the actual yield in balanced chemical equations. (Percent Yield)
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.6. Applies the gas laws to explain the relationship and effects of changes in pressure, temperature and volume in situations like building aerostats, climate changes and scuba-diving tanks, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.7. Collects evidence to explain how human activities interfere in climate changes, global warming and increased greenhouse effect gases, and proposes alternatives to minimize the effects, both locally and worldwide.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.Q.IT1.

Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Improves the design

INDICATOR

ES.Q.IT1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.Q.IT1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution for a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.3.

Uses technological means within reach to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life problems and optimize the utility of existing models.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.4.

Explains the functioning and use of models designed to solve everyday life problems.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.5.

Identifies the limitations of engineering designs to review the system and make decisions as to their use.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ESA.

Environmental Sciences

DOMAIN

History of Earth

EXPECTATION	ESA.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Earth's history; Tectonic plates and interaction systems on a large scale; Nuclear processes
INDICATOR	ESA.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT1.CC.1.	Evaluates evidence on the movement of continental and oceanic crusts in the past and in the present, as well as, the Theory of Tectonic Plates to explain the age of the crust's rocks. Emphasis is on the evidence that tectonic plates present to explain the age of rocks on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.2.	Describes the structure and changes that occur on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.3.	Explains the current geography of the island of Puerto Rico examining its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.4.	Analyzes geological phenomena based on the Theory of Tectonic Plates.
	ESA.CT1.CC.5.	Explains the geological evolution of Puerto Rico, identifying the tectonic plates around the island that have contributed to its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.6.	Identifies and describes the properties and formation of different minerals, and their location in Puerto Rico.
	ESA.CT1.CC.7.	Reviews obtained evidence from old materials from planet Earth, meteorites, and planetary surfaces, and uses it to build an explanation of the history and formation of Earth. Emphasis is on the use of available evidence within the solar system for reconstructing planet Earth's history. Examples of evidence include the age of materials (obtained by radiometric data of meteorites, lunar rocks, and the most antique minerals on Earth), the size and composition of objects in the solar system and the impact records of craters on Earth's surface.
	ESA.CT1.CC.8.	Explains the historical development of environmental education and Science progress in this area to maintain and /or recover planet Earth's wellbeing. Examples of values in environmental science may include a discussion of careers in environmental sciences and their implications in society.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	ESA.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth and the solar system; Tectonic plates and interaction systems at a large scale; Earth's materials and systems; Biogeology; Water's role in the processes of Earth's surface; Weather and climate
INDICATOR	ESA.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ESA.CT2.EM.1.	Describes water's properties and their effects of Earth's materials and processes of the surface. Emphasis is on chemical and mechanical investigations with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between hydrological cycles and interaction systems known commonly as the rock cycle. Examples of research may include: transport and deposit of rivers using flow diagrams and erosion using a content variety

on soil moisture. Examples of chemical research include weathering, erosion and re-crystallization or fusion generation (when examining how water decreases the fusion temperature of most solids).

- ESA.CT2.EM.2. Explains the importance of water for organisms and the need to protect this resource.
- ESA.CT2.EM.3. Builds an argument based on evidence of the co-evolution of Earth's systems and life on Earth. Emphasis is on the cause, effects and reaction of the dynamics between the biosphere and other Earth systems by which geo-science factors control the evolution of life, that at the same time continuously alters Earth's surface. Examples include how photosynthetic life alters the atmosphere by means of oxygen production, which at the same time increases the wear index and permits the evolution of animal life; or how evolution of coral reefs alter the erosion patterns and deposition of the coastlines and provide a habitat for the evolution of new life forms.
- ESA.CT2.EM.4. Collects evidence on the geological origin, location, and importance of Puerto Rico's natural resources and compares that evidence with that of other major Antilles islands. Examples of natural resources may include minerals, elements, forests and other non-renewable and renewable resources.
- ESA.CT2.EM.5. Identifies the characteristics of the natural environment of a tropical region to establish a contrast with the natural environments of other regions of the world.
- ESA.CT2.EM.6. Classifies and describes the characteristics, location and importance of Puerto Rico's forests. Compares other forests on Earth with tropical forests.
- INDICATOR ESA.CT2.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CT2.IE.1. Describes how internal and superficial Earth processes operate at different scales to conform the characteristics of continental and oceanic floors. Emphasis is on how the appearance of the characteristics of terrestrial surfaces (mountains, valleys, plains) and characteristics of oceanic floors (pits, ridges and oceanic mountains) are the result of both constructive forces (vulcanism, tectonic elevations, orogeny) and destructive forces (weathering, sedimentation mass and coastline erosion).
- ESA.CT2.IE.2. Analyzes geosciences data to affirm that a change on Earth's surface can generate a reaction that causes changes in other terrestrial systems. Examples must include the reactions that occur and affect climate, such as the result of greenhouse gases that cause the increase in temperatures that melt glacial ice, which reduces the quantity of solar rays that reflect on Earth's surface that cause an increase in surface temperature and further reduces the quantity of ice. Also, the loss of vegetation causes an increase in soil erosion; and damming rivers increases the recharge of subterraneous water, decreases sediment transport and increases coastline erosion.

- ESA.CT2.IE.3. Identifies human activities that intervene with the effect of global climate changes, analyzes diverse alternatives that permit minimizing this and evaluates the levels of local and international efforts to counteract the increase of greenhouse effect gases in the atmosphere.
- ESA.CT2.IE.4. Explains the relationship between energy and frequency of natural phenomena.
- ESA.CT2.IE.5. Examines why earthquakes happen and how their intensity is measured.
- ESA.CT2.IE.6. Develops a model of Earth's interior to describe the cycles of matter by thermal convection. Emphasis is on both the unidimensional model of Earth (with radial rays determined by density) and the tridimensional model which is controlled by convection of Earth's crust and tectonic plates.
- ESA.CT2.IE.7. Uses a model to describe how the flow variation of energy in and out of Earth's systems, results in climate changes. Examples include the evaluation of results in climate changes that are limited to temperature changes on the surface, precipitation patterns, volume of glacial ice, sea level, and biosphere distribution. Include the relationship between matter's cycles and energy flow, in the light of the Matter and Energy Conservation Law.
- ESA.CT2.IE.8. Obtains evidence that heat is absorbed or released in an ecosystem to compare the effect in the diverse ecosystems of Puerto Rico. Examples may include coastlines, urban areas, forests, mountains.
- ESA.CT2.IE.9. Recognizes that the major cause of climatological events on planet Earth is related to the interaction of solar energy with Earth, atmosphere and seas.
- ESA.CT2.IE.10. Plans and conducts research on water's properties and their effects on Earth's materials and surface processes. Emphasis is on the chemical and mechanical research with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between the hydrologic cycle and interaction systems, also known as the rock cycle.
- ESA.CT2.IE.11. Discusses the importance of aquatic ecosystems for the water dependent species and proposes alternatives for their conservation.
- ESA.CT2.IE.12. Describes the importance of hydrologic sciences.
- ESA.CT2.IE.13. Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon between the hydrosphere and atmosphere. Emphasis is on modeling biogeochemical cycles that include the carbon cycle by the ocean, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) when providing the base for living organisms.
- ESA.CT2.IE.14. Uses models and diagrams to explain the patterns of oceanic currents and winds that affect Puerto Rico and all the Caribbean.

DOMAIN

Human sustainability

EXPECTATION ESA.CT3.

Earth and human activity - Global climate change; natural resources; Weather and climate; Natural

		disasters; Human impact on Earth's systems; development of possible solutions
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ESA.CT3.IE.1.	Identifies how the historic origin of cities and human communities have affected populations in urban and rural zones.
	ESA.CT3.IE.2.	Evaluates the effect of human beings on communities and the capacity of planet Earth to support populations. Emphasis should include the capacity of having sufficient natural resources to satisfy the basic needs such as water, food and shelter.
	ESA.CT3.IE.3.	Describes the value of ecosystems and argues on the importance of their conservation and protection, and conservation and protection of their organisms, including specificity of the ecosystems and organisms of Puerto Rico. Emphasis must be on native organisms of Puerto Rico. Gives examples of organisms that are in salt-water, fresh-water, mangrove, beach, rocky-coast, coral reef ecosystems.
	ESA.CT3.IE.4.	Describes the use of common energy sources such as: fossil fuels, nuclear energy and alternate sources such as: wind, solar, ethanol and hydraulic.
	ESA.CT3.IE.5.	Explains the advantages and disadvantages, including economic impact, of the uses of energy that provide available resources and possible energy alternatives, analyzing the impact of fossil resource exploitation of the environment.
	ESA.CT3.IE.6.	Evaluates documents and announcements on the laws and government propositions on environmental conservation. Examples of laws or propositions would be on the protection of certain species and application of regulations on car emissions.
	ESA.CT3.IE.7.	Describes change patterns and action measures that would protect them in case of natural phenomena, such as earthquakes and hurricanes, according to the different geographic zones in Puerto Rico. Examples of natural phenomena may include hurricanes, earthquakes, tsunamis and storms.
	ESA.CT3.IE.8.	Identifies the effects of hurricanes depending on the geological zone of Puerto Rico.
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT3.CC.1.	Describes, based on scientific evidence, how the availability of natural resources, natural disasters, and climate changes have influenced human activities. Examples of key natural resources include the access to safe water (as rivers, lakes and subterraneous waters), fertile soil regions as deltas, high mineral concentrations and fossil fuels. Examples of natural disasters could be internal processes (as volcanic eruptions or earthquakes), surface processes (as tsunamis, mass wasting and floor erosion), and severe climate (as hurricanes, floods and droughts). Examples of the results in climate changes that can affect the population or drive

them to massive migrations include changes in sea levels, regional temperature patterns and precipitation, and the types of crop that can be grown.

- ESA.CT3.CC.2. Illustrates using technology, the relationships between the management of natural resources, sustainability of human population and biodiversity. Examples of factors that affect the management of natural resources include the cost of resource's extractions, waste management, per capita consumption and development of new technologies. Examples of factors that affect human sustainability include the agricultural efficiency, levels of conservation and urban planning.
- ESA.CT3.CC.3. Analyzes data from geosciences and the results of global climate models to make predictions based on evidence of current and future changes of regional and global climate, and associates future impacts to Earth's systems. Examples of evidence for data and results of climate models are the climate changes (as precipitation and temperature) and the impacts associated to them (as sea levels, volume of glacial ice, or the atmosphere's and ocean's composition).
- ESA.CT3.CC.4. Uses representations to illustrate the relationships between Earth systems and how these relationships are modified by human activity. Examples of the Earth systems that are found in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, lithosphere and biosphere. An example of the extent of the impact of human activities is the increase of carbon monoxide in the atmosphere leads to an increase of photosynthetic biomass on Earth and an increase of the ocean's acidification, that affect the health of marine organisms and marine population.
- ESA.CT3.CC.5. Evaluates design solutions that are competing to develop, manage and use energy and mineral resources based on cost-benefit indicators. Emphasis is on the conservation, recycling, re-using of resources (as minerals and metals) where possible and minimizing the impacts where not possible. Examples include developing better processes and skills for the use of agricultural soils, mining (for carbon, tar sands, bituminous shale) and pumping (oil and natural gas).
- ESA.CT3.CC.6. Evaluates and proposes a technological solution that reduces human activity impact in natural systems. Examples of impact data on human activities may include the quantities and types of pollutants that are emitted, changes in biomass and diversity of species, change in the surface of land for human use (as the development of urban areas, agriculture and livestock or mining). Examples of limitations for future impacts may vary from local efforts (as reducing, reusing and recycling resources) to large scale efforts, as geo-engineering design solutions (as the alteration of global temperatures by means of great changes in the atmosphere and ocean).
- ESA.CT3.CC.7. Evaluates environmental laws that affect the geography

and topography of Puerto Rico, and proposes solutions to eliminate or reduce the effects of various environmental problems in Puerto Rico. Examples may include deforestation, the use of minerals and fossil resources, and the impacts of agriculture.

- ESA.CT3.CC.8. Proposes solutions considering the scientific and economic development of Puerto Rico, in relation to the wellbeing of the natural environment. Examples may include pollution caused by solid waste, biomedical waste, air and water pollution, and conservation of non-renewable resources.
- ESA.CT3.CC.9. Proposes alternatives that help preserve our ecosystems for future generations, ensuring they include economic development and sustainability.
- ESA.CT3.CC.10. Analyzes patterns in changes that are produced in nature, and discusses effective ways to use science knowledge and the scientific method to diminish the change's effects. Examples of patterns may include data on air pollution, atmospheric phenomena, and changes in the population of various species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.11. Develops solutions to solve problems related with the conservation of exotic species, endangered species, and the extinction of other species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.12. Thinks about and implements a recycling and reusing plan of school and community materials.
- ESA.CT3.CC.13. Builds a model that shows how equilibrium in environmental systems is affected if altered beyond its tolerance capacity.

DOMAIN

Matter and energy in organisms and ecosystems

EXPECTATION ESA.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: Structure and processes - Flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycle and energy transference in ecosystems; Energy in chemical processes; Weather and climate

INDICATOR

- ESA.CB1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CB1.IE.8. Represents and describes the carbon cycle in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on illustrating the biogeochemical cycles. The carbon cycle must be included in oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings).
- ESA.CB1.IE.9. Describes the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration in carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples could be models or include simulations or graphic organizers.
- ESA.CB1.IE.10. Explains the importance of the processes that occur in the cycles: hydrological, carbon and nitrogen with the use of diagrams and models, and justifies the reasons why they are vital for living organisms.
- ESA.CB1.IE.11. Reviews evidence to support the fact that entropy is the main factor of energy loss available in food through the trophic levels.
- ESA.CB1.IE.12. Analyzes the role producers, consumers and

decomposers play in the chain and food web of an ecosystem, establishes connections and explains that the food chain or trophic is an example of the survival interrelationship between species. Includes representing food interdependence through the use of diagrams.

ES.A.CB1.IE.13. Represents the food interdependence with diagrams that illustrate chains and trophic webs, and establishes interdependent relationships between the elements of an ecosystem, between ecosystems themselves, and ecosystems and the planet.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.A.IT.1.

Design for engineering- Defines and delimits engineering problems; develops possible solutions; Improves a design

INDICATOR ES.A.IT.1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.A.IT.1.IT.1.

Analyzes a major global challenge impact to specify the limitations and quantitative specifications of the solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.2.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and more manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.3.

Proposes effective forms to raise awareness and promote possible solutions for environmental problems such as air, soil, and water pollution, waste management, species and resource protection, and also sustainable development.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.9.

Identifies innovative projects that permit development in a sustainable way.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.10.

Explains, with examples, how technology impacts life quality from an economic, social and environmental point of view.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.11.

Analyzes situations and takes individual and group decisions in the light of environmental problems.

CONTENT STANDARD

PR.ES.B.

Biology

DOMAIN

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Structure and function; flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycles and energy transference in ecosystems; Organism's development and growth

INDICATOR ES.B.CB1.EM.

Structure and organization levels of matter

ES.B.CB1.EM.1.

Uses models of cell types to establish differences between the organelles and their functions, including the nucleus, that contains the genetic material that determines heredity.

ES.B.CB1.EM.2.

Analyzes the structure of DNA and RNA molecules and their replication by means of tridimensional models.

ES.B.CB1.EM.3.

Explains, using scientific evidence, how DNA's structure

		determines the structure of proteins that perform the essential functions of life thru specialized cell systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.4.	Uses a model to illustrate the rank organization and interaction of systems that realize specific functions within multicellular organisms. Includes the human body systems such as: digestive, circulatory and immunological, skeletal, muscular, nervous, excretory, reproductive, integumentary and endocrinological systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.5.	Plans and realizes a research to provide evidence that the reaction mechanisms keep homeostasis. Examples of research may include the average of heartbeats in reaction to exercise, the reaction of stomas to humidity and temperature, a root's development in reaction to water levels.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.6.	Represents with concept maps or graph organizers, the relationship between the processes that occur in the mitochondria of cells during cellular respiration.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.7.	Builds diagrams and models to represent the changes that occur during the cellular division phases and cellular differentiation, when producing and keeping complex organisms.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB1.IE.1.	Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on making models of biogeochemical cycles that include carbon cycles in the oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) providing the base for living organisms.
	ES B.CB1.IE.2.	Builds and revises an explanation based on evidence on how carbon, hydrogen and oxygen of sugar molecules can combine with other elements to form amino-acids and other carbon molecules. Emphasis is on the use of models and simulations that support this explanation.
	ES B.CB1.IE.3.	Develops a model that illustrates that cellular respiration is a chemical process by which food molecule links and oxygen molecules break-up and form new links, resulting in a net energy transference. Emphasis is on conceptual understanding of entry and exit processes during cellular respiration.
	ES B.CB1.IE.4.	Uses models to illustrate how photosynthesis and respiration transform light energy into stored chemical energy. Emphasis is on the illustration of entry and exit of matter and the transference and transformation of energy in photosynthesis by plants and other photosynthetic organisms. Examples of models can include diagrams, chemical equations and conceptual models.
	ES B.CB1.IE.5.	Collects information about macromolecules (proteins, lipids, carbon hydrates, nucleic acids) that compose a cell and uses it to explain that spatial atom distribution in these determine some of their functions in living organisms.

	ES B.CB1.IE.6.	Explains thru models, the function and structure of cellular membrane in relation to particle movement in biotic and abiotic systems such as: diffusion and osmosis.
	ES B.CB1.IE.7.	Collects evidence to explain that the protein synthesis process is essential in the enzyme production that regulates all the processes that the cell realizes.
DOMAIN		Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics
EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB2.	Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics - Interdependent relationships in ecosystems; Dynamics, functioning and resistance of ecosystems; Cyclical movement of matter and energy transference in ecosystems; Social interactions and group behavior; Human beings and biodiversity; Development of a possible solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB2.EM.1.	Uses mathematical or technological representations to support explanations about the factors that affect the carrying capacity of ecosystems at different scales. Emphasis is on the quantitative analysis and relationship comparison between interdependent factors including limits, resources, climate and competition. Examples of mathematical comparisons may include graphs, tables, histograms, and population changes collected from simulations and historical data.
	ES.B.CB2.EM.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support and revise the explanations based on evidence about the factors that affect biodiversity and populations in ecosystems ant different scales. Examples of mathematical representations include finding an average, determine trends or patterns, and use comparative graphs of a variety of data.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB2.IE.1.	Builds and revises an explanation, based on evidence, about the cycles of matter and energy flow in aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of aerobic and anaerobic respiration in different environments.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support statements on matter's cycles and energy flow between organisms of an ecosystem. Emphasis is on the use of mathematical models of energy storage in biomass, to describe the flow transference of energy thru ecosystems. Emphasis is on atoms and molecules (such as carbon, oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) that are kept as they pass thru an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.3.	Develops models to illustrate the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples of models could include simulations and mathematical models. The evaluation does not include the specific chemical steps of photosynthesis and respiration.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.4.	Evaluates statements, evidence and reasoning that

complex interactions of ecosystems keep the number and type of organisms in a relatively consistent way in stable conditions. But changes in the conditions may result in a new ecosystem. Examples of changes in the conditions of an ecosystem may include small changes, either physical or biological such as temporary hunting or flooding; or extreme changes as volcanic eruptions and increase in sea levels.

INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB2.CC.1.	Identifies environmental factors to discuss the negative and positive effects of population growth.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.2.	Builds a model that represents and explains the step sequence of ecological succession states in an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.3.	Explains the relationship between populations, communities and ecosystems of the biosphere.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.4.	Designs, evaluates and refines a solution to reduce the impact of human activities in the environment and biodiversity. Examples of the activities may include urbanization, dam construction, dissemination of invading species.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.5.	Evaluates scientific evidence of group behavior of individuals and the opportunity they have to survive and reproduce. Emphasis is on : (1) distinguishing between group and individual behavior, (2) identifying evidence that supports the results of group behavior and (3) developing logical and reasonable arguments based on evidence. Examples of group behavior may include flocks, herds and cooperative behaviors such as hunting, migrations and swarms.

DOMAIN

Heredity and characteristic variations

EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB3.	Heredity and characteristic variations - Structure and function; Characteristic heredity; Characteristic variations
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB3.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB3.EM.1.	Poses questions to clarify the relationship of DNA's role and chromosomes in the instruction codes for the characteristic variations that pass from one generation to another.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB3.CC.1.	Poses and defends a statement based on evidence about the genetic and hereditary variations that can result from: (1) new genetic combination thru the meiosis process, (2) viable errors that may occur during DNA replication and/or (3) mutations caused by environmental factors. Emphasis is on the use of data to support arguments on the different forms in which mutations can occur.
	ES.B.CB3.CC.2.	Applies statistical and probability concepts to explain the variation and distribution of visible characteristics in a population. Emphasis is on the use of mathematics to describe the probability and characteristic presence that are related to genetics and environmental factors., as

well as representing phenotypic and genotypic proportions in different genetic crossings.

ES.B.CB3.CC.3. Recognizes and explains that multicellular organisms are developed from a simple zygote and that the resulting phenotype will depend on the genotype that was established at the moment of fertilization.

ES.B.CB3.CC.4. Explains the importance of life's continuity thru the action of genes, hereditary patterns, organism reproduction and cell reproduction.

DOMAIN

Natural selection and evolution

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB4.

Biological evolution: Unity and diversity - Evidence of common ancestors and diversity; Adaptation; Natural selection; Biodiversity and human beings; Development of a possible solution

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

ES.B.CB4.EM.1.

Communicates scientific information that biological evolution and common ancestors are supported by multiple lines of empiric evidence. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of each evidence line has and biological in relation to the common ancestor evidence and biological evolution. Examples of evidence may include similarities in the DNA sequences, anatomic structures and development appearance order of embryological structures.

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.B.CB4.IE.1.

Builds an explanation based on evidence that the evolution process mainly results from four factors: (1) a species potential to increase in quantity, (2) the genetic variation of individuals in a species by mutation or sexual reproduction, (3) the competition for limited resources that each individual needs to survive and reproduce in the environment, and (4) ensure the proliferation of those organisms that are more able to survive and reproduce in the environment. Emphasis is on the use of evidence to explain the influence that the four factors have on the number of organisms, behaviors, morphology, or physiology, in terms of the ability to compete for limited resources and subsequently, in the individual survival and adaptation of species. Examples of evidence may include mathematical models as a simple distribution graph and proportional reasoning.

ES.B.CB4.IE.2.

Determines the effects of the different types of natural selection in the gene set (gene pool) of an organism.

ES.B.CB4.IE.3.

Applies statistical and probability concepts to support explanations about organisms with advantageous hereditary characteristics that tend to increase in proportion comparing to those that don't have the same characteristics. Emphasis is on the change analysis in the numerical distribution of the characteristics and on using these changes as evidence to support explanation on how natural selection determines the survival capacity for groups of organisms.

ES.B.CB4.IE.4.

Builds an explanation based on evidence on how natural

		selection leads to the adaptation of populations. Emphasis is on using data to provide evidence on how biotic and abiotic differences in ecosystems (seasonal temperature changes, long period climate changes, light, acidity, geographic barriers, or evolution of other organisms) contribute to gene changes throughout time, leading to adaptation of the population. Hardy Weinberg's principle is integrated to quantify the process of natural selection in a population.
	ES.B.CB4.IE.5.	Evaluates the role of natural selection in the development of the Theory of Evolution.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB4.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB4.CC.1.	Evaluates the evidence that supports the statements that changes in the environmental conditions may result in: (1) increase in the number of individuals of a species, (2) emergence of new species, (3) extinction of other species. Emphasis is on determining the cause-effect relationships on how environmental changes, such as deforestation, fishing, use of fertilizers, drought, flooding and rate of environmental changes, affect the distribution or disappearance of species' characteristics.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.2.	Reviews and evaluates a simulation to test a solution that decreases the adverse impacts of human activities in biodiversity. Emphasis is on the design of solutions for a proposed problem that is related to a threatened species or in danger of extinction; or with genetic variation of multiple species organisms.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.3.	Analyzes how human beings have the responsibility to keep the environment in good condition for the survival of species.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	ES.B.IT1.	Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Optimizes the design solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.IT1.IT.	Design for Engineering
	ES.B.IT1.IT.1.	Analyzes a major global challenge to specify the limitations and quantitative criteria of solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.2.	Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be resolved using engineering knowledge.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.3.	Evaluates a real and complex problem solution based on criteria as costs, benefits, security, trustworthiness, and aesthetics considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.4.	Uses a computer simulation to model the impact of proposed solutions to solve a real and complex problem with multiple criteria and limitations within and between the relevant systems to the problem.
CONTENT	PR.ES.F.	Physics

STANDARD

DOMAIN

Forces and interactions

EXPECTATION ES.FCF2.

Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems

INDICATOR ES.FCF2.EM.

Structure and organization levels of matter

ES.FCF2.EM.1.

Explains what fluids are and describes how these create pressure on a surface. (surface tension)

ES.FCF2.EM.2.

Explains and describes how the surface tension principles and types of fluids affect mechanization. Emphasis is on applying the kinetic-molecular theory.

INDICATOR ES.FCF2.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.FCF2.IE.1.

Designs a model to explain the movement of a dimension through verbal, graphic and mathematic descriptions. Emphasis is on the movement's description through the concepts of: distance, displacement, speed, velocity and acceleration. The use of the units from the International Measurement System must be integrated, and also their conversions, significant digits, scientific notation and mathematical equations.

ES.FCF2.IE.2.

Identifies and describes the four fundamental forces in everyday life: strong nuclear interaction, weak nuclear interaction, gravity and electromagnetism.

ES.FCF2.IE.3.

Uses knowledge on the different movement laws to apply them in problem solutions of everyday life. Emphasis is on the Newton, Coulomb and Kepler laws.

ES.FCF2.IE.4.

Uses Newton's second law of motion when describing the mathematical relationship between net force on a macroscopic object, its mass and acceleration. Data examples may include tables or position or velocity graphs as time function for objects subject to a non-balanced net force, such as an object in free-fall, and object rolling on a ramp or an object in movement pulled by a constant force.

ES.FCF2.IE.5.

Uses mathematical representations of Newton's gravitational law and Coulomb's law, to describe and predict gravitational and electrostatic forces between objects.

ES.FCF2.IE.6.

Explains the functioning of machines, using force and movement concepts that are useful or resolve an everyday-life problem.

ES.FCF2.IE.7.

Uses mathematical representations to describe movement in two dimensions and the force equilibrium with vectors. Represents and calculates the magnitude and direction of vector quantities by graph and mathematical methods applying the basic trigonometrical functions. Projectile motion and inclined plane are included.

ES.FCF2.IE.8.

Designs an experiment to explain the principles and applications of uniform circular movement and simple harmonic movement.

	ES.FCF2.IE.9.	Applies scientific and engineering ideas to design and evaluate an apparatus that minimizes the force on a macroscopic object during collision. The examples may include a helmet or parachute.
	ES.FCF2.IE.10.	Explains the concepts of electrical charge, electric current, electric potential, electric field, and magnetic field, and establishes the difference between contact forces and long-range forces. Explains the properties of conductive materials and designs electrical circuits in series and in parallel.
	ES.FCF2.IE.11.	Offers experimental evidence that an electric current may produce a magnetic field and a magnetic field may produce an electric current.
	ES.FCF2.IE.12.	Describes apparatus that resolve everyday-life problems and those which result from the application of physics. Examples of force may be: electrical, magnetic, gravitational and nuclear forces. Examples of apparatus may include those that use conductors, circuits and fields.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.FCF2.CC.1.	Uses mathematical representations to support the premise that the total momentum of a system of objects is preserved when the net force on the system is zero.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	ES.FCF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Energy in chemical processes in everyday-life.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ES.FCF3.EM.1.	Explains energy in terms of scale, from atomic scale to macroscopic scale.
	ES.FCF3.EM.2.	Classifies energy as kinetic or potential and contrasts the different types: thermal, chemical, nuclear, electromagnetic and mechanical. Calculates the kinetic and potential energy changes in a system.
	ES.FCF3.EM.3.	Classifies and explains the origin of different sources of energy: fossil-fuels, solar, geothermic, wind, hydraulic, biomass, among others.
	ES.FCF3.EM.4.	Explains the relationship between energy, work, and power.
	ES.FCF3.EM.5.	Explains the work-energy theorem.
	ES.FCF3.EM.6.	Identifies the electrical phenomena as a manifestation of the charges of subatomic particles (electrons).
	ES.FCF3.EM.7.	Compares electric and magnetic forces regarding the field and its relationship with charges in movement.
	ES.FCF3.EM.8.	Explains the relationships between electrostatic charges using Coulomb's laws.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.FCF3.IE.1.	Calculates the energy change between the components of a system when the energy of one of them is known and the energy flow into or out-of the systems.

- ES.FCF3.IE.2. Designs a model that illustrates that energy at a macroscopic scale may be understood as a combination of energy associated to particle movements (objects) and energy associated to the relative position of particles (objects). Examples of macroscopic scale phenomena may include the conversion of kinetic energy to thermal energy, stored energy in an object positioned over Earth, and stored energy between two electrically charged plates.
- ES.FCF3.IE.3. Designs and refines an apparatus that works within controlled limitations to convert energy from one form into another. Examples of apparatus may include Rube Goldberg, wind turbines, solar cells, solar ovens and generators. Examples of limitations may include the use of renewable energy forms and efficiency.
- ES.FCF3.IE.4. Explains that when two components are combined at different temperatures in an enclosed system, the total transference of thermal energy results in a more uniform energy distribution between the system's components (thermodynamics' second law). Examples of research may include mixing liquids with different initial temperatures or adding different temperature objects to water.
- ES.FCF3.IE.5. Explains the interactions through electrical or magnetic fields to illustrate the forces between objects and energy changes of objects from interaction.
- ES.FCF3.IE.6. Plans and realizes research to propose the use of different energy sources in Puerto Rico, taking into consideration the cost-benefit and cost-effective proportion.

DOMAIN

Waves and their applications

EXPECTATION ES.FCF4.

Waves and their applications to technological development - Wave's properties; Electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.FCF4.EM.1. Explains, through models, the effect of wave's properties in the behavior of matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.2. Distinguishes between the types of mechanical waves: transverse and longitudinal.
- ES.FCF4.EM.3. Explains the idea that electromagnetic radiation can be described with a wave model or particle model, and that in some cases, one of the models is more useful than the other. Examples include how wave and particle models explain the properties of visible light.
- ES.FCF4.EM.4. Explains reflection, refraction, diffraction, polarization, transformation and absorption as manifestations of the interactions between waves and matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.5. Proposes the development of technology that demonstrates the application of light properties in the design of useful prototypes or to resolve a daily-life problem.
- ES.FCF4.EM.6. Explains and describes how wave principles are used to

create useful technologies for humans.

- ES.FCF4.EM.7. Communicates technical information on how some technological apparatus use behavioral principles and interactions of waves with matter to transmit and capture information and energy. Examples may include solar cells that capture light and convert it into electricity, medical imaging, and communication technologies.
- ES.FCF4.EM.8. Evaluates questions about the advantages and disadvantages of the transmission and digital storage of information. Examples of advantages may include that digital information is stable because it can be stored, transferred and copied in a reliable, easy and rapid way in a computer. The disadvantages could be problems related to the deletion, security and theft of information.
- ES.FCF4.EM.9. Evaluates and supports or refutes the validity and reliability of the premises in publications about the effects of distant electromagnetic radiation frequencies when absorbed by matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.10. Analyzes mirror's and lenses' properties to design beam diagrams that will allow to calculate the location and size of images.
- ES.FCF4.EM.11. Searches for reliable sources of information on the scientific or everyday applications of mirrors and lenses, to make an oral presentation.

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCF4.IE.1. Analyzes wave behavior as a transference phenomenon of energy.
- ES.FCF4.IE.2. Describes energy transference in mechanic waves, such as sound waves.
- ES.FCF4.IE.3. Describes a model to represent the relationships between wave properties in different environments. Examples must include a model that represents interference and the principle of superposition.
- ES.FCF4.IE.4. Uses mathematical representations to support a premise regarding the relationship between frequencies, length of wave, speed of waves traveling through different environments. Examples of data may include electromagnetic radiation traveling through voids and glass, or seismic waves through Earth.
- ES.FCF4.IE.5. Identifies practical uses of waves, such as seismic data, acoustic effects and Doppler effect.
- ES.FCF4.IE.6. Plans research to demonstrate how waves produce fields that use or generate particles.

DOMAIN

Space systems

EXPECTATION ES.FCT1.

Earth's place in the universe - Planet Earth and the solar system; Universe and the stars; Energy in chemical processes and in everyday life; Electromagnetic radiation

INDICATOR

- ES.FCT1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCT1.IE.1. Uses mathematical or computational representations to predict the movement of orbital objects in the solar system. Emphasis is on Newton's universal gravitational

law that describes orbital movements, and that are applied to artificial satellites, as well as planets and moons.

- ES.FCT 1.IE.2. Describes and predicts natural phenomena as the movement of celestial bodies, relative movements and others, based on the laws that describe planetary and satellite movements.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.3. Describes the role of nuclear fusion in the Sun's nucleus that releases energy and that at the same time arrives to Earth in the form of radiation. Predicts the Sun's time period using other stars as information base. Emphasis is on energy transference mechanisms that allows nuclear fusion energy from the Sun's center to reach Earth. Examples of evidence for the description may include mass observation and life-span of other stars, as well as solar radiation changes due to sudden Sun flares (spatial climate), 11 yr. Sunspot cycle and the non-cyclical variations through-out the centuries.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.4. Explains the Big Bang theory based on astronomic evidence of light specters, movement in distant galaxies, and the mass composition of the universe. Evidence is on the astronomic evidence from redshift galaxies as indicator that the universe is actually expanding, background radiation microwaves are residues from the Big Bang's radiation, and the study of ordinary mass composition of the universe that is mainly found in stars and interstellar gases (from electromagnetic radiation star specter) that coincides with the predicted Big Bang theory (3/4 hydrogen and 1/4 helium).
- ES.FCT 1.IE.5. Communicates scientific ideas on the types of stars, their life-cycles, and the elements they produce. Emphasis is on nucleosynthesis and the different that create it, as well as the variations as mass function of the star and its life-span.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.6. Describes the condition under which the total mass and energy of the universe are conserved.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.FIT 1.

Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimize the design solution

INDICATOR

ES.FIT 1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.FIT 1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution to a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.FIT 1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution to a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability, and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.FIT 1.IT.3.

Uses available technological means to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life situations and optimize pre-existing models.

- ES.F.IT.1.IT.4. Explains the functioning and utility of designed models to solve everyday problems.
- ES.F.IT.1.IT.5. Identifies the limitations of developed designs for solutions that consider society's wishes and needs.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ES.Q. Chemistry

DOMAIN

Chemical reactions

EXPECTATION ES.Q.CF1.

Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties of matter; Chemical reactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Development of possible solutions to a scientific problem; Improve the design

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization level of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.1. Describes and explains the different atomic models that have been postulated and the different experiments that led to the discovery of subatomic particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.2. Uses models to explain the atom's structure and its relationship with matter's properties.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.3. Explains the meaning of isotope concept, applies knowledge to determine the average atomic mass of an element and argues on its applications, benefits and risks in different aspects of the real world.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.4. Develops models to represent the changes in the atom's nucleus composition and the energy released during fusion, fission, and radioactive disintegration processes. Examples of models must include mathematical representations.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.5. Reviews the fundamentals of the atom's mechanical-quantum model to write electronic configurations and electronic structure of symbols (Lewis Diagram).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.6. Discusses contributions realized by different scientists in the development of the Periodic Table as a method to order and classify elements based on their properties. Contributions from Dobereiner, John Newlands, Dimitri Mendeleiv, Henry Mosely, among others, will be considered.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.7. Uses the periodic table as a model to determine the electronic configuration of elements and explains why elements of a same group have similar properties (periodic properties).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.8. Compares and contrasts the properties of metals, non-metals, metalloids and inert gases, and explains their uses and technological applications, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.9. Identifies and explains the properties that determine the location of an element in a period and a family on the Periodic Table, and uses them to predict the relative properties of other elements. Examples of these can be valence electrons and atomic number.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.10. Uses tendencies or patterns of the represented properties on the Periodic Table (atomic number, atomic mass, electronegativity, oxidation state and others) to

predict the elements' behavior and types of links that they form.

	ES.Q.CF1.EM.11.	Describes the processes by which substances are combined to form different chemical compositions and applies the naming convention of names and formulas of ionic and covalent compounds. The naming convention of positive and negative monoatomic and polyatomic ions are integrated based on their number of oxidation.
INDICATOR	ES.Q.CF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data on the properties of substances before and after interacting, to determine if a chemical reaction has happened. Examples of reactions may include burning sugar, wool-steel, and combining zinc or iron with hydrochloric acid.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.2.	Classifies chemical reactions and identifies the characteristics that distinguish them. (Combustion reactions, synthesis, etc).
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.3.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the total number of atoms does not change in a chemical reaction, and therefore mass is conserved. Emphasis is on Matter's Conservation Law and physical models and diagrams, including digital forms that represent atoms.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.4.	Designs a project to prove and modify a mechanism that releases or absorbs thermal energy in a chemical process. Emphasis is on the design, controlling the energy transference toward and from the environment, and the mechanism's modification using variables such as the type and concentration of a substance.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.5.	Creates a model that illustrates the absorption or release of energy in a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the idea that a chemical reaction is a system that produces changes of energy. Examples of models could include diagrams of reactions at a molecular level.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.6.	Applies principles and scientific evidence to provide an explanation about the effects of temperature changes or of particle concentration involved in the speed of a reaction. Emphasis is on the student's reasoning to focus on the number of particles and the energy of collision between molecules.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.7.	Evaluates the design of a chemical system specifying what change in the condition would produce an increase in the quantity of the product in equilibrium. Emphasis is on applying the Le Chatelier principle and on refining designs of chemical reaction systems, including descriptions of the connections between changes made at a macroscopic level, and what happens at a molecular level. Examples of design may include different ways of increasing the formation of a product when including the addition or extraction of reactives or products.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.8.	Uses mathematical representations to determine the stoichiometry of reactions and support the statement that atoms, and therefore, mass, are conserved during a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the use of

mathematical ideas to communicate the proportional relationships between atom's mass in reactives and products. Emphasis is also on the student's evaluation on the use of mathematical thinking and not on memorizing or memorized technique application to solve problems.

- ES.Q.CF1.IE.9. Analyzes the form in which energy is manifested and transformed from one form to another, for example, from chemical to thermal energy and from light to electric.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.10. Describes the temperature and heat flow in terms of random movement and atom and molecule vibrations.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.11. Explains how the transformation of energy is produced and vice versa during a nuclear reaction when applying the equation $\Delta E = \Delta mc^2$.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.12. Evaluates the process that occurs during a chemical reaction in terms of chemical energy transformation. Examples include necessary activation energy, absorption, and energy release during the reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.13. Explains that absorbed or released heat in a chemical reaction comes from the total energy involved in the process of forming and breaking links.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.14. Calculates the quantity of absorbed or released heat by a substance or by a chemical reaction when temperature changes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.15. Explains the difference between the concepts of enthalpy, entropy, and free energy, and how these determine the spontaneity of chemical reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.16. Uses Hess's law to determine the change in enthalpy of a chemical reaction.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.17. Explains the acid-base reactions and their application in chemical or biological processes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.18. Explains the relationship between the structure of molecules, chemical links and chemical energy.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.19. Evaluates new energetic options such as hydrogen, ethanol, carbon, waste incineration and others, with their economic and environmental implications.

DOMAIN

Structure and properties of matter

EXPECTATION ES.Q.CF1.

Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Nuclear processes; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Definitions of energy

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.12. Discriminates between extensive and intensive physical properties of matter and analyzes varied examples of situations where the material's property is fundamental for diverse uses. Examples include density, ductility, conductivity, etc.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.13. Communicates scientific and technical information on why the structure at a molecular level is important for the functioning of the design of materials. Examples may

include why materials that conduct electricity are usually made of metal, that long-lasting flexible materials are made of linked molecules, and that pharmaceutical products are designed to interact with specific receptors.

- ES.Q.CF1.EM.14. Analyzes the kinetic-molecular theory to describe and explain the physical properties of matter's states through a model.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.15. Relates the thermal energy content of a material with the movement of particles that compose it according to the kinetic-molecular theory.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.16. Explains the temperature concepts in terms of average kinetic energy content of particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.17. Describes and compares the crystalline structure and properties of different types of solids.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.18. Relates the properties of liquids (viscosity, superficial tension, capillary action and others) with intermolecular forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.19. Develops a model to predict and describe the changes in particle movement, temperature and state of a substance when there is energy change (addition or subtraction). Emphasis is on molecular quantitative models of solids, liquids and gases to demonstrate that changes in thermal energy affect the particles' kinetic energy until a change of state occurs. Example of a model is phase diagram of water and CO₂.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.20. Collects information on the attraction forces between molecules to compare the structure of different substances and infer on the intensity of forces between particles. Examples of forces are dispersion and dipole forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.21. Describes matter's classification system based on its characteristic properties (homogeneous and heterogeneous materials, substances, mixtures, solutions, etc) and applies them to explain its behavior.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.22. Designs and practices a procedure that applies adequate methods to separate mixtures and identifies substances present within, considering their properties. Offers examples of utility and application of these processes in the real world (filtration, chromatography, etc).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.23. Analyzes the properties of solutions based on the properties of their components. Examples include solute and dissolvent, types of solutions (liquid-solid, liquid-gas, etc), solution concentration (diluted, saturated, oversaturated), factors that affect solubility, solubility curves, colligative properties, solvation (dissolution) process and forces between solute and dissolvent.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.24. Analyzes the oxidation and reduction reactions to explain how they manifest in natural processes and identifies their applications in industry.

INDICATOR

ES.Q.CF1.CC. Conservation and change

ES.Q.CF1.CC.1. Analyzes the process by which chemical reactions reach

an equilibrium.

- ES.Q.CF1.CC.2. Analyzes and interprets data that shows that total mass and energy in the universe are always conserved.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.3. Evaluates Matter's Conservation Law to describe the changes that exist in a chemical reaction and establishes that in a chemical reaction the type and quantity of atoms are conserved even-though their combination form is changed. Emphasis is on the writing of chemical equations and the balance of these.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.4. Analyzes and interprets data to apply the mole concept in the calculation of empiric and molecular formulas, stoichiometric relationships and to express the concentration of a solution (molarity).
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.5. Identifies stoichiometric relationships in a chemical reaction and calculates the theoretical yield and the actual yield in balanced chemical equations. (Percent Yield)
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.6. Applies the gas laws to explain the relationship and effects of changes in pressure, temperature and volume in situations like building aerostats, climate changes and scuba-diving tanks, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.7. Collects evidence to explain how human activities interfere in climate changes, global warming and increased greenhouse effect gases, and proposes alternatives to minimize the effects, both locally and worldwide.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.Q.IT1.

Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Improves the design

INDICATOR

ES.Q.IT1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.Q.IT1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution for a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.3.

Uses technological means within reach to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life problems and optimize the utility of existing models.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.4.

Explains the functioning and use of models designed to solve everyday life problems.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.5.

Identifies the limitations of engineering designs to review the system and make decisions as to their use.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ESA.

Environmental Sciences

DOMAIN

History of Earth

EXPECTATION	ESA.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Earth's history; Tectonic plates and interaction systems on a large scale; Nuclear processes
INDICATOR	ESA.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT1.CC.1.	Evaluates evidence on the movement of continental and oceanic crusts in the past and in the present, as well as, the Theory of Tectonic Plates to explain the age of the crust's rocks. Emphasis is on the evidence that tectonic plates present to explain the age of rocks on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.2.	Describes the structure and changes that occur on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.3.	Explains the current geography of the island of Puerto Rico examining its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.4.	Analyzes geological phenomena based on the Theory of Tectonic Plates.
	ESA.CT1.CC.5.	Explains the geological evolution of Puerto Rico, identifying the tectonic plates around the island that have contributed to its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.6.	Identifies and describes the properties and formation of different minerals, and their location in Puerto Rico.
	ESA.CT1.CC.7.	Reviews obtained evidence from old materials from planet Earth, meteorites, and planetary surfaces, and uses it to build an explanation of the history and formation of Earth. Emphasis is on the use of available evidence within the solar system for reconstructing planet Earth's history. Examples of evidence include the age of materials (obtained by radiometric data of meteorites, lunar rocks, and the most antique minerals on Earth), the size and composition of objects in the solar system and the impact records of craters on Earth's surface.
	ESA.CT1.CC.8.	Explains the historical development of environmental education and Science progress in this area to maintain and /or recover planet Earth's wellbeing. Examples of values in environmental science may include a discussion of careers in environmental sciences and their implications in society.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	ESA.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth and the solar system; Tectonic plates and interaction systems at a large scale; Earth's materials and systems; Biogeology; Water's role in the processes of Earth's surface; Weather and climate
INDICATOR	ESA.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ESA.CT2.EM.1.	Describes water's properties and their effects of Earth's materials and processes of the surface. Emphasis is on chemical and mechanical investigations with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between hydrological cycles and interaction systems known commonly as the rock cycle. Examples of research may include: transport and deposit of rivers using flow diagrams and erosion using a content variety

on soil moisture. Examples of chemical research include weathering, erosion and re-crystallization or fusion generation (when examining how water decreases the fusion temperature of most solids).

- ESA.CT2.EM.2. Explains the importance of water for organisms and the need to protect this resource.
- ESA.CT2.EM.3. Builds an argument based on evidence of the co-evolution of Earth's systems and life on Earth. Emphasis is on the cause, effects and reaction of the dynamics between the biosphere and other Earth systems by which geo-science factors control the evolution of life, that at the same time continuously alters Earth's surface. Examples include how photosynthetic life alters the atmosphere by means of oxygen production, which at the same time increases the wear index and permits the evolution of animal life; or how evolution of coral reefs alter the erosion patterns and deposition of the coastlines and provide a habitat for the evolution of new life forms.
- ESA.CT2.EM.4. Collects evidence on the geological origin, location, and importance of Puerto Rico's natural resources and compares that evidence with that of other major Antilles islands. Examples of natural resources may include minerals, elements, forests and other non-renewable and renewable resources.
- ESA.CT2.EM.5. Identifies the characteristics of the natural environment of a tropical region to establish a contrast with the natural environments of other regions of the world.
- ESA.CT2.EM.6. Classifies and describes the characteristics, location and importance of Puerto Rico's forests. Compares other forests on Earth with tropical forests.
- INDICATOR ESA.CT2.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CT2.IE.1. Describes how internal and superficial Earth processes operate at different scales to conform the characteristics of continental and oceanic floors. Emphasis is on how the appearance of the characteristics of terrestrial surfaces (mountains, valleys, plains) and characteristics of oceanic floors (pits, ridges and oceanic mountains) are the result of both constructive forces (vulcanism, tectonic elevations, orogeny) and destructive forces (weathering, sedimentation mass and coastline erosion).
- ESA.CT2.IE.2. Analyzes geosciences data to affirm that a change on Earth's surface can generate a reaction that causes changes in other terrestrial systems. Examples must include the reactions that occur and affect climate, such as the result of greenhouse gases that cause the increase in temperatures that melt glacial ice, which reduces the quantity of solar rays that reflect on Earth's surface that cause an increase in surface temperature and further reduces the quantity of ice. Also, the loss of vegetation causes an increase in soil erosion; and damming rivers increases the recharge of subterraneous water, decreases sediment transport and increases coastline erosion.

- ESA.CT2.IE.3. Identifies human activities that intervene with the effect of global climate changes, analyzes diverse alternatives that permit minimizing this and evaluates the levels of local and international efforts to counteract the increase of greenhouse effect gases in the atmosphere.
- ESA.CT2.IE.4. Explains the relationship between energy and frequency of natural phenomena.
- ESA.CT2.IE.5. Examines why earthquakes happen and how their intensity is measured.
- ESA.CT2.IE.6. Develops a model of Earth's interior to describe the cycles of matter by thermal convection. Emphasis is on both the unidimensional model of Earth (with radial rays determined by density) and the tridimensional model which is controlled by convection of Earth's crust and tectonic plates.
- ESA.CT2.IE.7. Uses a model to describe how the flow variation of energy in and out of Earth's systems, results in climate changes. Examples include the evaluation of results in climate changes that are limited to temperature changes on the surface, precipitation patterns, volume of glacial ice, sea level, and biosphere distribution. Include the relationship between matter's cycles and energy flow, in the light of the Matter and Energy Conservation Law.
- ESA.CT2.IE.8. Obtains evidence that heat is absorbed or released in an ecosystem to compare the effect in the diverse ecosystems of Puerto Rico. Examples may include coastlines, urban areas, forests, mountains.
- ESA.CT2.IE.9. Recognizes that the major cause of climatological events on planet Earth is related to the interaction of solar energy with Earth, atmosphere and seas.
- ESA.CT2.IE.10. Plans and conducts research on water's properties and their effects on Earth's materials and surface processes. Emphasis is on the chemical and mechanical research with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between the hydrologic cycle and interaction systems, also known as the rock cycle.
- ESA.CT2.IE.11. Discusses the importance of aquatic ecosystems for the water dependent species and proposes alternatives for their conservation.
- ESA.CT2.IE.12. Describes the importance of hydrologic sciences.
- ESA.CT2.IE.13. Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon between the hydrosphere and atmosphere. Emphasis is on modeling biogeochemical cycles that include the carbon cycle by the ocean, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) when providing the base for living organisms.
- ESA.CT2.IE.14. Uses models and diagrams to explain the patterns of oceanic currents and winds that affect Puerto Rico and all the Caribbean.

DOMAIN

Human sustainability

EXPECTATION ESA.CT3.

Earth and human activity - Global climate change; natural resources; Weather and climate; Natural

		disasters; Human impact on Earth's systems; development of possible solutions
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ESA.CT3.IE.1.	Identifies how the historic origin of cities and human communities have affected populations in urban and rural zones.
	ESA.CT3.IE.2.	Evaluates the effect of human beings on communities and the capacity of planet Earth to support populations. Emphasis should include the capacity of having sufficient natural resources to satisfy the basic needs such as water, food and shelter.
	ESA.CT3.IE.3.	Describes the value of ecosystems and argues on the importance of their conservation and protection, and conservation and protection of their organisms, including specificity of the ecosystems and organisms of Puerto Rico. Emphasis must be on native organisms of Puerto Rico. Gives examples of organisms that are in salt-water, fresh-water, mangrove, beach, rocky-coast, coral reef ecosystems.
	ESA.CT3.IE.4.	Describes the use of common energy sources such as: fossil fuels, nuclear energy and alternate sources such as: wind, solar, ethanol and hydraulic.
	ESA.CT3.IE.5.	Explains the advantages and disadvantages, including economic impact, of the uses of energy that provide available resources and possible energy alternatives, analyzing the impact of fossil resource exploitation of the environment.
	ESA.CT3.IE.6.	Evaluates documents and announcements on the laws and government propositions on environmental conservation. Examples of laws or propositions would be on the protection of certain species and application of regulations on car emissions.
	ESA.CT3.IE.7.	Describes change patterns and action measures that would protect them in case of natural phenomena, such as earthquakes and hurricanes, according to the different geographic zones in Puerto Rico. Examples of natural phenomena may include hurricanes, earthquakes, tsunamis and storms.
	ESA.CT3.IE.8.	Identifies the effects of hurricanes depending on the geological zone of Puerto Rico.
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT3.CC.1.	Describes, based on scientific evidence, how the availability of natural resources, natural disasters, and climate changes have influenced human activities. Examples of key natural resources include the access to safe water (as rivers, lakes and subterraneous waters), fertile soil regions as deltas, high mineral concentrations and fossil fuels. Examples of natural disasters could be internal processes (as volcanic eruptions or earthquakes), surface processes (as tsunamis, mass wasting and floor erosion), and severe climate (as hurricanes, floods and droughts). Examples of the results in climate changes that can affect the population or drive

them to massive migrations include changes in sea levels, regional temperature patterns and precipitation, and the types of crop that can be grown.

- ESA.CT3.CC.2. Illustrates using technology, the relationships between the management of natural resources, sustainability of human population and biodiversity. Examples of factors that affect the management of natural resources include the cost of resource's extractions, waste management, per capita consumption and development of new technologies. Examples of factors that affect human sustainability include the agricultural efficiency, levels of conservation and urban planning.
- ESA.CT3.CC.3. Analyzes data from geosciences and the results of global climate models to make predictions based on evidence of current and future changes of regional and global climate, and associates future impacts to Earth's systems. Examples of evidence for data and results of climate models are the climate changes (as precipitation and temperature) and the impacts associated to them (as sea levels, volume of glacial ice, or the atmosphere's and ocean's composition).
- ESA.CT3.CC.4. Uses representations to illustrate the relationships between Earth systems and how these relationships are modified by human activity. Examples of the Earth systems that are found in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, lithosphere and biosphere. An example of the extent of the impact of human activities is the increase of carbon monoxide in the atmosphere leads to an increase of photosynthetic biomass on Earth and an increase of the ocean's acidification, that affect the health of marine organisms and marine population.
- ESA.CT3.CC.5. Evaluates design solutions that are competing to develop, manage and use energy and mineral resources based on cost-benefit indicators. Emphasis is on the conservation, recycling, re-using of resources (as minerals and metals) where possible and minimizing the impacts where not possible. Examples include developing better processes and skills for the use of agricultural soils, mining (for carbon, tar sands, bituminous shale) and pumping (oil and natural gas).
- ESA.CT3.CC.6. Evaluates and proposes a technological solution that reduces human activity impact in natural systems. Examples of impact data on human activities may include the quantities and types of pollutants that are emitted, changes in biomass and diversity of species, change in the surface of land for human use (as the development of urban areas, agriculture and livestock or mining). Examples of limitations for future impacts may vary from local efforts (as reducing, reusing and recycling resources) to large scale efforts, as geo-engineering design solutions (as the alteration of global temperatures by means of great changes in the atmosphere and ocean).
- ESA.CT3.CC.7. Evaluates environmental laws that affect the geography

and topography of Puerto Rico, and proposes solutions to eliminate or reduce the effects of various environmental problems in Puerto Rico. Examples may include deforestation, the use of minerals and fossil resources, and the impacts of agriculture.

- ESA.CT3.CC.8. Proposes solutions considering the scientific and economic development of Puerto Rico, in relation to the wellbeing of the natural environment. Examples may include pollution caused by solid waste, biomedical waste, air and water pollution, and conservation of non-renewable resources.
- ESA.CT3.CC.9. Proposes alternatives that help preserve our ecosystems for future generations, ensuring they include economic development and sustainability.
- ESA.CT3.CC.10. Analyzes patterns in changes that are produced in nature, and discusses effective ways to use science knowledge and the scientific method to diminish the change's effects. Examples of patterns may include data on air pollution, atmospheric phenomena, and changes in the population of various species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.11. Develops solutions to solve problems related with the conservation of exotic species, endangered species, and the extinction of other species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.12. Thinks about and implements a recycling and reusing plan of school and community materials.
- ESA.CT3.CC.13. Builds a model that shows how equilibrium in environmental systems is affected if altered beyond its tolerance capacity.

DOMAIN

Matter and energy in organisms and ecosystems

EXPECTATION ESA.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: Structure and processes - Flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycle and energy transference in ecosystems; Energy in chemical processes; Weather and climate

INDICATOR

- ESA.CB1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CB1.IE.8. Represents and describes the carbon cycle in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on illustrating the biogeochemical cycles. The carbon cycle must be included in oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings).
- ESA.CB1.IE.9. Describes the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration in carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples could be models or include simulations or graphic organizers.
- ESA.CB1.IE.10. Explains the importance of the processes that occur in the cycles: hydrological, carbon and nitrogen with the use of diagrams and models, and justifies the reasons why they are vital for living organisms.
- ESA.CB1.IE.11. Reviews evidence to support the fact that entropy is the main factor of energy loss available in food through the trophic levels.
- ESA.CB1.IE.12. Analyzes the role producers, consumers and

decomposers play in the chain and food web of an ecosystem, establishes connections and explains that the food chain or trophic is an example of the survival interrelationship between species. Includes representing food interdependence through the use of diagrams.

ES.A.CB1.IE.13. Represents the food interdependence with diagrams that illustrate chains and trophic webs, and establishes interdependent relationships between the elements of an ecosystem, between ecosystems themselves, and ecosystems and the planet.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.A.IT.1.

Design for engineering- Defines and delimits engineering problems; develops possible solutions; Improves a design

INDICATOR ES.A.IT.1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.A.IT.1.IT.1.

Analyzes a major global challenge impact to specify the limitations and quantitative specifications of the solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.2.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and more manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.3.

Proposes effective forms to raise awareness and promote possible solutions for environmental problems such as air, soil, and water pollution, waste management, species and resource protection, and also sustainable development.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.9.

Identifies innovative projects that permit development in a sustainable way.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.10.

Explains, with examples, how technology impacts life quality from an economic, social and environmental point of view.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.11.

Analyzes situations and takes individual and group decisions in the light of environmental problems.

CONTENT STANDARD

PR.ES.B.

Biology

DOMAIN

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Structure and function; flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycles and energy transference in ecosystems; Organism's development and growth

INDICATOR ES.B.CB1.EM.

Structure and organization levels of matter

ES.B.CB1.EM.1.

Uses models of cell types to establish differences between the organelles and their functions, including the nucleus, that contains the genetic material that determines heredity.

ES.B.CB1.EM.2.

Analyzes the structure of DNA and RNA molecules and their replication by means of tridimensional models.

ES.B.CB1.EM.3.

Explains, using scientific evidence, how DNA's structure

		determines the structure of proteins that perform the essential functions of life thru specialized cell systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.4.	Uses a model to illustrate the rank organization and interaction of systems that realize specific functions within multicellular organisms. Includes the human body systems such as: digestive, circulatory and immunological, skeletal, muscular, nervous, excretory, reproductive, integumentary and endocrinological systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.5.	Plans and realizes a research to provide evidence that the reaction mechanisms keep homeostasis. Examples of research may include the average of heartbeats in reaction to exercise, the reaction of stomas to humidity and temperature, a root's development in reaction to water levels.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.6.	Represents with concept maps or graph organizers, the relationship between the processes that occur in the mitochondria of cells during cellular respiration.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.7.	Builds diagrams and models to represent the changes that occur during the cellular division phases and cellular differentiation, when producing and keeping complex organisms.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB1.IE.1.	Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on making models of biogeochemical cycles that include carbon cycles in the oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) providing the base for living organisms.
	ES B.CB1.IE.2.	Builds and revises an explanation based on evidence on how carbon, hydrogen and oxygen of sugar molecules can combine with other elements to form amino-acids and other carbon molecules. Emphasis is on the use of models and simulations that support this explanation.
	ES B.CB1.IE.3.	Develops a model that illustrates that cellular respiration is a chemical process by which food molecule links and oxygen molecules break-up and form new links, resulting in a net energy transference. Emphasis is on conceptual understanding of entry and exit processes during cellular respiration.
	ES B.CB1.IE.4.	Uses models to illustrate how photosynthesis and respiration transform light energy into stored chemical energy. Emphasis is on the illustration of entry and exit of matter and the transference and transformation of energy in photosynthesis by plants and other photosynthetic organisms. Examples of models can include diagrams, chemical equations and conceptual models.
	ES B.CB1.IE.5.	Collects information about macromolecules (proteins, lipids, carbon hydrates, nucleic acids) that compose a cell and uses it to explain that spatial atom distribution in these determine some of their functions in living organisms.

	ES B.CB1.IE.6.	Explains thru models, the function and structure of cellular membrane in relation to particle movement in biotic and abiotic systems such as: diffusion and osmosis.
	ES B.CB1.IE.7.	Collects evidence to explain that the protein synthesis process is essential in the enzyme production that regulates all the processes that the cell realizes.
DOMAIN		Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics
EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB2.	Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics - Interdependent relationships in ecosystems; Dynamics, functioning and resistance of ecosystems; Cyclical movement of matter and energy transference in ecosystems; Social interactions and group behavior; Human beings and biodiversity; Development of a possible solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB2.EM.1.	Uses mathematical or technological representations to support explanations about the factors that affect the carrying capacity of ecosystems at different scales. Emphasis is on the quantitative analysis and relationship comparison between interdependent factors including limits, resources, climate and competition. Examples of mathematical comparisons may include graphs, tables, histograms, and population changes collected from simulations and historical data.
	ES.B.CB2.EM.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support and revise the explanations based on evidence about the factors that affect biodiversity and populations in ecosystems ant different scales. Examples of mathematical representations include finding an average, determine trends or patterns, and use comparative graphs of a variety of data.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB2.IE.1.	Builds and revises an explanation, based on evidence, about the cycles of matter and energy flow in aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of aerobic and anaerobic respiration in different environments.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support statements on matter's cycles and energy flow between organisms of an ecosystem. Emphasis is on the use of mathematical models of energy storage in biomass, to describe the flow transference of energy thru ecosystems. Emphasis is on atoms and molecules (such as carbon, oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) that are kept as they pass thru an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.3.	Develops models to illustrate the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples of models could include simulations and mathematical models. The evaluation does not include the specific chemical steps of photosynthesis and respiration.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.4.	Evaluates statements, evidence and reasoning that

complex interactions of ecosystems keep the number and type of organisms in a relatively consistent way in stable conditions. But changes in the conditions may result in a new ecosystem. Examples of changes in the conditions of an ecosystem may include small changes, either physical or biological such as temporary hunting or flooding; or extreme changes as volcanic eruptions and increase in sea levels.

INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB2.CC.1.	Identifies environmental factors to discuss the negative and positive effects of population growth.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.2.	Builds a model that represents and explains the step sequence of ecological succession states in an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.3.	Explains the relationship between populations, communities and ecosystems of the biosphere.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.4.	Designs, evaluates and refines a solution to reduce the impact of human activities in the environment and biodiversity. Examples of the activities may include urbanization, dam construction, dissemination of invading species.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.5.	Evaluates scientific evidence of group behavior of individuals and the opportunity they have to survive and reproduce. Emphasis is on : (1) distinguishing between group and individual behavior, (2) identifying evidence that supports the results of group behavior and (3) developing logical and reasonable arguments based on evidence. Examples of group behavior may include flocks, herds and cooperative behaviors such as hunting, migrations and swarms.

DOMAIN

Heredity and characteristic variations

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB3. Heredity and characteristic variations - Structure and function; Characteristic heredity; Characteristic variations

INDICATOR	ES.B.CB3.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB3.EM.1.	Poses questions to clarify the relationship of DNA's role and chromosomes in the instruction codes for the characteristic variations that pass from one generation to another.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB3.CC.1.	Poses and defends a statement based on evidence about the genetic and hereditary variations that can result from: (1) new genetic combination thru the meiosis process, (2) viable errors that may occur during DNA replication and/or (3) mutations caused by environmental factors. Emphasis is on the use of data to support arguments on the different forms in which mutations can occur.
	ES.B.CB3.CC.2.	Applies statistical and probability concepts to explain the variation and distribution of visible characteristics in a population. Emphasis is on the use of mathematics to describe the probability and characteristic presence that are related to genetics and environmental factors., as

well as representing phenotypic and genotypic proportions in different genetic crossings.

ES.B.CB3.CC.3. Recognizes and explains that multicellular organisms are developed from a simple zygote and that the resulting phenotype will depend on the genotype that was established at the moment of fertilization.

ES.B.CB3.CC.4. Explains the importance of life's continuity thru the action of genes, hereditary patterns, organism reproduction and cell reproduction.

DOMAIN

Natural selection and evolution

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB4.

Biological evolution: Unity and diversity - Evidence of common ancestors and diversity; Adaptation; Natural selection; Biodiversity and human beings; Development of a possible solution

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

ES.B.CB4.EM.1.

Communicates scientific information that biological evolution and common ancestors are supported by multiple lines of empiric evidence. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of each evidence line has and biological in relation to the common ancestor evidence and biological evolution. Examples of evidence may include similarities in the DNA sequences, anatomic structures and development appearance order of embryological structures.

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.B.CB4.IE.1.

Builds an explanation based on evidence that the evolution process mainly results from four factors: (1) a species potential to increase in quantity, (2) the genetic variation of individuals in a species by mutation or sexual reproduction, (3) the competition for limited resources that each individual needs to survive and reproduce in the environment, and (4) ensure the proliferation of those organisms that are more able to survive and reproduce in the environment. Emphasis is on the use of evidence to explain the influence that the four factors have on the number of organisms, behaviors, morphology, or physiology, in terms of the ability to compete for limited resources and subsequently, in the individual survival and adaptation of species. Examples of evidence may include mathematical models as a simple distribution graph and proportional reasoning.

ES.B.CB4.IE.2.

Determines the effects of the different types of natural selection in the gene set (gene pool) of an organism.

ES.B.CB4.IE.3.

Applies statistical and probability concepts to support explanations about organisms with advantageous hereditary characteristics that tend to increase in proportion comparing to those that don't have the same characteristics. Emphasis is on the change analysis in the numerical distribution of the characteristics and on using these changes as evidence to support explanation on how natural selection determines the survival capacity for groups of organisms.

ES.B.CB4.IE.4.

Builds an explanation based on evidence on how natural

		selection leads to the adaptation of populations. Emphasis is on using data to provide evidence on how biotic and abiotic differences in ecosystems (seasonal temperature changes, long period climate changes, light, acidity, geographic barriers, or evolution of other organisms) contribute to gene changes throughout time, leading to adaptation of the population. Hardy Weinberg's principle is integrated to quantify the process of natural selection in a population.
	ES.B.CB4.IE.5.	Evaluates the role of natural selection in the development of the Theory of Evolution.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB4.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB4.CC.1.	Evaluates the evidence that supports the statements that changes in the environmental conditions may result in: (1) increase in the number of individuals of a species, (2) emergence of new species, (3) extinction of other species. Emphasis is on determining the cause-effect relationships on how environmental changes, such as deforestation, fishing, use of fertilizers, drought, flooding and rate of environmental changes, affect the distribution or disappearance of species' characteristics.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.2.	Reviews and evaluates a simulation to test a solution that decreases the adverse impacts of human activities in biodiversity. Emphasis is on the design of solutions for a proposed problem that is related to a threatened species or in danger of extinction; or with genetic variation of multiple species organisms.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.3.	Analyzes how human beings have the responsibility to keep the environment in good condition for the survival of species.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	ES.B.IT1.	Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Optimizes the design solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.IT1.IT.	Design for Engineering
	ES.B.IT1.IT.1.	Analyzes a major global challenge to specify the limitations and quantitative criteria of solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.2.	Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be resolved using engineering knowledge.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.3.	Evaluates a real and complex problem solution based on criteria as costs, benefits, security, trustworthiness, and aesthetics considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.4.	Uses a computer simulation to model the impact of proposed solutions to solve a real and complex problem with multiple criteria and limitations within and between the relevant systems to the problem.
CONTENT	PR.ES.F.	Physics

STANDARD

DOMAIN

Forces and interactions

EXPECTATION ES.FCF2.

Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems

INDICATOR ES.FCF2.EM.

Structure and organization levels of matter

ES.FCF2.EM.1.

Explains what fluids are and describes how these create pressure on a surface. (surface tension)

ES.FCF2.EM.2.

Explains and describes how the surface tension principles and types of fluids affect mechanization. Emphasis is on applying the kinetic-molecular theory.

INDICATOR ES.FCF2.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.FCF2.IE.1.

Designs a model to explain the movement of a dimension through verbal, graphic and mathematic descriptions. Emphasis is on the movement's description through the concepts of: distance, displacement, speed, velocity and acceleration. The use of the units from the International Measurement System must be integrated, and also their conversions, significant digits, scientific notation and mathematical equations.

ES.FCF2.IE.2.

Identifies and describes the four fundamental forces in everyday life: strong nuclear interaction, weak nuclear interaction, gravity and electromagnetism.

ES.FCF2.IE.3.

Uses knowledge on the different movement laws to apply them in problem solutions of everyday life. Emphasis is on the Newton, Coulomb and Kepler laws.

ES.FCF2.IE.4.

Uses Newton's second law of motion when describing the mathematical relationship between net force on a macroscopic object, its mass and acceleration. Data examples may include tables or position or velocity graphs as time function for objects subject to a non-balanced net force, such as an object in free-fall, and object rolling on a ramp or an object in movement pulled by a constant force.

ES.FCF2.IE.5.

Uses mathematical representations of Newton's gravitational law and Coulomb's law, to describe and predict gravitational and electrostatic forces between objects.

ES.FCF2.IE.6.

Explains the functioning of machines, using force and movement concepts that are useful or resolve an everyday-life problem.

ES.FCF2.IE.7.

Uses mathematical representations to describe movement in two dimensions and the force equilibrium with vectors. Represents and calculates the magnitude and direction of vector quantities by graph and mathematical methods applying the basic trigonometrical functions. Projectile motion and inclined plane are included.

ES.FCF2.IE.8.

Designs an experiment to explain the principles and applications of uniform circular movement and simple harmonic movement.

	ES.FCF2.IE.9.	Applies scientific and engineering ideas to design and evaluate an apparatus that minimizes the force on a macroscopic object during collision. The examples may include a helmet or parachute.
	ES.FCF2.IE.10.	Explains the concepts of electrical charge, electric current, electric potential, electric field, and magnetic field, and establishes the difference between contact forces and long-range forces. Explains the properties of conductive materials and designs electrical circuits in series and in parallel.
	ES.FCF2.IE.11.	Offers experimental evidence that an electric current may produce a magnetic field and a magnetic field may produce an electric current.
	ES.FCF2.IE.12.	Describes apparatus that resolve everyday-life problems and those which result from the application of physics. Examples of force may be: electrical, magnetic, gravitational and nuclear forces. Examples of apparatus may include those that use conductors, circuits and fields.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.FCF2.CC.1.	Uses mathematical representations to support the premise that the total momentum of a system of objects is preserved when the net force on the system is zero.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	ES.FCF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Energy in chemical processes in everyday-life.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ES.FCF3.EM.1.	Explains energy in terms of scale, from atomic scale to macroscopic scale.
	ES.FCF3.EM.2.	Classifies energy as kinetic or potential and contrasts the different types: thermal, chemical, nuclear, electromagnetic and mechanical. Calculates the kinetic and potential energy changes in a system.
	ES.FCF3.EM.3.	Classifies and explains the origin of different sources of energy: fossil-fuels, solar, geothermic, wind, hydraulic, biomass, among others.
	ES.FCF3.EM.4.	Explains the relationship between energy, work, and power.
	ES.FCF3.EM.5.	Explains the work-energy theorem.
	ES.FCF3.EM.6.	Identifies the electrical phenomena as a manifestation of the charges of subatomic particles (electrons).
	ES.FCF3.EM.7.	Compares electric and magnetic forces regarding the field and its relationship with charges in movement.
	ES.FCF3.EM.8.	Explains the relationships between electrostatic charges using Coulomb's laws.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.FCF3.IE.1.	Calculates the energy change between the components of a system when the energy of one of them is known and the energy flow into or out-of the systems.

- ES.FCF3.IE.2. Designs a model that illustrates that energy at a macroscopic scale may be understood as a combination of energy associated to particle movements (objects) and energy associated to the relative position of particles (objects). Examples of macroscopic scale phenomena may include the conversion of kinetic energy to thermal energy, stored energy in an object positioned over Earth, and stored energy between two electrically charged plates.
- ES.FCF3.IE.3. Designs and refines an apparatus that works within controlled limitations to convert energy from one form into another. Examples of apparatus may include Rube Goldberg, wind turbines, solar cells, solar ovens and generators. Examples of limitations may include the use of renewable energy forms and efficiency.
- ES.FCF3.IE.4. Explains that when two components are combined at different temperatures in an enclosed system, the total transference of thermal energy results in a more uniform energy distribution between the system's components (thermodynamics' second law). Examples of research may include mixing liquids with different initial temperatures or adding different temperature objects to water.
- ES.FCF3.IE.5. Explains the interactions through electrical or magnetic fields to illustrate the forces between objects and energy changes of objects from interaction.
- ES.FCF3.IE.6. Plans and realizes research to propose the use of different energy sources in Puerto Rico, taking into consideration the cost-benefit and cost-effective proportion.

DOMAIN

Waves and their applications

EXPECTATION ES.FCF4.

Waves and their applications to technological development - Wave's properties; Electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.FCF4.EM.1. Explains, through models, the effect of wave's properties in the behavior of matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.2. Distinguishes between the types of mechanical waves: transverse and longitudinal.
- ES.FCF4.EM.3. Explains the idea that electromagnetic radiation can be described with a wave model or particle model, and that in some cases, one of the models is more useful than the other. Examples include how wave and particle models explain the properties of visible light.
- ES.FCF4.EM.4. Explains reflection, refraction, diffraction, polarization, transformation and absorption as manifestations of the interactions between waves and matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.5. Proposes the development of technology that demonstrates the application of light properties in the design of useful prototypes or to resolve a daily-life problem.
- ES.FCF4.EM.6. Explains and describes how wave principles are used to

create useful technologies for humans.

- ES.FCF4.EM.7. Communicates technical information on how some technological apparatus use behavioral principles and interactions of waves with matter to transmit and capture information and energy. Examples may include solar cells that capture light and convert it into electricity, medical imaging, and communication technologies.
- ES.FCF4.EM.8. Evaluates questions about the advantages and disadvantages of the transmission and digital storage of information. Examples of advantages may include that digital information is stable because it can be stored, transferred and copied in a reliable, easy and rapid way in a computer. The disadvantages could be problems related to the deletion, security and theft of information.
- ES.FCF4.EM.9. Evaluates and supports or refutes the validity and reliability of the premises in publications about the effects of distant electromagnetic radiation frequencies when absorbed by matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.10. Analyzes mirror's and lenses' properties to design beam diagrams that will allow to calculate the location and size of images.
- ES.FCF4.EM.11. Searches for reliable sources of information on the scientific or everyday applications of mirrors and lenses, to make an oral presentation.

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCF4.IE.1. Analyzes wave behavior as a transference phenomenon of energy.
- ES.FCF4.IE.2. Describes energy transference in mechanic waves, such as sound waves.
- ES.FCF4.IE.3. Describes a model to represent the relationships between wave properties in different environments. Examples must include a model that represents interference and the principle of superposition.
- ES.FCF4.IE.4. Uses mathematical representations to support a premise regarding the relationship between frequencies, length of wave, speed of waves traveling through different environments. Examples of data may include electromagnetic radiation traveling through voids and glass, or seismic waves through Earth.
- ES.FCF4.IE.5. Identifies practical uses of waves, such as seismic data, acoustic effects and Doppler effect.
- ES.FCF4.IE.6. Plans research to demonstrate how waves produce fields that use or generate particles.

DOMAIN

Space systems

EXPECTATION ES.FCT1.

Earth's place in the universe - Planet Earth and the solar system; Universe and the stars; Energy in chemical processes and in everyday life; Electromagnetic radiation

INDICATOR

- ES.FCT1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCT1.IE.1. Uses mathematical or computational representations to predict the movement of orbital objects in the solar system. Emphasis is on Newton's universal gravitational

law that describes orbital movements, and that are applied to artificial satellites, as well as planets and moons.

- ES.FCT 1.IE.2. Describes and predicts natural phenomena as the movement of celestial bodies, relative movements and others, based on the laws that describe planetary and satellite movements.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.3. Describes the role of nuclear fusion in the Sun's nucleus that releases energy and that at the same time arrives to Earth in the form of radiation. Predicts the Sun's time period using other stars as information base. Emphasis is on energy transference mechanisms that allows nuclear fusion energy from the Sun's center to reach Earth. Examples of evidence for the description may include mass observation and life-span of other stars, as well as solar radiation changes due to sudden Sun flares (spatial climate), 11 yr. Sunspot cycle and the non-cyclical variations through-out the centuries.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.4. Explains the Big Bang theory based on astronomic evidence of light specters, movement in distant galaxies, and the mass composition of the universe. Evidence is on the astronomic evidence from redshift galaxies as indicator that the universe is actually expanding, background radiation microwaves are residues from the Big Bang's radiation, and the study of ordinary mass composition of the universe that is mainly found in stars and interstellar gases (from electromagnetic radiation star specter) that coincides with the predicted Big Bang theory (3/4 hydrogen and 1/4 helium).
- ES.FCT 1.IE.5. Communicates scientific ideas on the types of stars, their life-cycles, and the elements they produce. Emphasis is on nucleosynthesis and the different that create it, as well as the variations as mass function of the star and its life-span.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.6. Describes the condition under which the total mass and energy of the universe are conserved.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.FIT 1.

Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimize the design solution

INDICATOR

ES.FIT 1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.FIT 1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution to a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.FIT 1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution to a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability, and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.FIT 1.IT.3.

Uses available technological means to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life situations and optimize pre-existing models.

- ES.F.IT.1.IT.4. Explains the functioning and utility of designed models to solve everyday problems.
- ES.F.IT.1.IT.5. Identifies the limitations of developed designs for solutions that consider society's wishes and needs.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ES.Q. Chemistry

DOMAIN

Chemical reactions

EXPECTATION

ES.Q.CF1. Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties of matter; Chemical reactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Development of possible solutions to a scientific problem; Improve the design

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization level of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.1. Describes and explains the different atomic models that have been postulated and the different experiments that led to the discovery of subatomic particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.2. Uses models to explain the atom's structure and its relationship with matter's properties.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.3. Explains the meaning of isotope concept, applies knowledge to determine the average atomic mass of an element and argues on its applications, benefits and risks in different aspects of the real world.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.4. Develops models to represent the changes in the atom's nucleus composition and the energy released during fusion, fission, and radioactive disintegration processes. Examples of models must include mathematical representations.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.5. Reviews the fundamentals of the atom's mechanical-quantum model to write electronic configurations and electronic structure of symbols (Lewis Diagram).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.6. Discusses contributions realized by different scientists in the development of the Periodic Table as a method to order and classify elements based on their properties. Contributions from Dobereiner, John Newlands, Dimitri Mendeleev, Henry Mosely, among others, will be considered.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.7. Uses the periodic table as a model to determine the electronic configuration of elements and explains why elements of a same group have similar properties (periodic properties).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.8. Compares and contrasts the properties of metals, non-metals, metalloids and inert gases, and explains their uses and technological applications, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.9. Identifies and explains the properties that determine the location of an element in a period and a family on the Periodic Table, and uses them to predict the relative properties of other elements. Examples of these can be valence electrons and atomic number.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.10. Uses tendencies or patterns of the represented properties on the Periodic Table (atomic number, atomic mass, electronegativity, oxidation state and others) to

predict the elements' behavior and types of links that they form.

ES.Q.CF1.EM.11. Describes the processes by which substances are combined to form different chemical compositions and applies the naming convention of names and formulas of ionic and covalent compounds. The naming convention of positive and negative monoatomic and polyatomic ions are integrated based on their number of oxidation.

INDICATOR	ES.Q.CF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data on the properties of substances before and after interacting, to determine if a chemical reaction has happened. Examples of reactions may include burning sugar, wool-steel, and combining zinc or iron with hydrochloric acid.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.2.	Classifies chemical reactions and identifies the characteristics that distinguish them. (Combustion reactions, synthesis, etc).
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.3.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the total number of atoms does not change in a chemical reaction, and therefore mass is conserved. Emphasis is on Matter's Conservation Law and physical models and diagrams, including digital forms that represent atoms.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.4.	Designs a project to prove and modify a mechanism that releases or absorbs thermal energy in a chemical process. Emphasis is on the design, controlling the energy transference toward and from the environment, and the mechanism's modification using variables such as the type and concentration of a substance.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.5.	Creates a model that illustrates the absorption or release of energy in a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the idea that a chemical reaction is a system that produces changes of energy. Examples of models could include diagrams of reactions at a molecular level.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.6.	Applies principles and scientific evidence to provide an explanation about the effects of temperature changes or of particle concentration involved in the speed of a reaction. Emphasis is on the student's reasoning to focus on the number of particles and the energy of collision between molecules.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.7.	Evaluates the design of a chemical system specifying what change in the condition would produce an increase in the quantity of the product in equilibrium. Emphasis is on applying the Le Chatelier principle and on refining designs of chemical reaction systems, including descriptions of the connections between changes made at a macroscopic level, and what happens at a molecular level. Examples of design may include different ways of increasing the formation of a product when including the addition or extraction of reactives or products.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.8.	Uses mathematical representations to determine the stoichiometry of reactions and support the statement that atoms, and therefore, mass, are conserved during a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the use of

mathematical ideas to communicate the proportional relationships between atom's mass in reactives and products. Emphasis is also on the student's evaluation on the use of mathematical thinking and not on memorizing or memorized technique application to solve problems.

- ES.Q.CF1.IE.9. Analyzes the form in which energy is manifested and transformed from one form to another, for example, from chemical to thermal energy and from light to electric.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.10. Describes the temperature and heat flow in terms of random movement and atom and molecule vibrations.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.11. Explains how the transformation of energy is produced and vice versa during a nuclear reaction when applying the equation $\Delta E = \Delta mc^2$.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.12. Evaluates the process that occurs during a chemical reaction in terms of chemical energy transformation. Examples include necessary activation energy, absorption, and energy release during the reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.13. Explains that absorbed or released heat in a chemical reaction comes from the total energy involved in the process of forming and breaking links.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.14. Calculates the quantity of absorbed or released heat by a substance or by a chemical reaction when temperature changes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.15. Explains the difference between the concepts of enthalpy, entropy, and free energy, and how these determine the spontaneity of chemical reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.16. Uses Hess's law to determine the change in enthalpy of a chemical reaction.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.17. Explains the acid-base reactions and their application in chemical or biological processes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.18. Explains the relationship between the structure of molecules, chemical links and chemical energy.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.19. Evaluates new energetic options such as hydrogen, ethanol, carbon, waste incineration and others, with their economic and environmental implications.

DOMAIN

Structure and properties of matter

EXPECTATION ES.Q.CF1.

Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Nuclear processes; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Definitions of energy

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.12. Discriminates between extensive and intensive physical properties of matter and analyzes varied examples of situations where the material's property is fundamental for diverse uses. Examples include density, ductility, conductivity, etc.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.13. Communicates scientific and technical information on why the structure at a molecular level is important for the functioning of the design of materials. Examples may

include why materials that conduct electricity are usually made of metal, that long-lasting flexible materials are made of linked molecules, and that pharmaceutical products are designed to interact with specific receptors.

- ES.Q.CF1.EM.14. Analyzes the kinetic-molecular theory to describe and explain the physical properties of matter's states through a model.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.15. Relates the thermal energy content of a material with the movement of particles that compose it according to the kinetic-molecular theory.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.16. Explains the temperature concepts in terms of average kinetic energy content of particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.17. Describes and compares the crystalline structure and properties of different types of solids.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.18. Relates the properties of liquids (viscosity, superficial tension, capillary action and others) with intermolecular forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.19. Develops a model to predict and describe the changes in particle movement, temperature and state of a substance when there is energy change (addition or subtraction). Emphasis is on molecular quantitative models of solids, liquids and gases to demonstrate that changes in thermal energy affect the particles' kinetic energy until a change of state occurs. Example of a model is phase diagram of water and CO₂.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.20. Collects information on the attraction forces between molecules to compare the structure of different substances and infer on the intensity of forces between particles. Examples of forces are dispersion and dipole forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.21. Describes matter's classification system based on its characteristic properties (homogeneous and heterogeneous materials, substances, mixtures, solutions, etc) and applies them to explain its behavior.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.22. Designs and practices a procedure that applies adequate methods to separate mixtures and identifies substances present within, considering their properties. Offers examples of utility and application of these processes in the real world (filtration, chromatography, etc).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.23. Analyzes the properties of solutions based on the properties of their components. Examples include solute and dissolvent, types of solutions (liquid-solid, liquid-gas, etc), solution concentration (diluted, saturated, oversaturated), factors that affect solubility, solubility curves, colligative properties, solvation (dissolution) process and forces between solute and dissolvent.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.24. Analyzes the oxidation and reduction reactions to explain how they manifest in natural processes and identifies their applications in industry.

INDICATOR

ES.Q.CF1.CC. Conservation and change

ES.Q.CF1.CC.1. Analyzes the process by which chemical reactions reach

an equilibrium.

- ES.Q.CF1.CC.2. Analyzes and interprets data that shows that total mass and energy in the universe are always conserved.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.3. Evaluates Matter's Conservation Law to describe the changes that exist in a chemical reaction and establishes that in a chemical reaction the type and quantity of atoms are conserved even-though their combination form is changed. Emphasis is on the writing of chemical equations and the balance of these.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.4. Analyzes and interprets data to apply the mole concept in the calculation of empiric and molecular formulas, stoichiometric relationships and to express the concentration of a solution (molarity).
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.5. Identifies stoichiometric relationships in a chemical reaction and calculates the theoretical yield and the actual yield in balanced chemical equations. (Percent Yield)
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.6. Applies the gas laws to explain the relationship and effects of changes in pressure, temperature and volume in situations like building aerostats, climate changes and scuba-diving tanks, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.7. Collects evidence to explain how human activities interfere in climate changes, global warming and increased greenhouse effect gases, and proposes alternatives to minimize the effects, both locally and worldwide.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.Q.IT1.

Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Improves the design

INDICATOR

ES.Q.IT1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.Q.IT1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution for a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.3.

Uses technological means within reach to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life problems and optimize the utility of existing models.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.4.

Explains the functioning and use of models designed to solve everyday life problems.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.5.

Identifies the limitations of engineering designs to review the system and make decisions as to their use.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ESA.

Environmental Sciences

DOMAIN

History of Earth

EXPECTATION	ESA.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Earth's history; Tectonic plates and interaction systems on a large scale; Nuclear processes
INDICATOR	ESA.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT1.CC.1.	Evaluates evidence on the movement of continental and oceanic crusts in the past and in the present, as well as, the Theory of Tectonic Plates to explain the age of the crust's rocks. Emphasis is on the evidence that tectonic plates present to explain the age of rocks on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.2.	Describes the structure and changes that occur on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.3.	Explains the current geography of the island of Puerto Rico examining its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.4.	Analyzes geological phenomena based on the Theory of Tectonic Plates.
	ESA.CT1.CC.5.	Explains the geological evolution of Puerto Rico, identifying the tectonic plates around the island that have contributed to its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.6.	Identifies and describes the properties and formation of different minerals, and their location in Puerto Rico.
	ESA.CT1.CC.7.	Reviews obtained evidence from old materials from planet Earth, meteorites, and planetary surfaces, and uses it to build an explanation of the history and formation of Earth. Emphasis is on the use of available evidence within the solar system for reconstructing planet Earth's history. Examples of evidence include the age of materials (obtained by radiometric data of meteorites, lunar rocks, and the most antique minerals on Earth), the size and composition of objects in the solar system and the impact records of craters on Earth's surface.
	ESA.CT1.CC.8.	Explains the historical development of environmental education and Science progress in this area to maintain and /or recover planet Earth's wellbeing. Examples of values in environmental science may include a discussion of careers in environmental sciences and their implications in society.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	ESA.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth and the solar system; Tectonic plates and interaction systems at a large scale; Earth's materials and systems; Biogeology; Water's role in the processes of Earth's surface; Weather and climate
INDICATOR	ESA.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ESA.CT2.EM.1.	Describes water's properties and their effects of Earth's materials and processes of the surface. Emphasis is on chemical and mechanical investigations with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between hydrological cycles and interaction systems known commonly as the rock cycle. Examples of research may include: transport and deposit of rivers using flow diagrams and erosion using a content variety

on soil moisture. Examples of chemical research include weathering, erosion and re-crystallization or fusion generation (when examining how water decreases the fusion temperature of most solids).

- ESA.CT2.EM.2. Explains the importance of water for organisms and the need to protect this resource.
- ESA.CT2.EM.3. Builds an argument based on evidence of the co-evolution of Earth's systems and life on Earth. Emphasis is on the cause, effects and reaction of the dynamics between the biosphere and other Earth systems by which geo-science factors control the evolution of life, that at the same time continuously alters Earth's surface. Examples include how photosynthetic life alters the atmosphere by means of oxygen production, which at the same time increases the wear index and permits the evolution of animal life; or how evolution of coral reefs alter the erosion patterns and deposition of the coastlines and provide a habitat for the evolution of new life forms.
- ESA.CT2.EM.4. Collects evidence on the geological origin, location, and importance of Puerto Rico's natural resources and compares that evidence with that of other major Antilles islands. Examples of natural resources may include minerals, elements, forests and other non-renewable and renewable resources.
- ESA.CT2.EM.5. Identifies the characteristics of the natural environment of a tropical region to establish a contrast with the natural environments of other regions of the world.
- ESA.CT2.EM.6. Classifies and describes the characteristics, location and importance of Puerto Rico's forests. Compares other forests on Earth with tropical forests.
- INDICATOR ESA.CT2.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CT2.IE.1. Describes how internal and superficial Earth processes operate at different scales to conform the characteristics of continental and oceanic floors. Emphasis is on how the appearance of the characteristics of terrestrial surfaces (mountains, valleys, plains) and characteristics of oceanic floors (pits, ridges and oceanic mountains) are the result of both constructive forces (vulcanism, tectonic elevations, orogeny) and destructive forces (weathering, sedimentation mass and coastline erosion).
- ESA.CT2.IE.2. Analyzes geosciences data to affirm that a change on Earth's surface can generate a reaction that causes changes in other terrestrial systems. Examples must include the reactions that occur and affect climate, such as the result of greenhouse gases that cause the increase in temperatures that melt glacial ice, which reduces the quantity of solar rays that reflect on Earth's surface that cause an increase in surface temperature and further reduces the quantity of ice. Also, the loss of vegetation causes an increase in soil erosion; and damming rivers increases the recharge of subterraneous water, decreases sediment transport and increases coastline erosion.

- ESA.CT2.IE.3. Identifies human activities that intervene with the effect of global climate changes, analyzes diverse alternatives that permit minimizing this and evaluates the levels of local and international efforts to counteract the increase of greenhouse effect gases in the atmosphere.
- ESA.CT2.IE.4. Explains the relationship between energy and frequency of natural phenomena.
- ESA.CT2.IE.5. Examines why earthquakes happen and how their intensity is measured.
- ESA.CT2.IE.6. Develops a model of Earth's interior to describe the cycles of matter by thermal convection. Emphasis is on both the unidimensional model of Earth (with radial rays determined by density) and the tridimensional model which is controlled by convection of Earth's crust and tectonic plates.
- ESA.CT2.IE.7. Uses a model to describe how the flow variation of energy in and out of Earth's systems, results in climate changes. Examples include the evaluation of results in climate changes that are limited to temperature changes on the surface, precipitation patterns, volume of glacial ice, sea level, and biosphere distribution. Include the relationship between matter's cycles and energy flow, in the light of the Matter and Energy Conservation Law.
- ESA.CT2.IE.8. Obtains evidence that heat is absorbed or released in an ecosystem to compare the effect in the diverse ecosystems of Puerto Rico. Examples may include coastlines, urban areas, forests, mountains.
- ESA.CT2.IE.9. Recognizes that the major cause of climatological events on planet Earth is related to the interaction of solar energy with Earth, atmosphere and seas.
- ESA.CT2.IE.10. Plans and conducts research on water's properties and their effects on Earth's materials and surface processes. Emphasis is on the chemical and mechanical research with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between the hydrologic cycle and interaction systems, also known as the rock cycle.
- ESA.CT2.IE.11. Discusses the importance of aquatic ecosystems for the water dependent species and proposes alternatives for their conservation.
- ESA.CT2.IE.12. Describes the importance of hydrologic sciences.
- ESA.CT2.IE.13. Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon between the hydrosphere and atmosphere. Emphasis is on modeling biogeochemical cycles that include the carbon cycle by the ocean, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) when providing the base for living organisms.
- ESA.CT2.IE.14. Uses models and diagrams to explain the patterns of oceanic currents and winds that affect Puerto Rico and all the Caribbean.

DOMAIN

Human sustainability

EXPECTATION ESA.CT3.

Earth and human activity - Global climate change; natural resources; Weather and climate; Natural

		disasters; Human impact on Earth's systems; development of possible solutions
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ESA.CT3.IE.1.	Identifies how the historic origin of cities and human communities have affected populations in urban and rural zones.
	ESA.CT3.IE.2.	Evaluates the effect of human beings on communities and the capacity of planet Earth to support populations. Emphasis should include the capacity of having sufficient natural resources to satisfy the basic needs such as water, food and shelter.
	ESA.CT3.IE.3.	Describes the value of ecosystems and argues on the importance of their conservation and protection, and conservation and protection of their organisms, including specificity of the ecosystems and organisms of Puerto Rico. Emphasis must be on native organisms of Puerto Rico. Gives examples of organisms that are in salt-water, fresh-water, mangrove, beach, rocky-coast, coral reef ecosystems.
	ESA.CT3.IE.4.	Describes the use of common energy sources such as: fossil fuels, nuclear energy and alternate sources such as: wind, solar, ethanol and hydraulic.
	ESA.CT3.IE.5.	Explains the advantages and disadvantages, including economic impact, of the uses of energy that provide available resources and possible energy alternatives, analyzing the impact of fossil resource exploitation of the environment.
	ESA.CT3.IE.6.	Evaluates documents and announcements on the laws and government propositions on environmental conservation. Examples of laws or propositions would be on the protection of certain species and application of regulations on car emissions.
	ESA.CT3.IE.7.	Describes change patterns and action measures that would protect them in case of natural phenomena, such as earthquakes and hurricanes, according to the different geographic zones in Puerto Rico. Examples of natural phenomena may include hurricanes, earthquakes, tsunamis and storms.
	ESA.CT3.IE.8.	Identifies the effects of hurricanes depending on the geological zone of Puerto Rico.
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT3.CC.1.	Describes, based on scientific evidence, how the availability of natural resources, natural disasters, and climate changes have influenced human activities. Examples of key natural resources include the access to safe water (as rivers, lakes and subterraneous waters), fertile soil regions as deltas, high mineral concentrations and fossil fuels. Examples of natural disasters could be internal processes (as volcanic eruptions or earthquakes), surface processes (as tsunamis, mass wasting and floor erosion), and severe climate (as hurricanes, floods and droughts). Examples of the results in climate changes that can affect the population or drive

them to massive migrations include changes in sea levels, regional temperature patterns and precipitation, and the types of crop that can be grown.

- ESA.CT3.CC.2. Illustrates using technology, the relationships between the management of natural resources, sustainability of human population and biodiversity. Examples of factors that affect the management of natural resources include the cost of resource's extractions, waste management, per capita consumption and development of new technologies. Examples of factors that affect human sustainability include the agricultural efficiency, levels of conservation and urban planning.
- ESA.CT3.CC.3. Analyzes data from geosciences and the results of global climate models to make predictions based on evidence of current and future changes of regional and global climate, and associates future impacts to Earth's systems. Examples of evidence for data and results of climate models are the climate changes (as precipitation and temperature) and the impacts associated to them (as sea levels, volume of glacial ice, or the atmosphere's and ocean's composition).
- ESA.CT3.CC.4. Uses representations to illustrate the relationships between Earth systems and how these relationships are modified by human activity. Examples of the Earth systems that are found in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, lithosphere and biosphere. An example of the extent of the impact of human activities is the increase of carbon monoxide in the atmosphere leads to an increase of photosynthetic biomass on Earth and an increase of the ocean's acidification, that affect the health of marine organisms and marine population.
- ESA.CT3.CC.5. Evaluates design solutions that are competing to develop, manage and use energy and mineral resources based on cost-benefit indicators. Emphasis is on the conservation, recycling, re-using of resources (as minerals and metals) where possible and minimizing the impacts where not possible. Examples include developing better processes and skills for the use of agricultural soils, mining (for carbon, tar sands, bituminous shale) and pumping (oil and natural gas).
- ESA.CT3.CC.6. Evaluates and proposes a technological solution that reduces human activity impact in natural systems. Examples of impact data on human activities may include the quantities and types of pollutants that are emitted, changes in biomass and diversity of species, change in the surface of land for human use (as the development of urban areas, agriculture and livestock or mining). Examples of limitations for future impacts may vary from local efforts (as reducing, reusing and recycling resources) to large scale efforts, as geo-engineering design solutions (as the alteration of global temperatures by means of great changes in the atmosphere and ocean).
- ESA.CT3.CC.7. Evaluates environmental laws that affect the geography

and topography of Puerto Rico, and proposes solutions to eliminate or reduce the effects of various environmental problems in Puerto Rico. Examples may include deforestation, the use of minerals and fossil resources, and the impacts of agriculture.

- ESA.CT3.CC.8. Proposes solutions considering the scientific and economic development of Puerto Rico, in relation to the wellbeing of the natural environment. Examples may include pollution caused by solid waste, biomedical waste, air and water pollution, and conservation of non-renewable resources.
- ESA.CT3.CC.9. Proposes alternatives that help preserve our ecosystems for future generations, ensuring they include economic development and sustainability.
- ESA.CT3.CC.10. Analyzes patterns in changes that are produced in nature, and discusses effective ways to use science knowledge and the scientific method to diminish the change's effects. Examples of patterns may include data on air pollution, atmospheric phenomena, and changes in the population of various species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.11. Develops solutions to solve problems related with the conservation of exotic species, endangered species, and the extinction of other species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.12. Thinks about and implements a recycling and reusing plan of school and community materials.
- ESA.CT3.CC.13. Builds a model that shows how equilibrium in environmental systems is affected if altered beyond its tolerance capacity.

DOMAIN

Matter and energy in organisms and ecosystems

EXPECTATION ESA.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: Structure and processes - Flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycle and energy transference in ecosystems; Energy in chemical processes; Weather and climate

INDICATOR

- ESA.CB1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CB1.IE.8. Represents and describes the carbon cycle in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on illustrating the biogeochemical cycles. The carbon cycle must be included in oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings).
- ESA.CB1.IE.9. Describes the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration in carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples could be models or include simulations or graphic organizers.
- ESA.CB1.IE.10. Explains the importance of the processes that occur in the cycles: hydrological, carbon and nitrogen with the use of diagrams and models, and justifies the reasons why they are vital for living organisms.
- ESA.CB1.IE.11. Reviews evidence to support the fact that entropy is the main factor of energy loss available in food through the trophic levels.
- ESA.CB1.IE.12. Analyzes the role producers, consumers and

decomposers play in the chain and food web of an ecosystem, establishes connections and explains that the food chain or trophic is an example of the survival interrelationship between species. Includes representing food interdependence through the use of diagrams.

ES.A.CB1.IE.13. Represents the food interdependence with diagrams that illustrate chains and trophic webs, and establishes interdependent relationships between the elements of an ecosystem, between ecosystems themselves, and ecosystems and the planet.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.A.IT.1.

Design for engineering- Defines and delimits engineering problems; develops possible solutions; Improves a design

INDICATOR ES.A.IT.1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.A.IT.1.IT.1.

Analyzes a major global challenge impact to specify the limitations and quantitative specifications of the solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.2.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and more manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.3.

Proposes effective forms to raise awareness and promote possible solutions for environmental problems such as air, soil, and water pollution, waste management, species and resource protection, and also sustainable development.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.9.

Identifies innovative projects that permit development in a sustainable way.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.10.

Explains, with examples, how technology impacts life quality from an economic, social and environmental point of view.

ES.A.IT.1.IT.11.

Analyzes situations and takes individual and group decisions in the light of environmental problems.

CONTENT STANDARD

PR.ES.B.

Biology

DOMAIN

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: structures and processes - Structure and function; flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycles and energy transference in ecosystems; Organism's development and growth

INDICATOR ES.B.CB1.EM.

Structure and organization levels of matter

ES.B.CB1.EM.1.

Uses models of cell types to establish differences between the organelles and their functions, including the nucleus, that contains the genetic material that determines heredity.

ES.B.CB1.EM.2.

Analyzes the structure of DNA and RNA molecules and their replication by means of tridimensional models.

ES.B.CB1.EM.3.

Explains, using scientific evidence, how DNA's structure

		determines the structure of proteins that perform the essential functions of life thru specialized cell systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.4.	Uses a model to illustrate the rank organization and interaction of systems that realize specific functions within multicellular organisms. Includes the human body systems such as: digestive, circulatory and immunological, skeletal, muscular, nervous, excretory, reproductive, integumentary and endocrinological systems.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.5.	Plans and realizes a research to provide evidence that the reaction mechanisms keep homeostasis. Examples of research may include the average of heartbeats in reaction to exercise, the reaction of stomas to humidity and temperature, a root's development in reaction to water levels.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.6.	Represents with concept maps or graph organizers, the relationship between the processes that occur in the mitochondria of cells during cellular respiration.
	ES.B.CB1.EM.7.	Builds diagrams and models to represent the changes that occur during the cellular division phases and cellular differentiation, when producing and keeping complex organisms.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB1.IE.1.	Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on making models of biogeochemical cycles that include carbon cycles in the oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) providing the base for living organisms.
	ES B.CB1.IE.2.	Builds and revises an explanation based on evidence on how carbon, hydrogen and oxygen of sugar molecules can combine with other elements to form amino-acids and other carbon molecules. Emphasis is on the use of models and simulations that support this explanation.
	ES B.CB1.IE.3.	Develops a model that illustrates that cellular respiration is a chemical process by which food molecule links and oxygen molecules break-up and form new links, resulting in a net energy transference. Emphasis is on conceptual understanding of entry and exit processes during cellular respiration.
	ES B.CB1.IE.4.	Uses models to illustrate how photosynthesis and respiration transform light energy into stored chemical energy. Emphasis is on the illustration of entry and exit of matter and the transference and transformation of energy in photosynthesis by plants and other photosynthetic organisms. Examples of models can include diagrams, chemical equations and conceptual models.
	ES B.CB1.IE.5.	Collects information about macromolecules (proteins, lipids, carbon hydrates, nucleic acids) that compose a cell and uses it to explain that spatial atom distribution in these determine some of their functions in living organisms.

	ES B.CB1.IE.6.	Explains thru models, the function and structure of cellular membrane in relation to particle movement in biotic and abiotic systems such as: diffusion and osmosis.
	ES B.CB1.IE.7.	Collects evidence to explain that the protein synthesis process is essential in the enzyme production that regulates all the processes that the cell realizes.
DOMAIN		Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics
EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB2.	Ecosystems: Interactions, energy and dynamics - Interdependent relationships in ecosystems; Dynamics, functioning and resistance of ecosystems; Cyclical movement of matter and energy transference in ecosystems; Social interactions and group behavior; Human beings and biodiversity; Development of a possible solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB2.EM.1.	Uses mathematical or technological representations to support explanations about the factors that affect the carrying capacity of ecosystems at different scales. Emphasis is on the quantitative analysis and relationship comparison between interdependent factors including limits, resources, climate and competition. Examples of mathematical comparisons may include graphs, tables, histograms, and population changes collected from simulations and historical data.
	ES.B.CB2.EM.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support and revise the explanations based on evidence about the factors that affect biodiversity and populations in ecosystems ant different scales. Examples of mathematical representations include finding an average, determine trends or patterns, and use comparative graphs of a variety of data.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.B.CB2.IE.1.	Builds and revises an explanation, based on evidence, about the cycles of matter and energy flow in aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of aerobic and anaerobic respiration in different environments.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.2.	Uses mathematical representations to support statements on matter's cycles and energy flow between organisms of an ecosystem. Emphasis is on the use of mathematical models of energy storage in biomass, to describe the flow transference of energy thru ecosystems. Emphasis is on atoms and molecules (such as carbon, oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) that are kept as they pass thru an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.3.	Develops models to illustrate the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples of models could include simulations and mathematical models. The evaluation does not include the specific chemical steps of photosynthesis and respiration.
	ES.B.CB2.IE.4.	Evaluates statements, evidence and reasoning that

complex interactions of ecosystems keep the number and type of organisms in a relatively consistent way in stable conditions. But changes in the conditions may result in a new ecosystem. Examples of changes in the conditions of an ecosystem may include small changes, either physical or biological such as temporary hunting or flooding; or extreme changes as volcanic eruptions and increase in sea levels.

INDICATOR	ES.B.CB2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB2.CC.1.	Identifies environmental factors to discuss the negative and positive effects of population growth.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.2.	Builds a model that represents and explains the step sequence of ecological succession states in an ecosystem.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.3.	Explains the relationship between populations, communities and ecosystems of the biosphere.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.4.	Designs, evaluates and refines a solution to reduce the impact of human activities in the environment and biodiversity. Examples of the activities may include urbanization, dam construction, dissemination of invading species.
	ES.B.CB2.CC.5.	Evaluates scientific evidence of group behavior of individuals and the opportunity they have to survive and reproduce. Emphasis is on : (1) distinguishing between group and individual behavior, (2) identifying evidence that supports the results of group behavior and (3) developing logical and reasonable arguments based on evidence. Examples of group behavior may include flocks, herds and cooperative behaviors such as hunting, migrations and swarms.

DOMAIN

Heredity and characteristic variations

EXPECTATION	ES.B.CB3.	Heredity and characteristic variations - Structure and function; Characteristic heredity; Characteristic variations
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB3.EM.	Structure and organization level of matter
	ES.B.CB3.EM.1.	Poses questions to clarify the relationship of DNA's role and chromosomes in the instruction codes for the characteristic variations that pass from one generation to another.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB3.CC.1.	Poses and defends a statement based on evidence about the genetic and hereditary variations that can result from: (1) new genetic combination thru the meiosis process, (2) viable errors that may occur during DNA replication and/or (3) mutations caused by environmental factors. Emphasis is on the use of data to support arguments on the different forms in which mutations can occur.
	ES.B.CB3.CC.2.	Applies statistical and probability concepts to explain the variation and distribution of visible characteristics in a population. Emphasis is on the use of mathematics to describe the probability and characteristic presence that are related to genetics and environmental factors., as

well as representing phenotypic and genotypic proportions in different genetic crossings.

ES.B.CB3.CC.3. Recognizes and explains that multicellular organisms are developed from a simple zygote and that the resulting phenotype will depend on the genotype that was established at the moment of fertilization.

ES.B.CB3.CC.4. Explains the importance of life's continuity thru the action of genes, hereditary patterns, organism reproduction and cell reproduction.

DOMAIN

Natural selection and evolution

EXPECTATION ES.B.CB4.

Biological evolution: Unity and diversity - Evidence of common ancestors and diversity; Adaptation; Natural selection; Biodiversity and human beings; Development of a possible solution

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.EM.

Structure and organization level of matter

ES.B.CB4.EM.1.

Communicates scientific information that biological evolution and common ancestors are supported by multiple lines of empiric evidence. Emphasis is on the conceptual understanding of the role of each evidence line has and biological in relation to the common ancestor evidence and biological evolution. Examples of evidence may include similarities in the DNA sequences, anatomic structures and development appearance order of embryological structures.

INDICATOR ES.B.CB4.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.B.CB4.IE.1.

Builds an explanation based on evidence that the evolution process mainly results from four factors: (1) a species potential to increase in quantity, (2) the genetic variation of individuals in a species by mutation or sexual reproduction, (3) the competition for limited resources that each individual needs to survive and reproduce in the environment, and (4) ensure the proliferation of those organisms that are more able to survive and reproduce in the environment. Emphasis is on the use of evidence to explain the influence that the four factors have on the number of organisms, behaviors, morphology, or physiology, in terms of the ability to compete for limited resources and subsequently, in the individual survival and adaptation of species. Examples of evidence may include mathematical models as a simple distribution graph and proportional reasoning.

ES.B.CB4.IE.2.

Determines the effects of the different types of natural selection in the gene set (gene pool) of an organism.

ES.B.CB4.IE.3.

Applies statistical and probability concepts to support explanations about organisms with advantageous hereditary characteristics that tend to increase in proportion comparing to those that don't have the same characteristics. Emphasis is on the change analysis in the numerical distribution of the characteristics and on using these changes as evidence to support explanation on how natural selection determines the survival capacity for groups of organisms.

ES.B.CB4.IE.4.

Builds an explanation based on evidence on how natural

		selection leads to the adaptation of populations. Emphasis is on using data to provide evidence on how biotic and abiotic differences in ecosystems (seasonal temperature changes, long period climate changes, light, acidity, geographic barriers, or evolution of other organisms) contribute to gene changes throughout time, leading to adaptation of the population. Hardy Weinberg's principle is integrated to quantify the process of natural selection in a population.
	ES.B.CB4.IE.5.	Evaluates the role of natural selection in the development of the Theory of Evolution.
INDICATOR	ES.B.CB4.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.B.CB4.CC.1.	Evaluates the evidence that supports the statements that changes in the environmental conditions may result in: (1) increase in the number of individuals of a species, (2) emergence of new species, (3) extinction of other species. Emphasis is on determining the cause-effect relationships on how environmental changes, such as deforestation, fishing, use of fertilizers, drought, flooding and rate of environmental changes, affect the distribution or disappearance of species' characteristics.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.2.	Reviews and evaluates a simulation to test a solution that decreases the adverse impacts of human activities in biodiversity. Emphasis is on the design of solutions for a proposed problem that is related to a threatened species or in danger of extinction; or with genetic variation of multiple species organisms.
	ES.B.CB4.CC.3.	Analyzes how human beings have the responsibility to keep the environment in good condition for the survival of species.
DOMAIN		Design for engineering
EXPECTATION	ES.B.IT1.	Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Optimizes the design solution
INDICATOR	ES.B.IT1.IT.	Design for Engineering
	ES.B.IT1.IT.1.	Analyzes a major global challenge to specify the limitations and quantitative criteria of solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.2.	Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be resolved using engineering knowledge.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.3.	Evaluates a real and complex problem solution based on criteria as costs, benefits, security, trustworthiness, and aesthetics considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.
	ES.B.IT1.IT.4.	Uses a computer simulation to model the impact of proposed solutions to solve a real and complex problem with multiple criteria and limitations within and between the relevant systems to the problem.
CONTENT	PR.ES.F.	Physics

STANDARD

DOMAIN

Forces and interactions

EXPECTATION ES.FCF2.

Movement and stability: Forces and interactions - Force and movement; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems

INDICATOR ES.FCF2.EM.

Structure and organization levels of matter

ES.FCF2.EM.1.

Explains what fluids are and describes how these create pressure on a surface. (surface tension)

ES.FCF2.EM.2.

Explains and describes how the surface tension principles and types of fluids affect mechanization. Emphasis is on applying the kinetic-molecular theory.

INDICATOR ES.FCF2.IE.

Interactions and energy

ES.FCF2.IE.1.

Designs a model to explain the movement of a dimension through verbal, graphic and mathematic descriptions. Emphasis is on the movement's description through the concepts of: distance, displacement, speed, velocity and acceleration. The use of the units from the International Measurement System must be integrated, and also their conversions, significant digits, scientific notation and mathematical equations.

ES.FCF2.IE.2.

Identifies and describes the four fundamental forces in everyday life: strong nuclear interaction, weak nuclear interaction, gravity and electromagnetism.

ES.FCF2.IE.3.

Uses knowledge on the different movement laws to apply them in problem solutions of everyday life. Emphasis is on the Newton, Coulomb and Kepler laws.

ES.FCF2.IE.4.

Uses Newton's second law of motion when describing the mathematical relationship between net force on a macroscopic object, its mass and acceleration. Data examples may include tables or position or velocity graphs as time function for objects subject to a non-balanced net force, such as an object in free-fall, and object rolling on a ramp or an object in movement pulled by a constant force.

ES.FCF2.IE.5.

Uses mathematical representations of Newton's gravitational law and Coulomb's law, to describe and predict gravitational and electrostatic forces between objects.

ES.FCF2.IE.6.

Explains the functioning of machines, using force and movement concepts that are useful or resolve an everyday-life problem.

ES.FCF2.IE.7.

Uses mathematical representations to describe movement in two dimensions and the force equilibrium with vectors. Represents and calculates the magnitude and direction of vector quantities by graph and mathematical methods applying the basic trigonometrical functions. Projectile motion and inclined plane are included.

ES.FCF2.IE.8.

Designs an experiment to explain the principles and applications of uniform circular movement and simple harmonic movement.

	ES.FCF2.IE.9.	Applies scientific and engineering ideas to design and evaluate an apparatus that minimizes the force on a macroscopic object during collision. The examples may include a helmet or parachute.
	ES.FCF2.IE.10.	Explains the concepts of electrical charge, electric current, electric potential, electric field, and magnetic field, and establishes the difference between contact forces and long-range forces. Explains the properties of conductive materials and designs electrical circuits in series and in parallel.
	ES.FCF2.IE.11.	Offers experimental evidence that an electric current may produce a magnetic field and a magnetic field may produce an electric current.
	ES.FCF2.IE.12.	Describes apparatus that resolve everyday-life problems and those which result from the application of physics. Examples of force may be: electrical, magnetic, gravitational and nuclear forces. Examples of apparatus may include those that use conductors, circuits and fields.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF2.CC.	Conservation and change
	ES.FCF2.CC.1.	Uses mathematical representations to support the premise that the total momentum of a system of objects is preserved when the net force on the system is zero.
DOMAIN		Energy
EXPECTATION	ES.FCF3.	Energy - Definitions of energy; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Energy in chemical processes in everyday-life.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ES.FCF3.EM.1.	Explains energy in terms of scale, from atomic scale to macroscopic scale.
	ES.FCF3.EM.2.	Classifies energy as kinetic or potential and contrasts the different types: thermal, chemical, nuclear, electromagnetic and mechanical. Calculates the kinetic and potential energy changes in a system.
	ES.FCF3.EM.3.	Classifies and explains the origin of different sources of energy: fossil-fuels, solar, geothermic, wind, hydraulic, biomass, among others.
	ES.FCF3.EM.4.	Explains the relationship between energy, work, and power.
	ES.FCF3.EM.5.	Explains the work-energy theorem.
	ES.FCF3.EM.6.	Identifies the electrical phenomena as a manifestation of the charges of subatomic particles (electrons).
	ES.FCF3.EM.7.	Compares electric and magnetic forces regarding the field and its relationship with charges in movement.
	ES.FCF3.EM.8.	Explains the relationships between electrostatic charges using Coulomb's laws.
INDICATOR	ES.FCF3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.FCF3.IE.1.	Calculates the energy change between the components of a system when the energy of one of them is known and the energy flow into or out-of the systems.

- ES.FCF3.IE.2. Designs a model that illustrates that energy at a macroscopic scale may be understood as a combination of energy associated to particle movements (objects) and energy associated to the relative position of particles (objects). Examples of macroscopic scale phenomena may include the conversion of kinetic energy to thermal energy, stored energy in an object positioned over Earth, and stored energy between two electrically charged plates.
- ES.FCF3.IE.3. Designs and refines an apparatus that works within controlled limitations to convert energy from one form into another. Examples of apparatus may include Rube Goldberg, wind turbines, solar cells, solar ovens and generators. Examples of limitations may include the use of renewable energy forms and efficiency.
- ES.FCF3.IE.4. Explains that when two components are combined at different temperatures in an enclosed system, the total transference of thermal energy results in a more uniform energy distribution between the system's components (thermodynamics' second law). Examples of research may include mixing liquids with different initial temperatures or adding different temperature objects to water.
- ES.FCF3.IE.5. Explains the interactions through electrical or magnetic fields to illustrate the forces between objects and energy changes of objects from interaction.
- ES.FCF3.IE.6. Plans and realizes research to propose the use of different energy sources in Puerto Rico, taking into consideration the cost-benefit and cost-effective proportion.

DOMAIN

Waves and their applications

EXPECTATION ES.FCF4.

Waves and their applications to technological development - Wave's properties; Electromagnetic radiation; Information and instrumentation technologies

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.FCF4.EM.1. Explains, through models, the effect of wave's properties in the behavior of matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.2. Distinguishes between the types of mechanical waves: transverse and longitudinal.
- ES.FCF4.EM.3. Explains the idea that electromagnetic radiation can be described with a wave model or particle model, and that in some cases, one of the models is more useful than the other. Examples include how wave and particle models explain the properties of visible light.
- ES.FCF4.EM.4. Explains reflection, refraction, diffraction, polarization, transformation and absorption as manifestations of the interactions between waves and matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.5. Proposes the development of technology that demonstrates the application of light properties in the design of useful prototypes or to resolve a daily-life problem.
- ES.FCF4.EM.6. Explains and describes how wave principles are used to

create useful technologies for humans.

- ES.FCF4.EM.7. Communicates technical information on how some technological apparatus use behavioral principles and interactions of waves with matter to transmit and capture information and energy. Examples may include solar cells that capture light and convert it into electricity, medical imaging, and communication technologies.
- ES.FCF4.EM.8. Evaluates questions about the advantages and disadvantages of the transmission and digital storage of information. Examples of advantages may include that digital information is stable because it can be stored, transferred and copied in a reliable, easy and rapid way in a computer. The disadvantages could be problems related to the deletion, security and theft of information.
- ES.FCF4.EM.9. Evaluates and supports or refutes the validity and reliability of the premises in publications about the effects of distant electromagnetic radiation frequencies when absorbed by matter.
- ES.FCF4.EM.10. Analyzes mirror's and lenses' properties to design beam diagrams that will allow to calculate the location and size of images.
- ES.FCF4.EM.11. Searches for reliable sources of information on the scientific or everyday applications of mirrors and lenses, to make an oral presentation.

INDICATOR

- ES.FCF4.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCF4.IE.1. Analyzes wave behavior as a transference phenomenon of energy.
- ES.FCF4.IE.2. Describes energy transference in mechanic waves, such as sound waves.
- ES.FCF4.IE.3. Describes a model to represent the relationships between wave properties in different environments. Examples must include a model that represents interference and the principle of superposition.
- ES.FCF4.IE.4. Uses mathematical representations to support a premise regarding the relationship between frequencies, length of wave, speed of waves traveling through different environments. Examples of data may include electromagnetic radiation traveling through voids and glass, or seismic waves through Earth.
- ES.FCF4.IE.5. Identifies practical uses of waves, such as seismic data, acoustic effects and Doppler effect.
- ES.FCF4.IE.6. Plans research to demonstrate how waves produce fields that use or generate particles.

DOMAIN

Space systems

EXPECTATION ES.FCT1.

Earth's place in the universe - Planet Earth and the solar system; Universe and the stars; Energy in chemical processes and in everyday life; Electromagnetic radiation

INDICATOR

- ES.FCT1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ES.FCT1.IE.1. Uses mathematical or computational representations to predict the movement of orbital objects in the solar system. Emphasis is on Newton's universal gravitational

law that describes orbital movements, and that are applied to artificial satellites, as well as planets and moons.

- ES.FCT 1.IE.2. Describes and predicts natural phenomena as the movement of celestial bodies, relative movements and others, based on the laws that describe planetary and satellite movements.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.3. Describes the role of nuclear fusion in the Sun's nucleus that releases energy and that at the same time arrives to Earth in the form of radiation. Predicts the Sun's time period using other stars as information base. Emphasis is on energy transference mechanisms that allows nuclear fusion energy from the Sun's center to reach Earth. Examples of evidence for the description may include mass observation and life-span of other stars, as well as solar radiation changes due to sudden Sun flares (spatial climate), 11 yr. Sunspot cycle and the non-cyclical variations through-out the centuries.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.4. Explains the Big Bang theory based on astronomic evidence of light specters, movement in distant galaxies, and the mass composition of the universe. Evidence is on the astronomic evidence from redshift galaxies as indicator that the universe is actually expanding, background radiation microwaves are residues from the Big Bang's radiation, and the study of ordinary mass composition of the universe that is mainly found in stars and interstellar gases (from electromagnetic radiation star specter) that coincides with the predicted Big Bang theory (3/4 hydrogen and 1/4 helium).
- ES.FCT 1.IE.5. Communicates scientific ideas on the types of stars, their life-cycles, and the elements they produce. Emphasis is on nucleosynthesis and the different that create it, as well as the variations as mass function of the star and its life-span.
- ES.FCT 1.IE.6. Describes the condition under which the total mass and energy of the universe are conserved.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.FIT 1.

Design for engineering - Define and delimit engineering problems; Develop possible solutions; Optimize the design solution

INDICATOR

ES.FIT 1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.FIT 1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution to a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.FIT 1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution to a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability, and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.FIT 1.IT.3.

Uses available technological means to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life situations and optimize pre-existing models.

- ES.F.IT.1.IT.4. Explains the functioning and utility of designed models to solve everyday problems.
- ES.F.IT.1.IT.5. Identifies the limitations of developed designs for solutions that consider society's wishes and needs.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ES.Q. Chemistry

DOMAIN

Chemical reactions

EXPECTATION ES.Q.CF1.

Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties of matter; Chemical reactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Development of possible solutions to a scientific problem; Improve the design

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization level of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.1. Describes and explains the different atomic models that have been postulated and the different experiments that led to the discovery of subatomic particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.2. Uses models to explain the atom's structure and its relationship with matter's properties.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.3. Explains the meaning of isotope concept, applies knowledge to determine the average atomic mass of an element and argues on its applications, benefits and risks in different aspects of the real world.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.4. Develops models to represent the changes in the atom's nucleus composition and the energy released during fusion, fission, and radioactive disintegration processes. Examples of models must include mathematical representations.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.5. Reviews the fundamentals of the atom's mechanical-quantum model to write electronic configurations and electronic structure of symbols (Lewis Diagram).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.6. Discusses contributions realized by different scientists in the development of the Periodic Table as a method to order and classify elements based on their properties. Contributions from Dobereiner, John Newlands, Dimitri Mendeleev, Henry Mosely, among others, will be considered.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.7. Uses the periodic table as a model to determine the electronic configuration of elements and explains why elements of a same group have similar properties (periodic properties).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.8. Compares and contrasts the properties of metals, non-metals, metalloids and inert gases, and explains their uses and technological applications, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.9. Identifies and explains the properties that determine the location of an element in a period and a family on the Periodic Table, and uses them to predict the relative properties of other elements. Examples of these can be valence electrons and atomic number.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.10. Uses tendencies or patterns of the represented properties on the Periodic Table (atomic number, atomic mass, electronegativity, oxidation state and others) to

predict the elements' behavior and types of links that they form.

	ES.Q.CF1.EM.11.	Describes the processes by which substances are combined to form different chemical compositions and applies the naming convention of names and formulas of ionic and covalent compounds. The naming convention of positive and negative monoatomic and polyatomic ions are integrated based on their number of oxidation.
INDICATOR	ES.Q.CF1.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.1.	Analyzes and interprets data on the properties of substances before and after interacting, to determine if a chemical reaction has happened. Examples of reactions may include burning sugar, wool-steel, and combining zinc or iron with hydrochloric acid.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.2.	Classifies chemical reactions and identifies the characteristics that distinguish them. (Combustion reactions, synthesis, etc).
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.3.	Develops and uses a model to describe how the total number of atoms does not change in a chemical reaction, and therefore mass is conserved. Emphasis is on Matter's Conservation Law and physical models and diagrams, including digital forms that represent atoms.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.4.	Designs a project to prove and modify a mechanism that releases or absorbs thermal energy in a chemical process. Emphasis is on the design, controlling the energy transference toward and from the environment, and the mechanism's modification using variables such as the type and concentration of a substance.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.5.	Creates a model that illustrates the absorption or release of energy in a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the idea that a chemical reaction is a system that produces changes of energy. Examples of models could include diagrams of reactions at a molecular level.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.6.	Applies principles and scientific evidence to provide an explanation about the effects of temperature changes or of particle concentration involved in the speed of a reaction. Emphasis is on the student's reasoning to focus on the number of particles and the energy of collision between molecules.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.7.	Evaluates the design of a chemical system specifying what change in the condition would produce an increase in the quantity of the product in equilibrium. Emphasis is on applying the Le Chatelier principle and on refining designs of chemical reaction systems, including descriptions of the connections between changes made at a macroscopic level, and what happens at a molecular level. Examples of design may include different ways of increasing the formation of a product when including the addition or extraction of reactives or products.
	ES.Q.CF1.IE.8.	Uses mathematical representations to determine the stoichiometry of reactions and support the statement that atoms, and therefore, mass, are conserved during a chemical reaction. Emphasis is on the use of

mathematical ideas to communicate the proportional relationships between atom's mass in reactives and products. Emphasis is also on the student's evaluation on the use of mathematical thinking and not on memorizing or memorized technique application to solve problems.

- ES.Q.CF1.IE.9. Analyzes the form in which energy is manifested and transformed from one form to another, for example, from chemical to thermal energy and from light to electric.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.10. Describes the temperature and heat flow in terms of random movement and atom and molecule vibrations.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.11. Explains how the transformation of energy is produced and vice versa during a nuclear reaction when applying the equation $\Delta E = \Delta mc^2$.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.12. Evaluates the process that occurs during a chemical reaction in terms of chemical energy transformation. Examples include necessary activation energy, absorption, and energy release during the reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.13. Explains that absorbed or released heat in a chemical reaction comes from the total energy involved in the process of forming and breaking links.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.14. Calculates the quantity of absorbed or released heat by a substance or by a chemical reaction when temperature changes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.15. Explains the difference between the concepts of enthalpy, entropy, and free energy, and how these determine the spontaneity of chemical reactions.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.16. Uses Hess's law to determine the change in enthalpy of a chemical reaction.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.17. Explains the acid-base reactions and their application in chemical or biological processes.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.18. Explains the relationship between the structure of molecules, chemical links and chemical energy.
- ES.Q.CF1.IE.19. Evaluates new energetic options such as hydrogen, ethanol, carbon, waste incineration and others, with their economic and environmental implications.

DOMAIN

Structure and properties of matter

EXPECTATION ES.Q.CF1.

Matter and its interactions - Structure and properties; Nuclear processes; Types of interactions; Stability and instability in physical systems; Energy conservation and transference; Relationship between forces and energy; Definitions of energy

INDICATOR

- ES.Q.CF1.EM. Structure and organization levels of matter
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.12. Discriminates between extensive and intensive physical properties of matter and analyzes varied examples of situations where the material's property is fundamental for diverse uses. Examples include density, ductility, conductivity, etc.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.13. Communicates scientific and technical information on why the structure at a molecular level is important for the functioning of the design of materials. Examples may

include why materials that conduct electricity are usually made of metal, that long-lasting flexible materials are made of linked molecules, and that pharmaceutical products are designed to interact with specific receptors.

- ES.Q.CF1.EM.14. Analyzes the kinetic-molecular theory to describe and explain the physical properties of matter's states through a model.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.15. Relates the thermal energy content of a material with the movement of particles that compose it according to the kinetic-molecular theory.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.16. Explains the temperature concepts in terms of average kinetic energy content of particles.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.17. Describes and compares the crystalline structure and properties of different types of solids.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.18. Relates the properties of liquids (viscosity, superficial tension, capillary action and others) with intermolecular forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.19. Develops a model to predict and describe the changes in particle movement, temperature and state of a substance when there is energy change (addition or subtraction). Emphasis is on molecular quantitative models of solids, liquids and gases to demonstrate that changes in thermal energy affect the particles' kinetic energy until a change of state occurs. Example of a model is phase diagram of water and CO₂.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.20. Collects information on the attraction forces between molecules to compare the structure of different substances and infer on the intensity of forces between particles. Examples of forces are dispersion and dipole forces.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.21. Describes matter's classification system based on its characteristic properties (homogeneous and heterogeneous materials, substances, mixtures, solutions, etc) and applies them to explain its behavior.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.22. Designs and practices a procedure that applies adequate methods to separate mixtures and identifies substances present within, considering their properties. Offers examples of utility and application of these processes in the real world (filtration, chromatography, etc).
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.23. Analyzes the properties of solutions based on the properties of their components. Examples include solute and dissolvent, types of solutions (liquid-solid, liquid-gas, etc), solution concentration (diluted, saturated, oversaturated), factors that affect solubility, solubility curves, colligative properties, solvation (dissolution) process and forces between solute and dissolvent.
- ES.Q.CF1.EM.24. Analyzes the oxidation and reduction reactions to explain how they manifest in natural processes and identifies their applications in industry.

- INDICATOR ES.Q.CF1.CC. Conservation and change
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.1. Analyzes the process by which chemical reactions reach

an equilibrium.

- ES.Q.CF1.CC.2. Analyzes and interprets data that shows that total mass and energy in the universe are always conserved.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.3. Evaluates Matter's Conservation Law to describe the changes that exist in a chemical reaction and establishes that in a chemical reaction the type and quantity of atoms are conserved even-though their combination form is changed. Emphasis is on the writing of chemical equations and the balance of these.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.4. Analyzes and interprets data to apply the mole concept in the calculation of empiric and molecular formulas, stoichiometric relationships and to express the concentration of a solution (molarity).
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.5. Identifies stoichiometric relationships in a chemical reaction and calculates the theoretical yield and the actual yield in balanced chemical equations. (Percent Yield)
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.6. Applies the gas laws to explain the relationship and effects of changes in pressure, temperature and volume in situations like building aerostats, climate changes and scuba-diving tanks, among others.
- ES.Q.CF1.CC.7. Collects evidence to explain how human activities interfere in climate changes, global warming and increased greenhouse effect gases, and proposes alternatives to minimize the effects, both locally and worldwide.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ES.Q.IT1.

Design for engineering - Defines and delimits engineering problems; Develops possible solutions; Improves the design

INDICATOR

ES.Q.IT1.IT.

Design for engineering

ES.Q.IT1.IT.1.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.2.

Evaluates a solution for a real and complex problem based on criteria as cost, benefit, security, reliability and aesthetic considerations, as well as possible social, cultural and environmental impacts.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.3.

Uses technological means within reach to design prototypes, models and alternatives to solve everyday life problems and optimize the utility of existing models.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.4.

Explains the functioning and use of models designed to solve everyday life problems.

ES.Q.IT1.IT.5.

Identifies the limitations of engineering designs to review the system and make decisions as to their use.

CONTENT
STANDARD

PR.ESA.

Environmental Sciences

DOMAIN

History of Earth

EXPECTATION	ESA.CT1.	Earth's place in the universe - Earth's history; Tectonic plates and interaction systems on a large scale; Nuclear processes
INDICATOR	ESA.CT1.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT1.CC.1.	Evaluates evidence on the movement of continental and oceanic crusts in the past and in the present, as well as, the Theory of Tectonic Plates to explain the age of the crust's rocks. Emphasis is on the evidence that tectonic plates present to explain the age of rocks on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.2.	Describes the structure and changes that occur on Earth's crust.
	ESA.CT1.CC.3.	Explains the current geography of the island of Puerto Rico examining its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.4.	Analyzes geological phenomena based on the Theory of Tectonic Plates.
	ESA.CT1.CC.5.	Explains the geological evolution of Puerto Rico, identifying the tectonic plates around the island that have contributed to its geological evolution.
	ESA.CT1.CC.6.	Identifies and describes the properties and formation of different minerals, and their location in Puerto Rico.
	ESA.CT1.CC.7.	Reviews obtained evidence from old materials from planet Earth, meteorites, and planetary surfaces, and uses it to build an explanation of the history and formation of Earth. Emphasis is on the use of available evidence within the solar system for reconstructing planet Earth's history. Examples of evidence include the age of materials (obtained by radiometric data of meteorites, lunar rocks, and the most antique minerals on Earth), the size and composition of objects in the solar system and the impact records of craters on Earth's surface.
	ESA.CT1.CC.8.	Explains the historical development of environmental education and Science progress in this area to maintain and /or recover planet Earth's wellbeing. Examples of values in environmental science may include a discussion of careers in environmental sciences and their implications in society.
DOMAIN		Earth's systems
EXPECTATION	ESA.CT2.	Earth's systems - Earth and the solar system; Tectonic plates and interaction systems at a large scale; Earth's materials and systems; Biogeology; Water's role in the processes of Earth's surface; Weather and climate
INDICATOR	ESA.CT2.EM.	Structure and organization levels of matter
	ESA.CT2.EM.1.	Describes water's properties and their effects of Earth's materials and processes of the surface. Emphasis is on chemical and mechanical investigations with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between hydrological cycles and interaction systems known commonly as the rock cycle. Examples of research may include: transport and deposit of rivers using flow diagrams and erosion using a content variety

on soil moisture. Examples of chemical research include weathering, erosion and re-crystallization or fusion generation (when examining how water decreases the fusion temperature of most solids).

- ESA.CT2.EM.2. Explains the importance of water for organisms and the need to protect this resource.
- ESA.CT2.EM.3. Builds an argument based on evidence of the co-evolution of Earth's systems and life on Earth. Emphasis is on the cause, effects and reaction of the dynamics between the biosphere and other Earth systems by which geo-science factors control the evolution of life, that at the same time continuously alters Earth's surface. Examples include how photosynthetic life alters the atmosphere by means of oxygen production, which at the same time increases the wear index and permits the evolution of animal life; or how evolution of coral reefs alter the erosion patterns and deposition of the coastlines and provide a habitat for the evolution of new life forms.
- ESA.CT2.EM.4. Collects evidence on the geological origin, location, and importance of Puerto Rico's natural resources and compares that evidence with that of other major Antilles islands. Examples of natural resources may include minerals, elements, forests and other non-renewable and renewable resources.
- ESA.CT2.EM.5. Identifies the characteristics of the natural environment of a tropical region to establish a contrast with the natural environments of other regions of the world.
- ESA.CT2.EM.6. Classifies and describes the characteristics, location and importance of Puerto Rico's forests. Compares other forests on Earth with tropical forests.
- INDICATOR ESA.CT2.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CT2.IE.1. Describes how internal and superficial Earth processes operate at different scales to conform the characteristics of continental and oceanic floors. Emphasis is on how the appearance of the characteristics of terrestrial surfaces (mountains, valleys, plains) and characteristics of oceanic floors (pits, ridges and oceanic mountains) are the result of both constructive forces (vulcanism, tectonic elevations, orogeny) and destructive forces (weathering, sedimentation mass and coastline erosion).
- ESA.CT2.IE.2. Analyzes geosciences data to affirm that a change on Earth's surface can generate a reaction that causes changes in other terrestrial systems. Examples must include the reactions that occur and affect climate, such as the result of greenhouse gases that cause the increase in temperatures that melt glacial ice, which reduces the quantity of solar rays that reflect on Earth's surface that cause an increase in surface temperature and further reduces the quantity of ice. Also, the loss of vegetation causes an increase in soil erosion; and damming rivers increases the recharge of subterraneous water, decreases sediment transport and increases coastline erosion.

- ESA.CT2.IE.3. Identifies human activities that intervene with the effect of global climate changes, analyzes diverse alternatives that permit minimizing this and evaluates the levels of local and international efforts to counteract the increase of greenhouse effect gases in the atmosphere.
- ESA.CT2.IE.4. Explains the relationship between energy and frequency of natural phenomena.
- ESA.CT2.IE.5. Examines why earthquakes happen and how their intensity is measured.
- ESA.CT2.IE.6. Develops a model of Earth's interior to describe the cycles of matter by thermal convection. Emphasis is on both the unidimensional model of Earth (with radial rays determined by density) and the tridimensional model which is controlled by convection of Earth's crust and tectonic plates.
- ESA.CT2.IE.7. Uses a model to describe how the flow variation of energy in and out of Earth's systems, results in climate changes. Examples include the evaluation of results in climate changes that are limited to temperature changes on the surface, precipitation patterns, volume of glacial ice, sea level, and biosphere distribution. Include the relationship between matter's cycles and energy flow, in the light of the Matter and Energy Conservation Law.
- ESA.CT2.IE.8. Obtains evidence that heat is absorbed or released in an ecosystem to compare the effect in the diverse ecosystems of Puerto Rico. Examples may include coastlines, urban areas, forests, mountains.
- ESA.CT2.IE.9. Recognizes that the major cause of climatological events on planet Earth is related to the interaction of solar energy with Earth, atmosphere and seas.
- ESA.CT2.IE.10. Plans and conducts research on water's properties and their effects on Earth's materials and surface processes. Emphasis is on the chemical and mechanical research with water and solid materials to provide evidence of the connections between the hydrologic cycle and interaction systems, also known as the rock cycle.
- ESA.CT2.IE.11. Discusses the importance of aquatic ecosystems for the water dependent species and proposes alternatives for their conservation.
- ESA.CT2.IE.12. Describes the importance of hydrologic sciences.
- ESA.CT2.IE.13. Develops a quantitative model to describe the cycle of carbon between the hydrosphere and atmosphere. Emphasis is on modeling biogeochemical cycles that include the carbon cycle by the ocean, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings) when providing the base for living organisms.
- ESA.CT2.IE.14. Uses models and diagrams to explain the patterns of oceanic currents and winds that affect Puerto Rico and all the Caribbean.

DOMAIN

Human sustainability

EXPECTATION ESA.CT3.

Earth and human activity - Global climate change; natural resources; Weather and climate; Natural

		disasters; Human impact on Earth's systems; development of possible solutions
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.IE.	Interactions and energy
	ESA.CT3.IE.1.	Identifies how the historic origin of cities and human communities have affected populations in urban and rural zones.
	ESA.CT3.IE.2.	Evaluates the effect of human beings on communities and the capacity of planet Earth to support populations. Emphasis should include the capacity of having sufficient natural resources to satisfy the basic needs such as water, food and shelter.
	ESA.CT3.IE.3.	Describes the value of ecosystems and argues on the importance of their conservation and protection, and conservation and protection of their organisms, including specificity of the ecosystems and organisms of Puerto Rico. Emphasis must be on native organisms of Puerto Rico. Gives examples of organisms that are in salt-water, fresh-water, mangrove, beach, rocky-coast, coral reef ecosystems.
	ESA.CT3.IE.4.	Describes the use of common energy sources such as: fossil fuels, nuclear energy and alternate sources such as: wind, solar, ethanol and hydraulic.
	ESA.CT3.IE.5.	Explains the advantages and disadvantages, including economic impact, of the uses of energy that provide available resources and possible energy alternatives, analyzing the impact of fossil resource exploitation of the environment.
	ESA.CT3.IE.6.	Evaluates documents and announcements on the laws and government propositions on environmental conservation. Examples of laws or propositions would be on the protection of certain species and application of regulations on car emissions.
	ESA.CT3.IE.7.	Describes change patterns and action measures that would protect them in case of natural phenomena, such as earthquakes and hurricanes, according to the different geographic zones in Puerto Rico. Examples of natural phenomena may include hurricanes, earthquakes, tsunamis and storms.
	ESA.CT3.IE.8.	Identifies the effects of hurricanes depending on the geological zone of Puerto Rico.
INDICATOR	ESA.CT3.CC.	Conservation and change
	ESA.CT3.CC.1.	Describes, based on scientific evidence, how the availability of natural resources, natural disasters, and climate changes have influenced human activities. Examples of key natural resources include the access to safe water (as rivers, lakes and subterraneous waters), fertile soil regions as deltas, high mineral concentrations and fossil fuels. Examples of natural disasters could be internal processes (as volcanic eruptions or earthquakes), surface processes (as tsunamis, mass wasting and floor erosion), and severe climate (as hurricanes, floods and droughts). Examples of the results in climate changes that can affect the population or drive

them to massive migrations include changes in sea levels, regional temperature patterns and precipitation, and the types of crop that can be grown.

- ESA.CT3.CC.2. Illustrates using technology, the relationships between the management of natural resources, sustainability of human population and biodiversity. Examples of factors that affect the management of natural resources include the cost of resource's extractions, waste management, per capita consumption and development of new technologies. Examples of factors that affect human sustainability include the agricultural efficiency, levels of conservation and urban planning.
- ESA.CT3.CC.3. Analyzes data from geosciences and the results of global climate models to make predictions based on evidence of current and future changes of regional and global climate, and associates future impacts to Earth's systems. Examples of evidence for data and results of climate models are the climate changes (as precipitation and temperature) and the impacts associated to them (as sea levels, volume of glacial ice, or the atmosphere's and ocean's composition).
- ESA.CT3.CC.4. Uses representations to illustrate the relationships between Earth systems and how these relationships are modified by human activity. Examples of the Earth systems that are found in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, lithosphere and biosphere. An example of the extent of the impact of human activities is the increase of carbon monoxide in the atmosphere leads to an increase of photosynthetic biomass on Earth and an increase of the ocean's acidification, that affect the health of marine organisms and marine population.
- ESA.CT3.CC.5. Evaluates design solutions that are competing to develop, manage and use energy and mineral resources based on cost-benefit indicators. Emphasis is on the conservation, recycling, re-using of resources (as minerals and metals) where possible and minimizing the impacts where not possible. Examples include developing better processes and skills for the use of agricultural soils, mining (for carbon, tar sands, bituminous shale) and pumping (oil and natural gas).
- ESA.CT3.CC.6. Evaluates and proposes a technological solution that reduces human activity impact in natural systems. Examples of impact data on human activities may include the quantities and types of pollutants that are emitted, changes in biomass and diversity of species, change in the surface of land for human use (as the development of urban areas, agriculture and livestock or mining). Examples of limitations for future impacts may vary from local efforts (as reducing, reusing and recycling resources) to large scale efforts, as geo-engineering design solutions (as the alteration of global temperatures by means of great changes in the atmosphere and ocean).
- ESA.CT3.CC.7. Evaluates environmental laws that affect the geography

and topography of Puerto Rico, and proposes solutions to eliminate or reduce the effects of various environmental problems in Puerto Rico. Examples may include deforestation, the use of minerals and fossil resources, and the impacts of agriculture.

- ESA.CT3.CC.8. Proposes solutions considering the scientific and economic development of Puerto Rico, in relation to the wellbeing of the natural environment. Examples may include pollution caused by solid waste, biomedical waste, air and water pollution, and conservation of non-renewable resources.
- ESA.CT3.CC.9. Proposes alternatives that help preserve our ecosystems for future generations, ensuring they include economic development and sustainability.
- ESA.CT3.CC.10. Analyzes patterns in changes that are produced in nature, and discusses effective ways to use science knowledge and the scientific method to diminish the change's effects. Examples of patterns may include data on air pollution, atmospheric phenomena, and changes in the population of various species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.11. Develops solutions to solve problems related with the conservation of exotic species, endangered species, and the extinction of other species.
- ESA.CT3.CC.12. Thinks about and implements a recycling and reusing plan of school and community materials.
- ESA.CT3.CC.13. Builds a model that shows how equilibrium in environmental systems is affected if altered beyond its tolerance capacity.

DOMAIN

Matter and energy in organisms and ecosystems

EXPECTATION ESA.CB1.

From molecules to organisms: Structure and processes - Flow organization of matter and energy in organisms; Matter's cycle and energy transference in ecosystems; Energy in chemical processes; Weather and climate

INDICATOR

- ESA.CB1.IE. Interactions and energy
- ESA.CB1.IE.8. Represents and describes the carbon cycle in the hydrosphere, atmosphere, geosphere and biosphere. Emphasis is on illustrating the biogeochemical cycles. The carbon cycle must be included in oceans, atmosphere, soil and biosphere (including human beings).
- ESA.CB1.IE.9. Describes the role of photosynthesis and cellular respiration in carbon cycles in the biosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and geosphere. Examples could be models or include simulations or graphic organizers.
- ESA.CB1.IE.10. Explains the importance of the processes that occur in the cycles: hydrological, carbon and nitrogen with the use of diagrams and models, and justifies the reasons why they are vital for living organisms.
- ESA.CB1.IE.11. Reviews evidence to support the fact that entropy is the main factor of energy loss available in food through the trophic levels.
- ESA.CB1.IE.12. Analyzes the role producers, consumers and

decomposers play in the chain and food web of an ecosystem, establishes connections and explains that the food chain or trophic is an example of the survival interrelationship between species. Includes representing food interdependence through the use of diagrams.

ESA.CB1.IE.13. Represents the food interdependence with diagrams that illustrate chains and trophic webs, and establishes interdependent relationships between the elements of an ecosystem, between ecosystems themselves, and ecosystems and the planet.

DOMAIN

Design for engineering

EXPECTATION ESA.IT 1.

Design for engineering- Defines and delimits engineering problems; develops possible solutions; Improves a design

INDICATOR ESA.IT 1.IT.

Design for engineering

ESA.IT 1.IT.1.

Analyzes a major global challenge impact to specify the limitations and quantitative specifications of the solutions that consider the wishes and needs of society.

ESA.IT 1.IT.2.

Identifies a possible solution for a real and complex problem, dividing it into smaller and more manageable problems that can be solved using engineering knowledge.

ESA.IT 1.IT.3.

Proposes effective forms to raise awareness and promote possible solutions for environmental problems such as air, soil, and water pollution, waste management, species and resource protection, and also sustainable development.

ESA.IT 1.IT.9.

Identifies innovative projects that permit development in a sustainable way.

ESA.IT 1.IT.10.

Explains, with examples, how technology impacts life quality from an economic, social and environmental point of view.

ESA.IT 1.IT.11.

Analyzes situations and takes individual and group decisions in the light of environmental problems.